

**A critical evaluation on the innovative performance of
Smartphone Industry:**

A case study on Micromax Informatics in India

Ajmal Alikhan

A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirement of
The University of the West of Scotland for the award of
Doctor of Business Administration (DBA)

December 2021

Acknowledgements

It is my pleasure to acknowledge the roles of several individuals who were an instrument for completion of my DBA research.

At the very top of my list is my supervisor, Prof Amare Desta. Prof Desta encouraged me to pursue this project and guided me to pursue my doctoral education. I truly enjoyed working with him in a research environment that stimulates original thinking and initiative and his innovative ideas and stoic patience are greatly appreciated. Prof Desta must have spent the past several months in a constant state of reading, commenting and editing. I therefore can't thank him enough for his patience, commitment, and ability to always be positive. In some small way, however, I hope that this thesis will be able to say thank you Prof. Desta for everything.

I must also thank my dearest wife, Nejila Mohammed, for her patient acceptance of less than my 50% contribution to our partnership in the last few months. My most profound appreciation will also be extended to my family in India for their patience and understanding. With regards to numerous questions about my future academic endeavours from family and then shall answer in the words of Sir Winston Churchill: "Now, this is not the end. It is not even the beginning of the future. But it is, perhaps, the end of the beginning"

I would also like to acknowledge helpful suggestions from my cohort members: Sreeraj Sreerenjan, Tharwat Khalil, Shobha Harebasur and Aishwarya Tiku.

This study would have been not so enjoyable without the support of the University of West of Scotland. I would Like to recognise the essential roles of the administration team, the lectures and the entire staff of the university.

Author's Declaration

I hereby declare that the material contained in this thesis have not been previously submitted for a degree in this or any other university. I further declare that this thesis is solely based on my own research. I am also declaring that all information has been obtained and presented in accordance with academic rules and ethical conduct.

Ajmal Alikhan

Abstract

There is evidence which suggest that smartphone industry is an active platform experiencing steady growth and demand. The industry is contented with tough competition from different Smartphone companies and thus innovations are considered as buzz word in the industry. Smartphone manufacturers are very keen on assessing the upcoming trends in the market and thereby establishing the updates in the technology in to their existing and new products. The main purpose of the current research study was therefore to evaluate the innovation performances of Indian Smartphone sector using the case of Micromax Informatics as an example.

This research sought to understand the impact of innovation performance of Micromax from the perspective of the various stakeholders. This included surveys and interviews with the aim of gaining first hand in-depth information about the Smartphone product. This research led DBA project also sought to identify the challenges, constraints and lessons learned on innovation performance from the experiences of diverse stakeholders in India smartphone industry's in the context of developing nations.

The sample size considered for the interview and survey was 10 managers and 100 customers respectively. By conducting survey with the customers, the researcher gathered a wealth of evidence about the performances of Micromax products. The user's opinion about the Micromax smartphones was identified by conducting survey with the customers and further interview were held with managers regarding the performances of their product in line with the trends in the industry.

The results suggest that, despite the interest and enthusiasm of Micromax for introducing Smartphones, the views of different authors are much more mixed regarding the performance of Micromax which is further exacerbated by the challenges coming from the competitors. Furthermore, there was evidence of the lack of innovative ideas and products of Micromax including not introducing the 4G when in line with the competitors. The main challenges observed when introducing Smartphones were a lack of detailed analysis of competitors and the rival.

Key words:

India, Smartphones; Innovation; Concerns-Based Adoption Model and Qualitative Research.

Contents

Acknowledgements.....	2
Abstract.....	4
List of Tables, Figures and Charts.....	9
Chapter 1: Introduction.....	10
1.1 Overview	10
1.2 Intentions of research	10
1.3 Problematizing the innovative performance of Micromax Informatics	13
1.3.1 History of innovation in India	13
1.3.2 The innovative performance of India and Micromax Informatics	14
1.3.3 Core problems	16
1.4 Research Questions.....	21
1.5 Hypothesis	21
1.6 Objectives	21
1.7 Significance of this study and chosen topic.....	22
1.8 Structure of the work	23
1.9 Summary	24
Chapter 2: Literature Review.....	25
2.1 Introduction	25
2.2 Defining Innovation performance	26
2.3 Innovation strategies and organisational performance	27
2.4 Innovation strategies for Smart Phone Sector	27
2.5 Smartphone Services benefits and Outcomes	29
2.6 Theories of innovation for business development	33
2.6.1 Hall's Concerns-Based Adoption Model	33
2.6.2 Schumpeter's Theory of Innovation	35
2.6.3 The Doblin Framework or ten types of innovation.....	36
2.6.4 Roger's Diffusion Model	38
2.7 Innovation process and various barriers of performance innovations.....	40
2.8 Latest trends and technologies in smartphone sector	45
2.9 Evolution of Micromax	50
2.10 Influence of innovation enablers on innovation performance of smartphoneenterprises.....	54

2.11 Study on the evolution of Smartphone industry in India since last decade...	59
2.12 Prevalence of Smartphone Addiction in India	61
2.13 Research Gap	62
2.14 Proposed Conceptual Frame work	64
2.15 Summary	65
Chapter 3: Research methodology.....	67
3.1 Introduction.....	67
3.2 Rationale for selecting the study	67
3.3 Research design	72
3.4 Staging the research	75
3.5 Overview of the fieldwork procedure.....	78
3.6 Identifying the stakeholder participants.....	80
3.7 Piloting	84
3.8 Observing and interviewing informants	87
3.9 Interpreting, reducing and analysing data.....	90
3.10 Appraising and the research design	91
3.11 Ethical issues.....	93
3.12 Limitations of the study	94
3.13 Summary	94
Chapter 4: Research Findings.....	96
4.1 Introduction	96
4.2 Plan of analysis	96
4.3 Quantitative Analysis	97
4.4 Qualitative analysis	111
4.5 Judgement of findings	128
Objective 1: To gain insights into the contributors to innovation performance in the Indian Smartphone sector	130
Objective 2: To analyse the intricacies of innovation performance in the context of Micromax Informatics	136
Objective 3: To fathom the particularities of the innovation crisis confronted by Micromax Informatics.	142
4.6 Discussion of findings	146
4.7 Summary	148
Chapter 5 Discussion.....	149
5.1 Introduction	149

5.2 Plan of analysis	149
5.3 Survey findings.....	150
5.4 Thematic analysis.....	153
Theme 1: Innovations in the smartphone industry	154
Theme 2: Factors that impact the innovation performance of Micromax.....	156
Theme 3: Changing buying preferences of the customers, market competition, technological advancements and current trends are the major drivers which leads to innovations in the smartphone industry.....	158
Theme 4: Leadership plays a vital role in the innovation performance of smartphone companies	161
5.5 Summary	164
Chapter 6: Conclusion and Recommendation.....	166
6.1 Introduction and summary of the thesis.....	166
6.2 Objectives	168
Objective 1: To gain insights into the contributors to innovation performance in Indian Smartphone sector.....	168
Objective 2: “To analyse the intricacies of innovation performance in the context of Micromax Informatics”	170
Objective 3: “To understand the particularities of the innovation crisis confronted by Micromax Informatics”	172
6.3 Recommendations.....	173
6.4 Limitation of the study	176
6.5. Recommendation for future researches	177
6.6 Contribution to the theory practice and knowledge	177
References.....	179

List of Tables, Figures and Charts

Figure 2.1: *Growth of Smartphones compared to PC's and Laptops*

Figure 2.2: Concerns-Based adoption model

Figure 2.3: Schumpeter's Theory of Innovation

Figure 2.4: Roger's diffusion model for Technology adoption

Figure 2.5: A framework developed using Diffusion Innovation Theory

Figure 2.6: Conceptual Framework

Chart 1: Gender

Chart 2: Age

Chart 3: Number of customers of Micromax

Chart 4: Factors considered while buying smartphones

Chart 5: Micromax features influence in purchase of Smartphones

Chart 6: Innovation level of Micromax

Chart 7: satisfaction level of Micromax users

Chart 8: Level of Micromax meeting the customer expectation.

Chart 9: Similarity of features of Micromax with its competitors.

Chart 10: Unique features of Micromax

Chart 11: Short falls of Micromax smartphones

Chart 12: Recommendations to friends and families to buy Micromax

Chart 13: Recommendations to Micromax for improvement.

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Overview

Introducing day-to-day innovations and novelties, the smartphone industry is one of the most important global market sectors that face fierce competition. With the advent of rapid developments in the telecom infrastructure and with the emergence of an increased number of competitors, the growth of the smartphone industry is at its highest peak. Welcoming more and more innovations according to the changing market trends and looking forward to implementing the latest technologies for satisfying the changing needs of current generations, the global smartphone industry forecasts to achieve a market value of \$795.3 billion by 2027 by maintaining an annual growth of 9.5% during 2020-2027 (Yahoo Finance, 2021).

Reporting a year-on-year growth of 14% and expecting a record sale of 173 million units by the end of 2021, India is on the onset of becoming one of the world's leading smartphone market performers (Business Today.In, 2021). Although the Indian smartphone industry succeeds in outperforming in the global scenario, some of the Indian manufacturers, such as Micromax Informatics, fails to outdo even in the home country. Despite focusing on introducing technological innovations as per changing market trends, Micromax Informatics has lost its competitive edge compared to its global competitors. This is the key area of focus in this thesis research.

Reviewing the concepts related to the smartphone industry with a special focus on the Indian scenario and problematising the core issues that were addressed by the researcher, the initial sections of this chapter focus on detailing the background of this thesis research. The significance of the research topic, objectives, hypothesis and research questions that underpins the basis of this research, the work structure that is followed in this thesis report, etc., also includes the various contents that are briefed through this introductory chapter. Thus, building foundations for the project research, through this chapter, the researcher aims to develop a detailed preface for the thesis research.

1.2 Intentions of research

I intend to make the following valuable contributions through this study, fully

acknowledging the fact that this research project forms the part of my DBA thesis work:

- i. To offer my results to all concerned stakeholders of the organisation (Micromax Informatics) and others that are associated with it as well, such as the suppliers.
- ii. To contribute to knowledge about the relevance and appropriateness of innovative performance in the Indian Smartphone sector, as well as to the wider societal developments.

Giachetti and Dagnino (2021) define innovative performance as one of the most important critical success factors of business performance. Identifying the implications of technological advancements in enhancing production capabilities, these authors opine that streamlining organisational processes through innovation investments is significant for maximising business profits. According to the outlooks of Fartash et al. (2018), integrating innovations to organisational operations helps in enhancing the value of products and services; however, in the opinion of Anzola-Román et al. (2018), the competency in improving technological capabilities indicates a direct measure of how well an organisation succeeds in providing innovative performance.

With the advent of globalisation, introducing technological innovations as per the changing market trends and varying consumer preferences has become necessary for most organisations. Apart from enhancing operational excellence and business productivity, the competency in introducing innovation investments has become a measure of brand value, states Fartash et al. (2018). The importance of innovative performance in influencing employee management and customer management efficiencies has also been thoroughly investigated in several literature studies.

According to Anzola-Román et al. (2018), advancements in machineries and operational procedures using the latest technological trends helps employees accurately meet the customers' changing preferences. The success in integrating inter-department operations and efficiency in monitoring and nurturing the potencies of the employees are also potential benefits achieved through innovation investments. According to Anzola-Román et al. (2018), competency to manage global talents and thereby achieve improved business productivity is also an important outcome of innovation investments.

Improved customer management is also an important aspect of innovation investment. Improvising the communication platforms and recognising new means for customer engagement, innovation investments help in building healthy relationships and strong

bonds states, Fartash et al. (2018). The role of technological innovations in meeting the changing customer demands and changing market preferences have also been studied in this literature study. Thus, recognising the potential benefits of innovation investments in positively influencing both employees and customers, it is inferred by the researcher that innovative performance has increasing importance in day-to-day market competitions. The smartphone industry is one of the best industrial examples that competitively endeavours in providing innovative performance. According to Yeo et al. (2020), the smartphone industry is at its highest peak of expansion. Hence, introducing innovations with respect to changing technologies has a significant role in determining the performance of smartphone manufacturers. Connecting people globally and making communications faster and easier, the application of smartphones has crossed beyond borders (Yeo et al., 2020). Although smartphones technologies were initially boomed in the business sectors, with the advent of telecom infrastructure developments and increasing disposable incomes, it is observed that utilisation of smartphones has become more individual-oriented rather than for business purposes.

Apart from being used for direct conversations, the application of smartphones for entertainment, banking and other purposes have steadily increased in the recent era. The increasing usage of social media and mobile banking facilities among the current generations are examples that fortify the increased use of smartphones for personal purposes. Recognising the increasing applications of technological innovations such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, big data analytics, etc., in smartphone designing, Yeo et al. (2020) also opines that the growth of the smartphone industry is unpredictable and beyond the limits of business forecasters.

In this context, through this thesis research, the researcher intends to explore the influence of innovative performance in the smartphone industry by taking into consideration the case of Micromax Informatics in India. Micromax Informatics is a telecommunications and consumer electronics organisation with a product portfolio of tablets, Smartphones, power banks, laptops, LED TVs, air conditioners and soundbars (Micromax Informatics, 2020). Although this company had gained adequate recognition in the Indian smartphone industry with its pricing efficiency, with the advent of giant market players and changing customer needs, Micromax Informatics has started losing its competitive edge. Thus, evaluating and exploring the innovative performance aspects of Micromax Informatics, through this work, the researcher intends to recognise the increasing importance of innovation investments. Evaluating the complexities associated

with the innovative performance of Micromax, this study also intends to analyse the impacts of smartphone industrial innovations on society. Thus, exploring and evaluating the above-stated facts through this thesis research, the researcher intends to make valuable contributions for both company stakeholders as well as society on the various aspects of innovative performance.

1.3 Problematising the innovative performance of Micromax Informatics

1.3.1 History of innovation in India

The history of innovation in India begins from the primeval activities of human beings, right from the times of Indus Valley Civilization. Identifying breakthroughs in mathematics, medicine, space science, mining, metrology, construction engineering, etc. India has been a hub of discoveries and innovations since its early decades (Menon, 2017). Following independence, the discoveries and inventions of India have delved into a different perspective. According to the findings of Menon (2017), following independence, the country was more focused on expanding its operations and inventions through science and technology, and this clearly reflected on the nation's discoveries in automobile engineering, nuclear science, polar science, space science, telecommunications and information technology.

India, after its independence in 1947, under the leadership of its prime minister, Jawaharlal Nehru, implemented numerous development strategies, including the five-year plan to develop the economy. However, until 1980 the country was not able to economically develop like the other Asian nations such as Malaysia, Korea or Singapore, and so were its innovative capabilities (Menon, 2017). Even though several technological reforms were also introduced under the leadership of the Rajiv Gandhi government in 1986 for surmounting the weak economy of the nation, most of the strategies that were implemented in these days did not succeed in achieving their utmost benefits. However, towards the 20th-century end, the circumstances seemed to turn around. In 1991, the Narasimha Rao government, along with the help of its finance minister Dr. Manmohan Singh introduced new economic reforms which reduced the governmental regulations on private companies (Mohan, 2018). These economic reforms resulted in more multinational companies coming to India, thereby paving the way for more productive and

profitable innovations. Thus gradually, powered by the emergence of new market players and with the backing of governmental support and domestic capabilities, the Indian business environment transformed itself to a global level by adapting to the changing innovative needs of the current century (Mohan, 2018). Internationalising the operations of domestic players and inviting foreign competitors to the domestic market with the abundance of resources and favourable regulatory conditions, India currently succeeds in maintaining its competitive edge in the global innovative performance.

1.3.2 The innovative performance of India and Micromax Informatics

As discussed in the above section, evolving from ancient times, India had successfully implemented innovations and in the current milieu with its technological capabilities and competitive discoveries. India succeeded in winning global recognition for its innovative performance. The country's competency in acquiring a respectable position in the Global Innovation Index ranking signifies this fact. According to the reports of Cornell University (2019), India has acquired the 52nd position in Global Innovation Index among the 129 world economies based on its innovation capabilities.

Even though the performance of India lags behind the economic giants such as the US, Canada, UK, Switzerland, etc., the competency of the country in climbing 29 notches in 4 years (from 81st position (2015) to 52nd ranking (2019)) implies the innovation potential of this developing nation (Cornell University, 2019). Business sophistication, market sophistication, institutions, technology and knowledge outputs, human capital and research, infrastructure and creative outputs are the seven pillars used to estimate a country's Global Innovation Index. Thus, evaluating the innovation inputs/outputs of the country, and having recognised the rising trajectory of the nation in contributing to various fields such as information technology, space technology, pharmaceuticals, new-age technologies such as robotics, artificial intelligence, etc. Global Innovation Index identifies that India is a major contributor that shapes the global innovation economy (Sury, 2021).

According to the observations of Zuelke and Kirwan (2016), the smartphone industry is one of the most important global market sectors that exemplify innovative performance. Upgrading technologies regularly and discovering innovations according to changing customer needs, the global smartphone industry is one of the best examples of tech hubs and innovation hubs, states Zuelke and Kirwan (2016). Encompassed of several

domestic brands such as Micromax Informatics, Karbonn Mobiles, Xolo, Intex Technologies, Spice Telecom, I-Ball Mobile, etc. and with many more international players such as Samsung, Huawei Technologies, Nokia, Apple, Xiaomi, etc. the smartphone industry is one of the most profitable market sectors of India.

However, comparing the inventions and performance delivered by domestic and global brands, it is apparent that the innovative performance provided by the Indian smartphone companies is far behind the international players (Arora, 2015). Evaluating the innovation investments of Indian smartphone brands such as Micromax Informatics and recognising the technological aspirations of current generations, Anagha (2018) and Schilling and Shankar (2019) identify that improving the innovative performance of Indian brand's is necessary for ensuring the competitive edge in the global market. This exemplifies the necessity in investigating the innovative performance of the Indian smartphone industry.

Micromax Informatics is an Indian smartphone company established in 2000. Recognised as one of the cheapest and economical smartphone providers in India (for the year 2010), Micromax Informatics was once one of the globally renowned smartphone companies in the world (Anagha, 2018). However, with the advent of technological advancements introduced by several international brands, Micromax Informatics started losing its momentum and competitive edge even in the domestic market. Having determined this libel and focused on regaining the market momentum, Micromax Informatics has made strategic plans to improvise the R&D units of the company by investing an estimate of 5 billion Indian rupees, reports Micromax Informatics (2020).

Evaluating the initial performance of Micromax Informatics, it is observed that this smartphone brand was competitive in satisfying the economic and technological needs of the customers. The clear-cut strategies implemented by the company for fortifying their back-end programmers by affiliating with potential start-ups and the productive growth reported by this smartphone brand in its initial decades by introducing brand-new and cutting-edge products signify this fact (Anagha, 2018). The success of the company in attaining passable economic figures (365.8Cr Rupees in 2017) even at times of intense market competition by balancing its marketing and other additional expenses is also an example of the competitive strategy used by Micromax Informatics for delivering quality performance (The Economic Times, 2019).

However, with the intensified market competition, the financial figures of the company

showcased a falling performance. According to the reports of Sing (2019), for the year 2018-19, Micromax Informatics reported a sales decline of 26%. As per the observations of this author, one of the prime factors that contributed to the falling performance of this company was the incompetency in modifying its innovation policies. Evaluating the R&D activities and growth strategies of Micromax Informatics, and recognising the ineffectiveness of this smartphone brand in acclimatising changing innovation trends, Sing (2019) summarised that enhancing innovative performance is a requisite for Micromax Informatics to regain its competitive edge.

According to the reports of Livemint (2020), the latest governmental policies of India have set up initiatives for curtailing low-quality Chinese smartphones and are on the onset of fortifying the growth of domestic players. This break opens the revival opportunity for Micromax Informatics. As per the findings of Kundu (2020), Micromax Informatics has been competitive in understanding this upcoming market opportunity, and this is reflected through the company's initiative in launching its new product segment, "In". Focused on introducing innovative products with cutting-edge technologies at economical pricing (Rs.7000-10,000 range, Rs.15000- 20,000 range, Rs.25000 and above based on level of innovation), Micromax Informatics believes that the introduction of the "In" product segment will help the company in regaining and rebuilding their lost market space (Kundu, 2020). Diversifying the portfolio by adding additional connected devices such as TVs, ACs, and other products is also another growth strategy through which Micromax Informatics focuses on fortifying its brand (The Hindu, 2020). Thus, having determined the developmental plans of Micromax Informatics and understanding the growing market opportunities, the researcher interprets that carrying out a detailed study on the innovative performance of this Indian smartphone brand is meaningful.

1.3.3 Core problems

1. The influencers of innovation performance are more acknowledged by the international smartphone companies rather than the Indian companies

Characterised by diverse social and economic statuses, India is one of the world's biggest consumer societies. Attracted by technological innovations of international brands and enthralled by the economical pricing of domestic players, India is one of the largest consumer markets of smartphones. Evaluating the smartphone trends in India, it

is apparent that Samsung Electronics, a Korean based company, is one of the high-quality smartphone providers that have earned the highest trust and reputation among Indian buyers (Walk Through India, 2020). Xiaomi and OnePlus also include international smartphone brands that are widely chosen by Indian customers. Although these companies provide smartphones at high-end prices, taking into consideration of quality and innovation, the consumers believe that purchasing these brands are worthwhile, and value for money reports Walk Through India (2020). Comparing the sales figures of various international smartphone brands, Counter Point (2019) summarised that Samsung and Xiaomi are the key players in the Indian market. The record shipment of 53 million units into the Indian market and the growth strategies of these brands by setting up leading-edge production units within the country illustrate the intense competition embarked by these international brands in this tech-savvy market (Counter Point, 2019).

The premium smartphone brand such as Apple has also often been a top-notch choice among at least some of the Indian consumers. The competency of these smartphones in delivering quality performance through cutting-edge innovations and the brand image achieved by these companies in the global market are the influential factors that persuaded consumers in purchasing these international brands, reports, Walk Through India (2019).

Further, looking into the sales figures and market shares of domestic players, the researcher identifies that Spice Telecom, LYF and I-Ball Mobile are the main brands that have achieved adequate recognition in the Indian market (Counter Point, 2019). However, comparing the market performance of local and global brands, it is explicit that, on the whole, the Indian consumers showcase an increased inclination towards international smartphones (Jakhar and Bharadwaj, 2018). This implies that the brand recognition achieved by domestic smartphones in the Indian market is far behind the international brands. One of the major reasons that caused Indian brands to get less recognised is their incompetency in introducing cutting-edge technologies (Vuori and Huy, 2016). This is the first core problem under consideration in this study.

The findings of Rajasekaran et al. (2018) and Sakkthivel et al. (2020) also identify the ineffectiveness of Indian smartphone companies in updating their innovation policies. Recognising the necessity of revamping R&D activities and identifying the importance of introducing innovations for achieving improved market recognition, these authors opine

that innovative performance is the most significant element that has to be immediately acknowledged by Indian smartphone providers. The increasing growth opportunities for Indian smartphone brands in the home country with the advent of new governmental policies that focuses on motivating domestic players by curtailing Chinese products have also been identified by Sakkthivel et al. (2020). This implies that the importance of investigating the innovative performance of the Indian smartphone industry. The role of technological advancements in attracting customers and the significance of introducing innovations for improved market share will be analysed through this research. The factors that encourage the growth of smartphone companies and the role of innovation in influencing these factors will also be emphasised through this research. Thus, through this study, the researcher focuses on investigating how much innovative performance is important for Indian smartphone brands for attracting influencers over the international players. Further, all the above-mentioned aspects will also be reexamined by taking into consideration the case of Micromax Informatics.

2. Micromax Informatics has lost its competitive edge in its own market and has fallen behind most of the international companies

Micromax Informatics, headquartered in Gurgaon, is a manufacturer of home appliances and consumer electronics. When established in 2000, the company was an IT software service provider that operated in the embedded devices domain (Micromax Informatics, 2020). On entering into the business of mobile handsets (in 2008), Micromax Informatics was competent in devising strategies for developing innovative smartphone products that meet changing customer needs at economical pricing. Smartphones at affordable pricing were the unique selling proposition of this Indian brand (Micromax Informatics, 2020). Thus, influencing the price sensitivity of customers and attracting populations that seek economical smartphone brands, Micromax Informatics was one of the highly recognised smartphone brands in both Indian and global markets.

The success of this company in acquiring a market share of 16.6% in the Indian market in 2014, which was even more than Samsung (14.4% in 2014), also points towards the competitive edge that Micromax Informatics had attained in the past era (Livemint, 2014). Moreover, the competency exhibited by this brand is being recognised as 2010's India's largest manufacturer of low-cost feature phones and 2014's world's tenth biggest smartphone vendor also signifies the competitiveness that had achieved by this brand in

the smartphone industrial sector (Micromax Informatics, 2020; Livemint, 2015).

However, with the advent of technological innovations of several international players and with the penetration of Chinese companies to the Indian market, Micromax Informatics started facing stiff competition and delayed growth. The introduction of economical and innovative Chinese brands drastically changed the outlooks of customers towards smartphones (Singh, 2019; Molenaar, 2016). Motivating individuals to opt for better choices that offer improved, innovative performances as per the changing networking needs, Chinese and other international players showcased an increased boom in the Indian markets. According to the reports of Digit (2021), Oppo, Lenovo, Xiaomi, Huawei, etc., are examples of Chinese brands that have conquered the Indian smartphone market.

The growth of social media that encourages the use of highly sophisticated technologies and steadfast networks also changed the outlooks of individuals towards the smartphone. The changing trends of consumer spending that motivated individuals to expend more on smartphones recognising the price worthiness and value of products, also dissuaded the growth of low-cost smartphone manufacturers like Micromax Informatics (Molenaar, 2016). The growth of international players such as Apple and Samsung in the Indian market illustrates the changing outlooks of Indian consumers spending more on valuable brands (Digit, 2021).

The preference of Indian customers to choose alternative brands over Micromax smartphones illustrates the falling fame of this company in the home market. Moreover, the 26% profit fall experienced by Micromax Informatics for the year 2018 in the light of falling revenues (from 5,614 crore Rupees (2017) to 4,430 crore Rupees (2018)) also signifies the falling performance of this Indian brand. This is the second core problem under consideration in this study. According to the opinion of Almeida (2020), the ineffectiveness of Micromax Informatics in making prompt decisions according to the changing industrial trends and the inefficiency in delivering innovative performances as per the international standards were the prime factors that deterred the growth of this smartphone manufacturer even in the home market. Thus, having identified the incompetence of Micromax Informatics in maintaining a competitive edge in the home country, through this research, the researcher aims to critically analyse the factors that caused Micromax to fall behind most of the international companies.

3. The Indian smartphone company Micromax Informatics faces several barriers to enhancing its innovative performance compared to other international brands

Although most of the companies tend to show an increased market share in their home market, analysing the context of the Indian smartphone sector, it is apparent from the findings of Chandola and Fu (2017) that the performance of the Indian smartphone companies is far behind the international players even in the home market. One of the prime reasons for the falling fame of Indian brands even in the home country is its incompetence in introducing novel products that encompass high-end technologies (Vikram and Ramanathan, 2015). According to the observations of Sujata et al. (2016), the reasons for the falling performance of Indian smartphone companies does not confine to the innovation factor. Identifying the inefficiency of several Indian brands in upholding a strong and robust business model related to marketing, manufacturing, positioning and R&D, Sujata et al. (2016) summarised that ineffectiveness in exploring and utilising the resources in the most effective manner also underpins the barriers to the growth of the Indian smartphone companies.

From these facts, the researcher recognises that there are several barriers that impede Indian smartphone companies in delivering innovative performance. This is the third core problem under consideration in this study. Evaluating the various constraints and challenges faced by Indian smartphone companies in delivering innovative performance, through this research, the researcher focuses on identifying the barriers to innovation in the Indian smartphone industry. Identifying the factors that paved the way for the innovation crisis in the Indian smartphone sector, through this research, the researcher also discusses why Indian smartphones are less attractive to customers compared to other international brands. Further reexamining these findings in the context of Micromax Informatics, through this thesis research, the researcher will identify the barriers to innovative performance that impeded the growth of Micromax compared to other international brands, even in the home market.

The research questions developed in the light of the above core problems are the following:

1.4 Research Questions

- What are the most significant influencers of innovation performance, and how does the Indian smartphone sector recognise the significance of these influencers?
- What are the characteristic attributes of innovation performance, and how does Micromax Informatics attempt in realising these elements?
- What caused the innovation crisis in Micromax Informatics, and what are the challenges and constraints that impeded the innovative performance of the Indian smartphone sector?
- What are the lessons that are to be learned by the Indian smartphone sector and Micromax Informatics on behalf of the past decade's investment and activities, successes and failures in the global smartphone market?

1.5 Hypothesis

H1: Innovation performance plays a crucial role in the sustenance of organisations.

H2: Innovation crisis has a deteriorating effect on the profitability of Micromax Informatics.

1.6 Objectives

- To identify the contributing factors that promote innovative performance in the smartphone industry with a special focus on the context of the Indian market
- To analyse and recognise the intricacies and challenges of innovation performance with regards to the case of Micromax Informatics
- To comprehend the factors, impacts and other particulars associated with the innovation crisis confronted by Micromax Informatics and thereby understand the causes that impeded the competitive edge of this company even in the home market
- To suggest recommendations for Micromax Informatics for improving the organisations' innovation strategies, so that the company could sustain its innovative performance

1.7 Significance of this study and chosen topic

The smartphone industry is one of the booming market sectors in the current era. With countless market players battling to win the hearts of the customers, and with the intrusion of international players aimed at acquiring increased market shares, the smartphone industry is a clear example of industrial sectors that confronts intense and fierce market competition. Smartphones have become an essential part of day-to-life. Apart from being used for business and professional purposes, smartphones have become the largest and most dependable means for communication. The increasing application of social media technologies and changing shopping trends of current generations that anticipates accessing all sources at their fingertips illustrates the enduring growth of the smartphone sector. The changing expenditure trends that showcase the inclination of customers to opt for a branded smartphone rather than other gadgets also represent the smartphone industry's growing phase. Thus, in this context, the researcher identifies that analysing the aspects and influential factors of the smartphone sector has adequate industrial significance.

India is one of the largest consumer societies in the world, and hence recognising the growth opportunities, most of the market players tends to establish their roots in the Indian market. The smartphone industry sector is one of the best examples of industrial domains that have deep-rooted its performance in the Indian market. Encompassed of several international players and abundant of several native brands, the Indian smartphone industry is a perfect example of market domains that showcases steadfast growth. However, with the penetration of Chinese brands and the exceptional performance and global recognition of international brands, Indian smartphone companies tend to showcase a declining performance even in their home market. While Oppo, Lenovo, Xiaomi, Huawei, etc., include the examples of Chinese brands that have established their roots in the Indian market, Samsung and Apple are the key examples of international players that have gained an adequate competitive edge in the Indian market.

One of the prime factors that caused Indian companies to fall behind these international brands is its incompetence in delivering quality innovation. Comparing the performance of international companies over Indian smartphones, it is apparent from the above sections of this chapter that Indian brands fail to introduce cutting-edge technologies compared to those of international players. Though the Indian companies succeed in

delivering economical smartphones, the technological innovations upgraded by these brands are relatively less compared to the global players. Moreover, customers' changing attitudes to accept and purchase high-end priced smartphones by recognising their value for money and price-worthiness also significantly affected the growth of the Indian smartphone companies. In this perspective, the researcher recognises that analysing the concept of innovative performance with reference to the Indian smartphone industry is significant.

Further, taking into consideration the case of Micromax Informatics, the researcher identified from the above sections that this Indian brand fails to maintain a consistent competitive edge even in its home market. Although this company was initially popular for its economical products, with the advent of time, the preferences of customers to choose the Micromax brand gradually declined. One of the key factors that paved the way for the falling brand recognition was its incompetency in upgrading its products with the latest leading-edge technologies. This led to an innovation crisis at Micromax Informatics. Negatively affecting the financial performance and brand value, the innovation crisis also caused Micromax Informatics to lose its competitive edge even in its home market. In this context, the researcher identifies that evaluating the aspect of innovative performance of smartphone industrial sector with special focus on the case of Micromax Informatics is significant.

1.8 Structure of the work

The implementation of the current DBA project is presented through six significant chapters in the research. The first introductory chapter attempts to construct the context and foundations for the project by focusing on the research title. The prime intention for conducting the research, along with discussing the core problems, objectives, questions and hypotheses of the research are included in this chapter. The second literature review chapter discusses available literature concerning the topic, also evolving a theoretical underpinning of the major concepts linked with the topic. In the third chapter of research methodology, the methods employed for collecting, analysing and interpreting the research data. The section also justifies the selection of methods considering the role of innovative performance in cultivating the Indian Smartphone sector in Micromax

Informatics. The subsequent chapter, 'Findings', analyses and interprets the accumulated information along with cross-comparing those with the literature reviewed to lead towards the conclusion.

The fifth chapter discusses the overall results interpreted through interrogating the data and linking it back to the conceptual framework framed in the literature review. The final chapter represents the conclusion by scrutinising the findings and results against the research objectives. Further, recommendations will be made to Micromax Informatics in India to improve the highlighted issue to enhance the competitive edge.

1.9 Summary

This present introductory section has provided a route map to the researcher's entire research study in the selected research context. The chapter highlighted the basis and context for the research project by providing a brief overview of the study. The chapter enlightens the setting-up of the context in the Indian Smartphone sector and background context to the significance and role of innovative performance in this respective sector.

The background section highlighted the Indian Smartphone sector as one of the world's leading market performers today. India has achieved a respectful spot in the global smartphone sector with affluent technological capabilities and competitive discoveries. However, a few Smartphone manufacturers in India failed to attain a competitive advantage even in the domestic market despite their innovative capabilities as per market trends. Micromax Informatics is one such firm that lost its competitive edge in the Smartphone sector. The entire context indicated the significance of identifying core problems that lead to the current status of Micromax. Given this context, the research questions, hypothesis and objectives are developed as representatives of the research study. All the core problems signified that the present study is highly potential and offer valuable contributions to the country, industry and company.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The literature review aimed to analyse recent research on several innovation methods that supported the growth of the smartphone sector. The goal was for the researcher to better understand the available research that has been done on the subject of innovation strategies and their performance in the Indian smartphone sector. More specifically, it sought to see how much intrinsic and extrinsic innovation methods influence the business performance of the Micromax Smartphone industry, India. This chapter begins by considering the definitions of the terms 'innovation performance' and 'Smartphones' before reviewing the literature on the issues affecting the relevance and appropriateness of innovative performance. These include the difficulties of showing measurable benefits from the investments made to date in regards to R&D for deriving updated technology to bring creative ideas in the making of Smartphones along with studying the experiences of the customers in using Smartphones as well as examining some practical conceptual frameworks that will be employed in the discussion of the findings in Chapter 5. The chapter concludes by discussing the debates surrounding the role and significance of innovative performance in smartphone manufacturing by taking the case of a developing country like India. This chapter will discuss the literature review on the critical evaluation of innovation performance in the Indian smartphone sector. Innovation is mainly defined as creating new ideas, products, or methods that positively impact the organisation or firm (Kahn, 2018). Innovative performance is quintessential to the better performance of any business entity. The organisation's innovation improves the success rate, new product value and reduces the time to market and cost waste. The review includes smartphone service's benefits and its outcomes, and it will present some literature works. Smartphones are highly beneficial for social life, education, health, and other fields in society. The review will discuss innovation theories for business development, such as Hall's Concerns-Based Adoption Model, Schumpeter's Theory of Innovation. The types of innovation in the business will discuss in the review later.

The report will study the smartphone industry's evolution since the last decade in India and will mention the literature's conceptual framework. The study mainly focused on the innovation matrix model, The Doblin Framework and The Roger's Diffusion Model. The innovation process and the various barriers of performance innovations will discuss in the

review, and the latest trends and technologies will discuss in the next sector. The trends and customer necessities are changing day by day. Hence this review will enlighten the current trends in the smartphone sector. The influence of innovation enables smartphone enterprises' innovation performance will discuss in detail through every section of literature.

2.2 Defining Innovation performance

According to Stankovska et al. (2019), innovation means to develop or replace anything, such as a technique, a product, or a service. Innovation is a series of process that a domain, a product, or a service is renewed and kept up to date by the application of new procedures, the introduction of new techniques, or the establishment of innovative concepts to produce new value. But in the view of Rodríguez-López, Á. and Souto (2020), an innovation performance is referred to be the creation of new idea that has been transformed into practical reality. That can be a product or business concept or combination or products that have been activated in the market place and are generating new profits and growth of the company. But the innovation strategy is a plan is to increase the market profitability by developing new products (Geissdoerferetal.2018).

The employment of creative methods and fresh creativity on market products, processes, or procedures, according to Surosoand Azis (2015), raises the market rate, usefulness, significance, and performance of the products or services. The ability to translate innovation inputs into outputs that result in inventive commercial success is called innovation strategy. According to Gault (2018), the notion of innovation strategy is concerned with several steps that lead to the creation of new products, such as trademarks and R&D, sourcing, and the methods through which new products and services are introduced. The two characteristics of innovation performance are the quality and quantity of inventive concepts and the efficiency with which ideas are converted into the appropriate innovation processes (Gault, 2018). From the findings of de Solà-Morales et al. (2018), by enabling the organisations to improve their performance to the market needs, innovations serve as an integral role in bringing forth success to the organisations irrespective of the difference in the type of industries. As per Surosoand Azis (2015) observation, institutionalising strategy-driven Enterprise Innovation Management allows to maximise the impact of the innovation investment portfolio and aligns investment decisions with performance goals. Intrinsically linked to your organisation's business

strategy are the best-practice metrics for measuring performance (Gault, 2018).

2.3 Innovation strategies and organisational performance

Entrepreneurs use innovation as a tool to take advantage of change as an opportunity to start a new firm or provide a new service (Peter Drucker, 2014). New features brought into an organization's production and supply operation are referred to as process innovations. They do not make things or provide services, but they do indirectly impact the entry of products and services (Hervas-Oliver et al., 2017). Entrepreneurs must actively seek out new ideas with the assistance of employees and discuss the feasibility and viability of each one. Furthermore, a comprehensive organisational strategy for innovation must be implemented (Kumar et al., 2013). It is critical to have an innovation plan to guarantee that all workers work together and fully know the broader picture (Shiplov et al., 2015). If an effective innovation plan is not developed, "million-dollar ideas" may be overlooked or delayed. Competitors may acquire wind of the idea during this period, and there's a risk they'll profit from it. Today, some businesses are plagued by ambiguity and a lack of direction, making strategy formulation extremely challenging (Rao and Choudhury, 2017). As a result, as soon as a viable idea is recognised, it must be developed as quickly as possible. Smith (2015) states that every innovation starts with clear and coordinated thinking of various employees in a firm. Often, that leads to the interdisciplinary innovations process and suggests that it is very complicated to organise without sharing ideas and opinions. Moreover, the studies by Rao and Choudhury (2017) disclose the importance of patents to support the organisation's growth by promoting novel technologies since new opportunities can be developed in the form of new products.

2.4 Innovation strategies for Smart Phone Sector

The Smartphone industry is a fast-paced sector. The market shares are extremely unequally divided, with a few corporations controlling the majority of the market. Even though there is a several standardisation in terms of product features and technology, there is still a lot of innovation in this industry (Cecere et al., 2014). Just after Rim debuted Blackberry in 2006, did smartphones become a market trend. Soon after, in

2007, Apple released the iPhone, a smartphone model, which was quickly followed by Samsung in 2008, accelerates the new product trend in the smartphone sector. (Varriale et al., 2021). Ross (2019) paved the way for Samsung's Galaxy and Apple's iPhone in terms of innovation. Ross calculated the level of product and process innovations. Ross also discovered that the iPhone's route to innovation is higher than that of the Samsung Galaxy. This indicates that the innovativeness of the iPhone and Samsung Galaxy are the same, and their product innovation is effective as service innovation. Furthermore, according to Ross (2019), Samsung obtained a marketing innovation' approach, whereas Apple obtained a 'technological innovation' approach. This demonstrates that Samsung offers a wide range of costs and features in its many smartphones, whereas Apple manufactures the iPhone and utilises its own operating system.

According to Calvosa (2020), new products are introduced into the market regularly. Because of the need for diversity, groundbreaking invention occurs, and sales of such products go on until a maximum level is achieved. Distinctiveness, recognition, and recurrent purchase are the steps that make an idea commercially successful (Singh, 2013). Novelties in technologies that can improve the lives of people in society while also providing job opportunities are also termed social innovations (Sharma and Sharma, 2020). According to Madhusudan et al. (2017), companies can turn some disruptive technologies into successful goods. Regardless of its field of operation or industry, every firm can innovate (Jha, 2015). As a hypercompetitive sector, innovation of smartphone sectors is characterised by short product design and production process, persistently evolving in market landscape leading to unpredictable market conditions. Therefore, Smartphone developers required to create technology to meet the requirements of the customers. As a result, smartphone technology innovation is a crucial driver of business expansion for mobile technology companies and helps them stay competitive (Yun et al., 2018).

According to Varriale et al. (2021), horizontal and vertical innovation strategies are the two main innovation strategies used by the most forward-thinking smartphone manufacturers. In general, the earlier entails the development of new product features and the operating system's capability, whereas the latter entails using pre-existing technology or expertise (Roscaet al.2017). Horizontal advances could include screen resolution, ringtones number, or storage capacity, whereas vertical innovations could

include network or data connectivity, or processor power (Chen et al., 2018). This invention has fueled continuing technological breakthroughs in mobile phone consumer goods, such as the switch from 1G to 5G connectivity, the shift from analogue to touch screens, the shrinking of handset size and weight, and the development of longer-lasting batteries (Fuentelsaz et al., 2018). Parallel scientific breakthroughs (e.g., the invention of Lithium-Ion batteries) with horizontal cross-sector applications resulted from the latter innovation, which was a response to customer demands for features (Yun et al., 2018).

Also, some of the industry's long-standing giants, including Nokia, Motorola, Sony Ericsson, and RIM, are fast losing market share and are currently battling to develop viable innovation plans that will ensure a long-term competitive edge (Cecere, Corrocher and Battaglia, 2017). Nokia's CEO, unsurprisingly, stated that the cause of the organizational marketing drift and the key to its revival is tied to the understanding of mobile competitive dynamics as a war of platforms rather than a battle between producers (Yun, Won and Park, 2016). As an innovation strategy, Samsung pursued Nokia, the low-cost market leader, into the early market demand. Moreover, Samsung focused on the structure by modifying its products' design, function, and features in order to stay competitive in the market. However, it has surpassed Nokia as the market leader, despite Nokia's losses in converting its portfolio to the smartphone market. Samsung not only pursued the market leader but also researched the market environment and other competitors (Calvosa, 2019). According to Kaylynn C (2019), Samsung became the leading producer of high-quality devices and services through effective advertising and inventive techniques. Furthermore, the brand re-organisation was carried out in order to notify more people about the company's exceptional products. At the corporation, this strategy has become a long-term investment. It is currently attracting a large number of potential purchasers from all throughout Asia.

2.5 Smartphone Services benefits and Outcomes

From the studies by Rosca et al., (2017), initial introduction of smartphone devices were in the market to integrate a diverse range of services, referring to it as a new class of mobile phones. The varied range of services integrated includes communication services such as personal information management, messaging, voice communication, and

wireless communication, as noted from the source Smartphones were first utilised exclusively for corporate purposes due to their higher price, but this has changed in recent years, and smartphones now have a more significant effect on society. According to Hubert et al. (2017), there is a tremendous demand and increase in the popularity of smartphones among the general people, which is faster than the demand in the corporate sector. Smartphones were utilised as enterprise devices in the early days of smartphones, primarily aimed at corporate users. Smartphones have been available on the market since 1993, but it was only with Apple's release of the smartphone to the broad consumer market that it reached the general public. Swendeman et al. (2015) pointed out that the day-to-day activities of consumers are getting influenced in several surprising ways by smartphones through Apple's and Google's digital marketplace. Thus, it has more than 1 billion users and 2.5 million apps approximately. Globally the utilisation of smartphones in various sectors has been increased day by day. From Spittle et al. (2016) report, it has been observed that mobile devices have been utilised by 80% of the whole world population, and in the US alone, 42% of mobile subscribers use smartphones.

Additionally, according to Chan (2016), most smartphone users use their devices primarily to read news feeds, read and respond to messages, update posts stats, and publish images. Furthermore, many nowadays prefer smartphones to computers. On the other hand, it has been observed that long-dominated organisations are currently experiencing tight marketing competition based on the increased technological updation. Also, increased use of tablets and smart phones and long partnerships are causing fractures as there is more significant pressure to gain market share in the mobile device market, as noted in the Chan report (2018). However, despite the significant increase achieved from tablets and smartphones, millions of PCs will remain sold in the future.

*Figure 2.1: Growth of Smartphones compared to PC's and Laptops Source: Chan (2018)
Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.*

According to Chan (2018), cell phones have become popular among consumers due to the diverse range of applications that they deliver. People's communications can be facilitated by utilising smartphones, and the smartphone is quite useful in a variety of daily tasks. According to Pope et al., the many services given by smartphones include the latest things customers may gain massive exposure, simple ways to access applications, business idea generation, learning alternatives for users, and a variety of venues to build their application (2019). Also, Spittle et al. (2016) discovered that the impact of smartphones on enterprises has produced new dimensions. It should also be highlighted that smartphone suppliers are not the only ones who benefit, as app development businesses, other connected industries, and the internet all benefit as well. Also, Spittle et al. (2016) mentioned that new dimensions have been created due to the influence of smartphones on businesses. It is also noted that smartphone vendors alone are not getting benefitted but also the app development companies, other related sectors and internet service providers are also getting benefited by the smartphone usage in businesses as noted from (Chan, 2018).

On the other hand, the research on the technological innovations and acceptance by Indian consumers by Vishwakarma, Mukherjee and Datta (2019) revealed that users influence individual attitudes and behaviours necessitating new solutions. They have a generation of digitally intelligent and enterprising consumers with a deep appreciation for the latest gadgets, technology, and a connected lifestyle. Co-creation is gaining traction 31

in a consumption-intensive business like the Smartphone sector, where people's opinions, thoughts, and input are crucial in product invention and development. Spittle et al. (2016) found that a quad-camera with a high pixel count, for example, used to be a desirable feature seen primarily in expensive smartphones. As Indian consumers sought increasingly advanced camera functionalities at a lower price point, these premium features have been revolutionised among entry-level smartphones, gaining widespread acceptance.

G. (2020) noticed that customer experience pertains to a person's entire journey and encounter with a company, its services, and its goods. A user's experience with a specific brand is no longer the user experience. Technology is a great facilitator, and businesses strategically invest in tools and platforms to improve their user experience. And Handa and Ahuja (2020) reported that the smartphone markets are witnessing the immediate effects of the ever-expanding internet ecosystem. Consumers today want a smooth, multi-device journey to complement their connected lifestyle, prompting smartphone manufacturers to deliver a rich and immersive experience throughout the product ecosystem. In contrast, Baber et al. (2020) explored the application of smartphone gadgets in the healthcare system. The study that analysed the impact of wearables in daily life have evolved into extensions of smartphones, providing alerts in the event of a sudden drop in SpO₂ (oxygen saturation), body temperature, heart rate, and other vital signs. Handa and Ahuja (2020) state that with the increased demand for virtual reality headsets to meet gaming needs in 2019, marketers are introducing augmented reality and Virtual reality pitstops into their user journeys.

From the results attained, it has been observed that in the various aspects of life and in society, smartphones have sizeable impacts. The various areas that smartphone highly impacts human life are social life, health, education and business. The individual behaviours and cultural norms are drastically changed by mobile technology. Both on the positive and negative sides, there are higher impacts by the smartphone. The negative influence of smartphone use has to be minimised and controlled in numerous ways in the current society by educating users and educating them on how to use smartphones smartly. There is limitless potential with the use of a smartphone device, and it is considered as the pocket-sized PC.

2.6 Theories of innovation for business development

2.6.1 Hall's Concerns-Based Adoption Model (CBAM)

A quantitative survey with 610 school teachers in Kuwait, Al-Furaih and Al-Awid (2018) found out that the concern and perceptions of adoption of newly developed Smartphone technology strongly associated with the competency level of each smartphone. The study broadly explained the concepts of change, level of application and innovation characteristics based on the Hall's Concerns Based-Adoption Model (CBAM). This model explains the changes in the contribution of an individual in the change process regarding the technology implementation.

Figure 2.2: Concerns-Based adoption model

Source: Min et al. (2017) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

The model primarily emphasises the different factors associated with learning and teaching factors in which the different stages of innovative practices and its effectiveness in managing changes as per the innovations. From the reports of Min (2017), the model has helped in collaborating the existing resource of an organisation with the change facilitators through which the innovative steps are developed as per the company's objectives. The seven stages of the model initiate from stage zero (Awareness) through which the changes through innovation are announced among the employees.

Whereas, Jung (2017) suggesting that to make creative modifications in technological innovation aspect, stages such as informational, personal, and management are followed. Ultimately, the model binds the stages of innovation in smartphone technology by detecting implications and working on restructuring of the technological platform. As the latter phase of the refocusing stage, the emphasis is on monitoring

changes that have been integrated into the firm. However, the model has identified these phases as expressions of concern in which the various levels of emotional changes among employees are controlled, while the model does not offer alternate solutions for challenges in integrating innovation. Moreover, by applying CBAM, Cho et al. (2019) gave a new contribution in the form of different platform divers to the literature on innovations in smartphone industries and strives to resolve the competition problem. Their study emphasizes the importance of the platform paradigm in the mobile sector by illustrating the impact of created company networks on innovation. However, by addressing the issue at a broad industrial level, it misses out on identifying the unique dimensions of this influence on businesses and making specific solutions.

On the other hand, the reports of Trapani and Annunziato (2019) states some of the limitations of the model in which the assumptions such as change process as a continuous instruction represents the lack of effective, innovative management in an event basis. Furthermore, the innovative adoption for employees is considered as the reaction of their emotional and institutional capabilities, which creates a contradiction in managing client-centric diagnosis. The strict adherence of systematic and adaptive change integration for innovation expected from the employees furthermore develops a low efficiency of model output.

2.6.2 Schumpeter's Theory of Innovation

Cantner and Vannuccini (2018) made an attempt to define a new dimension of Schumpeter's Theory of Innovation to explore empirical evidence of the innovative trends in mobile phone sectors regarding the innovative activities by explaining societal challenges that associated with innovation policy and product design. Schumpeter's Theory of Innovation indicates the major comprehension on the innovative and entrepreneurship standards associated with an organisation and different dimensions of a product research and factors affecting these factors's growth are observed to be assistive in managing innovative development. As per the reports of Malerba and McKelvey (2020), the intensive innovation process indicates the functions of an entrepreneur in generating innovative idea combination that assists in managing revolutionary business development as well as enhanced economic development.

Figure 2.3: Schumpeter's Theory of Innovation

Source: Malerba and McKelvey (2020)

Development through innovation is stated as an effective management practice that supports the long-term sustainability of an organisation. The theory emphasis five types of driving factors that manage innovation such as;

- Introduction of a new product or developing an innovative alternative to an

existing product.

- Methodological inclusion is different from traditional production and sales standards.
- Initiating new market potential in new places.
- Developing effective relationship management with new suppliers and distributors.
- Adoption of new industry structures accurate for market development.

The integral result of structural change and substantial driving factors are observed by Croitoru (2017) as the factors that support effective management of innovative development in an organisation. A similar perception is stated through the model through which the opportunity for growth with minimum investment is attained. The model emphasises two stages of innovative development through integrating economic growth and investment factors that support entrepreneurial innovation in which the different factors that support the introduction of a new production process is specified. The reports of Callegari (2018) have stated the importance of effective production management in which an essential factor that supports future development of business growth is integrated into the inclusion of change from the traditional production process. The second stage of the model emphasis on the different factors that is associated with market dimensions such as competitors and employees in which the entire impact of innovation is assessed. Through a critical evaluation of the model stages, the initiation of the initial wave is observed to be generating effective economic development which is not only consolidated within the organisation but also spread towards the economic development. However, the reports of Chen et al. (2020) indicate the lack of effective management practices offered in the model in identifying market liquidation, which can critically impact the overall anticipated innovative level.

2.6.3 The Doblin Framework or ten types of innovation

Another prominent model for innovation is the Doblin Framework. The framework contains ten types of innovations and defines that every innovation can be framed in terms of combinations of these ten innovations (Doblin, 2020). As per the framework,

innovations do not go wrong due to lack of creativity; in most cases, it is due to the low discipline. Thus, the ten types of innovations as per the framework focus on discipline. The Doblin Framework can also be used for the analysis of innovations from an internal perspective. Competitive environment of the organisation and the capabilities of the innovation can also be evaluated using the Doblin Framework. Profit model, network, structure, process, product performance, product system, service, channel, brand and customer engagement are the ten types of innovations proposed by the Doblin Framework.

Profit is among the most important variables for a business organisation. Through innovations, the process of converting the potential and other resources of a company into money can be made more effective. Agwu et al. (2017), states that the innovative profit model can result in an improvement of the overall performance of the firm. Similarly, the network, structure and process of an organisation can be subjected to innovations for making them more efficient. The main characteristic of innovations based on profit, network, structure or process is that these innovations are based on an internal perspective of the organisation and generate from within the organisation.

According to Agwu et al. (2017), product performance and production system-based innovations are concentrated on the main products and services of an organisation. Innovations in product performance focus on introducing new products and updating the current product lineup. Product performance innovations can be used to gain a competitive advantage in the long term. The product system innovations, on the other hand, focus on a combination of products rather than individual products. These innovations lead to the development of ecosystems involving many products of an organisation. The reputation of the organisation plays a key role in such innovations.

Innovations based on service, channel, brand and customer engagement are more related to the customer end. The main objective of these innovations is the engagement of customers, making customers notice the products or services of the firm. Brand innovations lead to the enhancement of the brand image and try to uplift the whole image of the brand. The Doblin Framework is very effective in evaluating innovations and provides an extra advantage when compared to other models. The thing that sets apart the Doblin Framework from other models is the availability of

many options. Most of the innovations in the current business environment is a combination of more than one innovation, and this makes the Doblin Framework a more feasible model.

2.6.4 Roger's Diffusion Model

In the last two decades, the innovation diffusion hypothesis has been a key theory in the study of technology diffusion. Many researches have been done and will be done all around the world using IDT (Zhang, 2018). Innovation Diffusion Theory, which first proposed in 1962 by Roger (1995). This theory aims to figure out how, why, and at what rate new ideas and amplified products in a given society (Rogers, 1962). When it comes to evolution theories, the Innovation Diffusion hypothesis takes a different approach. Rather than convincing individuals to change, it views transformation as primarily involving the expansion or "reinvention" of products and practices to meet individuals and groups' requirements better. Hence it is widely recognise as a useful change model for guiding technological development, in which the innovation is improved and represented in ways that fit the demands of users at all levels (Zhang, 2018). Within the adoption phase, it also emphasises the necessity of communication and peer networking. The spread of innovation, in simplistic words, is the process through which people accept a new concept, product, practise, ideology, and so on Tahir (2015). Throughout time, the new idea or product spreads throughout the population until it reaches a maximum. Innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards are the five types of innovators identified by Rogers. Non-adopters are sometimes included as a different group. The bell-shaped curve graphic beneath depicts the initial five categories, as can be seen. Rogers calculated the percentages in each category, which are pretty close to those seen in a standard bell curv (Huang and Shih, 2017).

Figure 2.4: Roger's diffusion model for Technology adoption. Source: Wells and Nieuwenhuis (2018)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

A study on scope of the Smartphone's adoption in India by Tahir (2015) tried to incorporate the diffusion theory for studying the possibility of diffusion of smart phones in India. They have made additional construction to focus on the technological innovations of smartphones to understand the diffusion of mobile phones in the consumer market of India.

Choudrie, Pheeraphuttrangkoon and Davari (2018) conducted a similar study to discover and explain how silver surfer owned micro-firms in the UK – acquire and use smartphones. To examine the same, they suggested a framework that included Rogers' Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DOI) and the Decomposed Theory of Planned Behavior.

Figure 2.5: A frame work developed using Diffusion Innovation Theory Source: Choudrie, Pheeraphuttrangkoon and Davari (2018)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

2.7 Innovation process and various barriers of performance innovations

According to Torugsa and Arundel (2016), the benchmark is the organisation's innovation performance, which is critical for profitability and success. Furthermore, as Abdullah et al. (2016) point out, those technological achievements are essential for establishing a competitive advantage in the global and local economy. In the smartphone industry, ideas and innovations are critical in identifying problems and developing appropriate solutions to improve client happiness. As previously stated innovation can take the form of modest incremental improvements or freshly developed products/services that are beneficial to increasing customer interest in smartphone businesses (Ávila et al., 2017). Every corporate endeavour aims to increase productivity while lowering operating costs. Although the upfront cost or expense of implementing the new system is higher, innovation saves operational costs (vila et al., 2017). According to Torugsa and Arundel (2016), the use of new technology can help businesses become more efficient and competitive in the market. An innovation management strategy takes advantage of a company's brand recognition and competitiveness. According to vila et al.(2017), the company's innovation performance can be improved by forming a collaboration with potential companies. The cooperation aids the organisation in closing the technology gap it is experiencing and facilitating knowledge transfer (Avila et al., 2017).

According to the study of Ávila et al.(2017), smartphone brands loses the market competition if the competitors are developing cutting-edge technologies and presenting it to the customers. Besides, the brand following out-dated technologies also confronts difficulties existing in the cutting-throat competitiveness (Torugsa and Arundel, 2016). In addition to this, the productivity and efficacy is lowered if the brands are not competitive enough in the market. Over time, many smartphone marketers have lost their business completely, as there is a significant decline in the innovation approach. Moreover, the profit and margins are significantly downsized in brands with lower innovations in the smartphone sector (Torugsa and Arundel, 2016). As per the study of Hameed et al. (2020), the initial approach towards innovation in the case of smartphone brands is noted as the identification of the market needs. Besides, planning innovation is also considered as the imperative approach that improves the

innovation and creative approach of the firm.

In addition to this, Apanasovich et al. (2016) examined that any changes or innovations added into the product/services should be aligned with the needs and interest of the customers. During the planning innovation, strategic vision and business strategy should be specified to streamline the innovation integrated into the firm. For instance, the product quality and services should be revamped if the customers are looking for value for money products (Hameed et al., 2020). Moreover, marketers undergo the continuous process and service improvements in the market and besides, the amendments are highly important for leveraging the performance innovation approach of the organisation. On the other hand, the business might undertake either a new business model or new innovative technologies which improve the organisation and at the major aspect which should be recognised are the employee talents (Hameed et al., 2020). The inferences shows that the brands need to undertake systematic steps to improve innovative business performance.

Based on the study of Mura et al. (2015), the lack of shareholder and stakeholder support is identified as one of the major problems experienced in the innovation performance. The marketers have to attain the complete support and assistance from their key stakeholders and shareholders to operate in the market seamlessly. However, Wang et al. (2015) added that the negative approach of the stakeholders or shareholders in the business sphere would create additional challenges in employing the innovations in the firm. Henceforth, the stakeholders and shareholder's reaction is considered one of the major issues that limit innovation performance (Wang et al., 2015).

In addition to this, the lack of effective leadership is also considered as one of the key limitations that negatively impact innovations in an organisation. Wang et al. (2015) explained that the companies showing the high capability of growth and development possess innovative leaders to manage and organise the workforce. The workforce might be interested in innovations of the organisation, and however, most of the talents only have meager expertise on the reason for innovation and how to accomplish. Mura et al. (2015) argued that the lack of direction would be another significant challenge that put limitations on innovative business performance. Henceforth, the leaders

should have a clear idea of how to accomplish innovations in the organisation (Mura et al., 2015). The innovative ambitions are the core reason for triggering new roadmaps and ideas in the organisation, and therefore, strong direction and leadership is also considered as highly important for lifting the business performance (Mura et al., 2015).

Another issue often confronted in innovation performance is noted as the inability to change with the business's market and economic needs. The complication of the innovation process is one of the major aspects that put limitations on the business to accomplish it (Mura et al., 2015). The planning on innovation should be explicit about attaining better growth in the market, and besides, the strategies and tactics incorporated by the marketer should be able to boost the performance of the company to accomplish success (Wang et al., 2015). Moreover, one of the major aspects that put barriers on the propagation of innovation performance is noted as customer-centric ideas. Wang et al. (2015) explained that most of the marketers fail to attain the expected results is due to the lack of customer-centric idea. Every innovation has to adhere to customer interest, and the innovation might fail if the customer fails to recognise the innovative products (Ritala et al., 2015).

Another significant issue that destroys the innovation of a business is the intensity of competition in the market (Zhao et al., 2016). When too many marketers show up with the same innovative products, the customers might end up choosing the right one after conducting regular analysis and evaluation on the products, pricing and availability. International brands providing an excellent quality of products should be available to all markets, and sometimes, the new product realise might be mainly in the main marketers (Zhao et al., 2016). At the same time, other marketers also come up with similar innovation before international marketers reach. For example, Samsung, Apple Inc and Xiaomi Corporation are international smartphone brands having a higher competitive advantage in the industry. Apple Inc might realise a new technology or innovative products in the United States, made available only to some key markets initially. By that time, the other smartphone brands also develop similar technologies and intensify the competition, which put limitations on the international smartphone behemoth to performance explicitly (Ritala et al., 2015).

Another internal challenge that impacts the innovation performance of the firm is noted as the lack of fund and resources for executing the new idea. Santoro et al. (2020)

explained that most companies lack potential and capabilities to the innovative executive idea due to the lack of fund and resources. The resources might be the fund which is one of the key aspects that enhances the performance of the firm. Santoro et al. (2020) added that fund is not only the most significant aspect but also the lack of advanced technological support to enhance the innovation outcome is another serious crisis which is often seen while implementing an innovation. The study of Ritala et al. (2015) identified that the lack of skilled workers is another major issue confronted while implementing the innovations. Besides, the skilled workerforces that are having high technical expertise and knowledge is imperative to supportbusiness performance. Likewise, the quality of leadership, the ability of followers to understand and act to enhance the innovation is also significant (Santoro et al., 2020).

Most of the organisations fail to identify the right innovations and also fails in executing the new ideas which become later concise into the laboratories. Santoro et al. (2020) argued that most of the organisations lack interest and enthusiasm to show efforts in developing ideas which seem to be unrealistic in the initial phase, and later some other competitors of marketers put efforts and develop the same. Zhai et al. (2018) added that the companies should be willing to try for a change and build better and innovative ideas.

The success and failure of the business mainly adhere to the amount of risk confronted in the organisation, mentioned by Zhai et al. (2018). The pitfalls should be identified, and steps should be ensured to support the business from these issues, which might negatively impact the whole business process. The company should also possess clear-cut expertise on the organisational impediments that might restrain the efforts of the marketers in creating a better growth and development of the firm (Ritala et al., 2015). Transparency and discipline approach undertaken by the firm is one of the major aspects that create a successful transition of the modest business to a highly developed organisation. The innovation journey should be managed by strong people, and henceforth, most of the companies appoint a separate division or management for accomplishing the expected result in the firm (Ritala et al., 2015).

Some of the stages involved in innovation are innovation strategy, innovation sprint, business build-up and innovation enablement (Ritala et al., 2015). On the other hand, Piening and Salge (2015) pinpointed that while moving forward with an innovative idea, the following steps should be focused. The marketers should build a clear-cut strategyand future state vision for supporting the innovation, and this is considered as

the first step. In addition to this, better market opportunities and spaces for trading the innovation should be identified by the marketers before establishing the new idea (Ritala et al., 2015). An eco-system of developing an internal and external team is highly imperative for the organisation in order to achieve the expected results.

The communication channels and methods should be specified for the key players in the organisation who are considered part of innovation performance. The management should provide full support for the workers during the transition state (Ritala et al., 2015). Sources of new business opportunities in the market should also be noted by the marketers before establishing the new idea, pinpointed out by Edquist et al. (2018).

The testing of the product is highly imperative, and at that time, the product might not show the expected performance. The significance of iteration stages is highly imperative after completing these stages. The marketers probe deep into the additional factors that bring about significant changes in product performance. The last stage is to market the newly developed product (Hameed et al., 2020). The study of Piening and Salge (2015) explained that the long-term view and objectives of the firm are highly important and significant for attaining better results through innovation performance. For example, the smartphone developed and sold to the end customers should have greater performance and long-term customer value which significantly impacts the brand performance (Hameed et al., 2020). While implementing an innovative project, the support of the suppliers and vendors is also important. Based on the examination of Edquist et al. (2018), the quality of suppliers is important, especially in the case of the smartphone sector while undertaking a new innovative strategy or system.

The smartphone marketer should keep a systematic and highly confidential contract system to procure best quality products which is a significant aspect which impacts long-term profitability and views of the firm by implementing innovations (Piening and Salge, 2015). In addition to these, smartphone marketers should hire significant talents who can bring potential changes to the organisation, thereby leveraging the chance of successful innovation performance of the business. The overall inferences indicate that innovation performance has certain barriers which need to be eliminated for improving operational performance.

2.8 Latest trends and technologies in smartphone sector

A very strict evolution has been seen in the smartphone sector in the past years, and besides, the evolution continues because the smartphone dominates the world, mentioned by (2020). While taking the case of 2019, the global mobile phone shipment was downsized to a significant level; however, the trends and updates in the case of innovation were at their peak.

Some of the notable innovations in smartphones are considered style, appearance and screen size, examined by Laport-López et al. (2020). The recent phones released have a full screen which is beneficial and highly attractive for providing stunning visual effects. In addition to this, creative development alongside high technological assistance has made it possible for every smartphone company to design alluring phones (Laport-López et al., 2020). Recently, no-notch displays and water-drop notch are some of the other innovations where the marketers are investing time currently. The no-notch displays and water-drop notch aim to maximise the screen size of mobile phones, and besides, the water-drop notch provides 85% of the screen-to-body ratio for leveraging size. On the other hand, many updates such as pop-up camera were employed in the no-notch displays for providing utmost screen size for the users (Petrovčič et al., 2018). However, technology has taken the next level, which is one reason why there are so many advancements seen in the smartphone sector. The Apple Inc has developed a display of 6.10-inch, 1170x2532 pixels and iPhone 12 Pro Max is having 6.70-inch, 1284x2778 pixels (iPhone 12 Pro, 2020). While considering the case of Samsung, the company has introduced Galaxy A02s, which is having a screen size of the 6.50-inch touchscreen, reported by NDTV Gadgets (2020a).

The era of built-in digital cameras on the mobile phone was imperative for taking photos and videos traditionally. However, the development over a period has resulted in the dwindling of conventional technologies in smartphones, thereby leveraged the significance of advanced cutting-edge innovations. The mobile photography was advanced by implementing super-high-definition, low-tech image-capturing devices and besides, most of the top-notch smartphone sellers are dedicated to vending the best products with higher camera features (NDTV Gadgets, 2020b).

While checking the recent features integrated into the Apple iPhone 12 Pro, 12MP + 12MP + 12MP is the rear camera and 12MP front camera (NDTV Gadgets, 2020b). In

addition to this, the iPhone 12 Pro Max is also provided with the same camera specification. On the other hand, the primary camera of Samsung Galaxy A02s is 13MP + 2MP + 2MP (NDTV Gadgets, 2020b). The specification indicates that the mobile photograph is becoming a trending aspect of the market, which could attract the market. The social media is trending with mobile photography, especially in India, and therefore, mobile phone with the cutting-edge photographic specification is boon for the marketers. Most of the camera is in the 21st century having anti-shake technology, night-mode options, high-definition and highly defined video. Currently, 64-megapixel with high-res imaging technology and fitted front camera is highly effective for capturing the market attention.

The wireless standards have developed from 1G, 2G, 3G, 4G and 5G and presently, most of the companies are working on updating their 4G services to 5G (Petrovčič et al., 2018). The 1st generation of wireless cellular technology was the initial standard launched in the United States in 1980 which later progressed into 2nd Generation wireless telephone technology where meagre internet facilities, text, messages were able to send through the mobile phones (Petrovčič et al., 2018). However, the third generation of wireless mobile telecommunications technology has significantly changed the shape and facilities of mobile phones where high-speed data was accessible to smartphones (Kiani et al., 2020). With the advent of 3G, many smartphones have evolved and modified their phone technology. On the other hand, 4th generation is acknowledged as the era of mobile broadband, and from 2010, most of the smartphones are releasing their phones in 4G LTE (Kiani et al., 2020). Presently, most of the phones are coming under this specification, and this is helpful for transferring high-speed data which is approximately ten times faster and quicker than the 3G services (Kiani et al., 2020). The 4G LTE network even led to the downfall of 3G, 2G and 1G services in the market, examined by Petrovčič et al. (2018).

The interface of 5G is highly helpful for contributing to the next generation user experience as the fast processing, data share, download and upload speed are considered as highly advanced when compared with the 4G LTE. The negligible latency, reliability, superior and higher speed of 5G technology is expected to create a new realm in the smartphone sector (Kiani et al., 2020). The advancement in the interface from 4G to 5G creating significant innovations in the technologies used in the smartphones. Narayanan et al. (2020) explained that smartphone companies would

be switching their interface from 4G to 5G, which is attractive. The mobile phones launched initially lacked expandable memory, and presently, 256MB and 192 MB are the maximum internal storage capacity observed in traditional mobile phone technologies (Narayanan et al., 2020). However, Laport-López et al. (2020) examined that 16 GB was the maximum expandable memory seen in the case of traditional mobile phone technologies. In a decade, a significant transformation was observed in smartphones where minimum RAM was noted as 12GB and a maximum of 1T (Narayanan et al., 2020). The RAM is an imperative and crucial device that elevates the users' capability to perform multi-tasking seamlessly (Laport-López et al., 2020). RAM is considered as the main memory of a mobile phone, and memory management is highly imperative for executing the tasks properly. A processor is a chipset that controls everything in a smartphone and makes sure the device works properly. Processor stores users' actions in phones memory which is called Fetch Phase. Number processors, clock speed, are two major factors that determine the processor speed. Laport-López et al. (2020) noted that clock speed determines how many instructions should be executed per second. Processor core assigns the workload that comes to the processor. A14 Bionic with 2990 Mhz, Snapdragon 888 with 2840 Mhz, Exynos 2100 with 2900 Mhz are ranked in the top three of the most powerful processors of a mobile phone. Apple iPhone 12 uses the A14 Bionic processor, which is considered the best and most powerful processor of today. Snapdragon is another widely used chipset with Snapdragon 865+ used in Asus ROG Phone 3; currently, the chipset Snapdragon is introducing in smartphones (Laport-López et al., 2020). Modem, Graphics, and Multimedia engines are necessary components for the processor to work smoothly.

Previously there were only quad-core processors for smartphones, nowadays there are Hexa-core processors, and the most widely used processor is the octa-core processor. A good processor determines the performance for a smartphone, and for example, Razer Phone 2 is considered to be the best gaming phone in the world which has Qualcomm Snapdragon 845 octa-core processor running it (Arshad et al., 2017). Calling, messaging, using other applications, displaying videos, playing mobile games are done by a processor. Lag, a major issue of a smartphone is because of the weak processor with less core or clock speed used in the smartphone (Arshad et al., 2017). A processor is built inside the smartphone which can never be replaced with another

processor or be upgraded to latest chipset according to the user.

Internal memory in the smartphone is used for the data storage purpose, which keeps all files and other data saved even after the smartphone is switched off. There is a fixed hard disk inside the smartphone, and after that, the memory can be expanded by using an external SD card as per user's choice, examined by Sağbaşı et al. (2020). Internal memory is where the software and internal application of a phone are installed. The data stored in internal memory can be erased, added or even be modified as per the user's choice. The lesser the bloatware manufactures install in their smartphones, the more storage a user gets. Previous phones which was not a smartphone had an internal memory of 128 MB – 256 MB (Sağbaşı et al., 2020).

Later as cell phone industry expanded internal memory became an essential part of a phone, and thus manufacturers started increasing the Internal Memory of the smartphones, and nowadays, smartphones are even classified on the basis of ROM. Oneplus 7T, Samsung Galaxy Note10, Oneplus 8 are among smartphones having 256 GB as their internal memory. Internal storage is erased if the user opts for resetting or formatting the phone, hence the data should be backed up to an external hard drive or the internet storage facility (Sağbaşı et al., 2020).

The battery is the most important part of mobile phones as it is the only component which supplies power function the device, mentioned by He et al. (2020). Nick Mediati Lithium-ion batteries are used in almost every smartphone available today. Lithium-ion batteries can store more power in less space, making it an ideal choice to supply power to a mobile phone (He et al., 2020). Blackview is the latest smartphone using BV9100 technology and has the highest battery capacity of 13,000 mAh. Samsung Galaxy S20 Ultra has the highest standby time 11 hrs 58 mins in the smartphone category. Unlike some parts of a mobile phone which can't be replaced, a battery can be replaced with a new one but can never increase the battery capacity in the specific phone. Charging the mobile battery is also important as the fastest charging phone is Oppo Reno Ace which has 4,000 mAh battery capacity and can charge from 0% to 100% in less than 31 minutes when its charged with 65W charger (Mankowski et al., 2016).

SIM card connects the phone to the network. SIM card allows to make calls, message, connect to the internet etc. on the phone. A SIM card has a maximum of 256 KB storage capacity allowing to save up to 250 contacts approximately. A SIM card has a PIN (Personal Identification Number) which protects users from the theft of the SIM

card (Aricat and Ling, 2020). A SIM card can be replaced with other SIM card with different service providers, but the size of the SIM card slot is standard and cannot be varied. Standard, Micro and Nano are the three different types of SIM cards types used today with Nano SIM card opted widely by the cell phone manufacturers to reduce the consumption of space inside a mobile phone (Aricat and Ling, 2020).

The USB port was not used until the introduction of smartphones to the telecom market, and today all smartphones have a USB port which has two functions in a smartphone which is to charge and to transfer data to external sources. Mini-USB was used in earlier smartphones but soon replaced by Micro-USB, and USB-C type is the kind of USB that is used today. Cell phone manufacturers can alter the USB port type as per requirements like iPhone, which uses Lightning Cable Port unique to iPhones only (Mankowski et al., 2016). The USB port can be replaced with a new port and also its cables can be replaced as well. USB adaptors can match the kind of port the smartphone has with the cable user has (Aricat and Ling, 2020). Data can be easily shared between smartphone and a PC via USB port with the help of USB cable connecting in between them, and this kind of data sharing is the most secured way to share data in between two devices when compared to wireless sharing. Sensors are various sensing devices which collect user's data and to work according to the user's needs. Geomagnetic field sensor and Accelerometer sensor are the two sensors provided in a standard smartphone, examined by Ambeth Kumar et al. (2020).

Sensors are used to detect tilt, rotation, displacement etc. and to respond accordingly. The fingerprint sensor is a good example of the usage of sensors in a smartphone as it increases the security of the phone and the contents which are private to the users (Aricat and Ling, 2020). Samsung Galaxy S7 Edge has eight sensors in total which are Fingerprint Sensor, Accelerometer Sensor, Gyro Sensor, Proximity Sensor, Compass Sensor, Barometer Sensor, Heart rate Sensor, SpO Sensor which assumed to be the smartphone with the greatest number of sensors. Companies like Apple, Oneplus, Xiaomi, Asus etc. are including the maximum number of sensors in various variants of smartphones. A sensor can be repaired or even be replaced when it's damaged or not working, but users can't manually add sensors to their smartphone (Ambeth Kumar et al., 2020).

2.9 Evolution of Micromax

Micromax has become the largest domestic company in India. As per the opinion of Chaudhuri and Yadav (2020) the company was famous for its sales of smartphones at a low price. At the beginning of the year, 2010, many Indians were not similar to the company as they did market their product efficiently. The advertisement for the company was very low at that time. In the beginning, the company was only sold the handset with the keypads. But when the smartphone revolution has shaken the global telecommunication market, Micromax was also affected by it. The company has tried a lot of strategies and implemented new methods to survive in the market (Raman and Aashish, 2021).

Marler (2018) cited that the companies have brought many new features to their existing keypad model mobile phones. But by that time, many customers have abandoned the old keypad models and started to purchase the new smartphones. The main reason the customers have abandoned the key pad mobiles as there is no additional feature in it. The keypad models only met the customer's basic needs, but the smartphones came with many features and luxury. When the company analysed the market, and the customers, the company realise that the customers are more attracted to the smartphones than the models which have the keypads. So, the mobile phone company started to manufacture smartphones to the industry. Sarmah, Kamboj and Rahman (2017), mentioned that by the time Micromax has launched their smartphones, there had been many competitors in the market who have already started the selling of smartphones. The smartphones of the Micromax were not a success at the beginning; they have failed to attract the customers. So, the company started to analyse its competitors which gave some insights to the organisation. The company identified the important features of their competitors and also identified the likes of the people which they are attracted to.

As per the findings of Susanto et al. (2018), the company then started to launch many new smartphones to the market where they brought many new features to their product. The features have attracted many customers to the company. This helped the company to survive in the market and generate huge profits. In the following years, the company has seen a huge success in the smartphone industry. Following many new companies have arrived at the smartphone industry, which has greatly affected the Micromax where the sales were very low. The company has adopted many new strategies to compete with its competitors. But by that time other

smartphone companies have taken many of the Micromax's customers to them.

Many Micromax competitors have started to launch their smartphones at a low price, but most of the products had good quality. Panda (2017) mentioned that the competitors of Micromax again started to attract many of their customers. The company has started losing its customers. It has hugely affected the company's total annual income.

The company then started to make its smartphones with many features and sold it for low prices. The main competitors of the Micromax at that time were the Samsung, htc, apple and lava. Chopra and Chawla (2018) noted that when the Micromax started to sell their smartphones at a low price again, many consumers started to buy the product of Micromax. Due to the low price, the company has succeeded in attracting many customers to their company. But when the company sold their products at a low cost, they also lacked the product's quality. Many customers have complained about the radiation of the smartphones of the Micromax, which was very high. Due to the high radiation of smartphones, the company has failed to retain its customers who have affected the company's sales. Many have complained about the build quality of the smartphones due to the low price the company has lacked the build quality.

According to Raman and Aashish (2020), the company has started to use new techniques in their supply chain management and the marketing management of the organisation. The company has started to market its smartphones with huge expenses. The company started digital marketing and advertised their products with celebrities around the world. The company has also increased its budget, which was used for marketing. The company invested huge money in their mass media advertisement. Micromax has also started social media marketing where they paid a huge amount to celebrities to review their product and give feedback to the customers (Chopra and Chawla, 2018).

After spending a huge amount of money on marketing their products, the customers started to purchase their products. Dhir and Dhir (2020) cited that the company also started to make smartphones with good quality and many added features. The customers were very satisfied with their products. The customers started to give feedback to the company about its product which was very positive. This has helped the company to motivate its management and employees. In the following years, the company has started to make good products which have seen good quality. The build quality of the smartphones has eventually started to improve. By getting positive

feedbacks from the customers, the company also could retain its employees.

Where, when the company had lost their sales, the employees started to resign from the company due to the low salary and management quality but later when the company started to sell more products and getting many feedbacks it attracted not only the customers but also the retained their employees which helped the company to increase their productivity and to improve their brand reputation in the smartphone industry. According to Sharma (2017). To boost up the sales of the firm, the company has also started to improve their features on the products. The companies have improved many new features like the camera quality before the camera's quality was very low in the smartphone, but later the company could solve that issue. One of the main issues every smartphone lacked at that time was the battery life of the product. Micromax started to make their products with good battery backup, which was also one reason to attract many customers. As per the opinion of Parmar (2020) in the beginning, the company only provided smartphones with very less storage, but later the company started to manufacture smartphones with large storage space. Many factors have helped the company to increase sales and helped the company to generate huge profits in the smartphone market. Later the company has decided to reduce their expenses which have again affected the quality of the company's products. The customers of the company have started to complain about the products. Mehta and Rajan (2017) noted that some of the products launched by the company had a radiation problem which has affected the sales of the company. The company started to lose some customers because of radiation issues. Many customers started to buy products from other smartphone brands which have caused the sales of the company. As a result, the company has started to see a huge loss in the smartphone industry. The company started to reduce the manufacturing of the smartphone slowly, and they started to launch only one or two smartphones every year after that. This has affected the popularity of the company. Because in this competing smartphone industry, most smart phone brands are releasing many new products to the market. So naturally, the customers have forgotten about the Micromax. But the company can improve their profits by increasing their sales. According to Singh (2019), the company has also failed to create innovative ideas in their firm.

The lack of innovation has hugely affected the productivity of the company. If the company has adopted various innovation strategies, the organization can launch new

innovative products with a lot of new features in the smartphone sector. With innovative products, the company can attract a lot of customers. As the customers are seeking for new innovative products, the company can generate a huge profit. The company can also increase their marketing strategies for improving their product sales and attracting a lot of new customers.

According to Jamalova and Milán (2019), Micromax is one of the famous brands manufactured in India. Micromax produced a variety of electronic equipment through maintaining its quality and minimum price range. In the past year of 2000, Micromax plans to produce a smartphone with 2000. According to the manufacturers, it is a big challenging task to manufacture a qualified smartphone with this minimum price range. In 2010 Micromax became one of India's largest domestic companies that produce the handset with low cost. Later on, Micromax got a standard position in the market when comparing it with other electronic Company.

In the year of 2000 Micromax incorporated with Micromax informatics Ltd by Rahul Sharma and Rohit Patel. Micromax made competition advantages in bringing technological improvement in the Micromax Company. The company developed innovative strategies in to the organization through proper technological implementation. In the past years, Micromax Company faced sustainability in the market due to its poor services. Micromax introduced keypad phones during 2000, but later on, the company introduced extra features through smartphones' implementation (Chopra and Chawla, 2018).

Micromax production later spread in Russia during the year of 2014. According to (Raman and Bharadwaj, 2017), Micromax produced several electronic technologies into the market to meet the competition level. In addition to its, Micromax maintained a minimum price range of product in to the market. In recent years, consumers preferred Micromax Company due to its sales of low-price products. When considering Micromax Company's journey, in the initial stage, Micromax made the people's attention through innovative ideas and user-friendly nature. In the early period, the people in India always try to fulfill their basic needs. Still, in this new scenario, people follow criteria to fulfill their excess need beyond basic needs. Consumer buying behavior is extremely changed. Price and quality of the product should be considered as a significant factor. Most people buy the product with the least prices between 5000 to 10000 ranges during recent years (Anagha, 2018).

These criteria influenced Micromax as well that they were producing their product at a

cheap rate. But later on, the situation changed, the consumption rate of Micromax became less. The implementation of Chinese brands like Xiaomi and oppo created a failure of Micromax Company. According to Hoffman et al. (2017), many of the new companies develop in the market by providing practical innovation into the market. Other companies implement a variety of innovations in the market. Micromax Company produced 3G enabled smartphones, which created a distraction among the consumers level distracted due to the implementation of the 4th generation smartphone which a Micromax company cannot implement. Micromax introduced new advancements due to its failure; new executives and managers were appointed to make notable changes (Arora, 2015). But they were not able to maintain an eye-to-eye contact to bring up effective communication. Lack of communication between executives fails in the organisation. Venu Gopal et al. (2015) reveal that Micromax lacks significant manufacturing facilities while introducing their product into the market.

Moreover, one of the significant factors affected by the failure of Micromax Company is the company's financial requirement. As the marketing of Micromax products declined gradually, it created a destructive impact on the organisation's outcome. Micromax does not have enough financial power to implement advanced technologies. Conflicts are raised in the Micromax management; these results in fewer fund investments. Micromax failed to obtain consumer trust due to its inefficient marketing. Increased marketing of Chinese products in the Indian market fails Micromax. Sundararaj (2015) reveal that failure to maintain effective brand promotion leads to the company's failure.

2.10 Influence of innovation enablers on innovation performance of smartphone enterprises

According to Baga et al. (2016), the critical specifications that determine the exterior and interior factors of the smartphone industry are knowledge management, economic status; leadership skills and networking that are included in the essential enablers of the innovation performance. As per the opinion of Bagga et al. (2016), integration and interpretation are considered as the most significant factors in the Micromax smartphone industry, and it is the critical factor to attain the innovation performance within the industry. From the study of Bagga et al. (2016), leadership skills play a vital role in improving the innovation performance where the leaders motivate, create new

ideas, communicate and inform the entire workforce of the organisation and take appropriate actions for it. Depending upon the creation of unique and competitive insights from the leaders, the organisation can withstand the tight competition and can succeed under high pressure as in Micromax (Jakhar and Bharadwaj, 2018). Additionally, the conquering of the exterior and interior factors of innovation performance can stimulate the growth of the smartphone industry to a greater extent (Nekmahmud et al., 2017).

The exploitation of the internal factors such as knowledge and education can contribute to the production of creative products, and this is done by researching and experimenting, and the results are amalgamated to form the strategy for Micromax industry (Zhang et al., 2018). The conquering of knowledge can affect innovation performance by creating a correlation between the customers and other shareholders that are critical in the Micromax smartphone (Bagga et al., 2016).

The crucial internal factor that can contribute to the better aid of the smartphone industry is the economy (El Kadiri et al., 2016). The financial assistance helps the industry to do research and needed experiments to bring innovative and creative ideas for the sustainability of the smartphone industry (El Kadiri et al., 2016). Regulation policies form the external factors, needed for innovation performance and the type of systems depends upon the innovation taken (Teece and Linden, 2017). The networking factors such as knowledge sharing and information exchange plays a crucial role in the innovation performance of the Micromax smartphone industry (Teece and Linden, 2017).

The smartphone industry is current undergoing transitions as a result of changing customer buying behaviour and cut-throat competition from their rivals. Frequent proliferations in the new and existing products and technical changes made the sector even more dynamic and competitive. Arpaci et al. (2015) identified the smartphone sector as highly innovative segment, where the firms keep on innovating products so as to meet the changing customer demands and interests. Analysing from the industry perspective, it can be said that the manufacturers continue innovations in order to improve the product quality and thereby to gain competitive advantage in the market. This on the other hand ultimately improves the sales performances and customer satisfaction. The notions, competitiveness and innovation are interconnected and need to be managed hand in hand for gaining an enhanced competitive advantage in the market. Zhang et al. (2020) has conducted a detailed research study to

understand the association between the terms innovation and competitive advantage. From the research findings of Cecere et al. (2015) it can be understood that the firm that makes effective utilisation of innovation for gaining competitive advantage is able to generate better sales and profits by meeting the changing customer needs and requirements. The real innovations in organisations are truly challenging and are impacted by many factors for e.g. cultural beliefs and corporate environment. As identified from the research studies of Zhang et al. (2020) creativity, knowledge, imagination and values is driven by the cultural beliefs and corporate environment. The innovation performances of organisation are driven by many factors, and this includes corporate culture, leadership, employee commitments and organisational environment.

Organizational culture refers to the values and ideas that influence employee performance in the workplace. The organisational culture has a significant impact on the organization's ability to innovate. Zhang et al. (2020) found that the company's innovation performance is influenced by its organisational culture in an indirect way. Suifan (2020) did a thorough investigation to determine the relationship between organisational culture, innovation, and company performance. The research was solely focused on Spanish businesses. According to the authors, firms believe innovation to be the only element influencing the firm's long-term growth and success. Cecere et al. (2015), on the other hand, suggested that, in addition to innovations, employee dedication and openness to change, customer happiness with the firm's products and services, and service quality are the other important elements that define the firm's long-term success. The link between organisational culture and the innovation performances of the company has been studied by many researchers. Cecere et al. (2015) has conducted a detailed study to identify the effects of organisational culture and innovativeness on business performances considering the cases in the healthcare industry. The study was conducted by the authors considering 332 employees of private hospitals. Through the study, the authors reached in the conclusion that the firms that embrace positive and people-oriented culture where high degree of knowledge sharing and mutual respect and understanding exists would be able to deliver exceptional innovation performances.

Defining in a simpler term, Cecere et al. (2015) pinned organisational culture as the way things done in the organisation. The organisational culture consists of all the things that define the direction and operations of the company, such as the vision, mission, aim and the goals set. Cecere et al. (2015) pinned that the firms with good and innovative leaders would be able to build a potential team capable of delivering better outcomes. An efficient leader is able to contribute their best towards creating a better team and thereby the innovations of the company. The role played by organisational or corporate culture is undeniable in building a well and capable team adequate enough to support the innovation performances of the entity. As identified from the research studies of Zhang et al. (2020) the corporate culture is a main factor that impacts the frequency and speed of innovation. For e.g. the firms that promote people-oriented culture on the other hand values the people contributions, knowledge sharing and mutual respect and understanding which are fundamental for innovation performances of the company.

It is the culture of the firm that determines the human values and styles, more specifically the personality of managers, the approach of leaders in managing the team and the willingness of the team to take risks and explore the opportunities for the prosperity and wellness of the company (Arpaci et al.2015). In the case of Smartphone industry, some of the major factors that motivate the firms operating the industry to come up with the innovations includes, changing customer buying behaviour and cut-throat competition (Saeidi et al. 2015).

The customer do expects more from the Smartphone manufacturers as their preferences and the desire to experience updates in technology change from time to time. Realising the customer expectations and their preferences, the firms operating in the Smartphone industry pools increased investments towards R&D and aims to bring updates in the technology and launch new products and services that caters to the changing needs of customers. Arpaci et al. (2015) mentioned that the innovations are the important factor that determines the survivability and the competitive advantage of Smartphone manufacturers in the industry. Analysing from the contexts of smartphone industry, it can be said that almost all the smartphone manufacturers are renowned for their breakthrough innovations. Micromax is well known for their great innovations in the technology and updates in the software's. According to the reports of Arpaci et al.(2015) focussing up on existing and upcoming trends, Micromax focussed more on launching innovations that do not compromise on quality and

affordability. The latest launch of smartphones from the Micromax mainly focussed on fulfilling the connectivity, camera quality, battery backup and storage expectations. The studies of Mobility India (2016) identified that, Micromax is already leading in the smartphone market with groundbreaking innovations in its manufacturing service and hardware segments.

Assessing the smartphone industry of India, it can be understood that, on an average the users of smartphone spends 3.5hrs on their phones and uses 4-5GB per month. The growing demand for internet and connectivity can be identified better from the activities of users in their smartphones, especially, the time spend by them on social media pages and various other applications (Cecere et al., 2015). Taking account of customer interests to experience the 4G connectivity, Micromax pooled increased investments to make the upgraded technology, i.e.4G accessible to the customer. Boosting the 4G availability in all the smartphones, Micromax assured customer satisfaction and loyalty towards the brand (Mobility India, 2016).

Customer satisfaction is also among the many factors that lead to innovations in organisations. Saeidi et al. (2015), opine that customer satisfaction is an effective tool to gain a competitive advantage in the market. Increase of competition in the market has pressured companies to focus more on customer satisfaction. The pursuit of customer satisfaction leads organisations to innovations. The need for innovation is important in particular industries, such as the smartphone industry. The smartphone industry is an extremely volatile sector, with one of the highest rates of change. Innovations are a regular occurrence in the industry, with changes in trends happening rapidly. The competition in the smartphone industry is very intense. There are a large number of smartphone brands in the global smartphone market. Even though the customer base of the smartphone industry is high, the large number of brands leads to the fight over customers. Agolla et al. (2018), opine that providing innovations to customers enhance the smartphone user experience. A recent example of this is the introduction of the 120 Hz refresh rate display in smartphones.

The Asus Razer phone 1 was the first phone to introduce 120 Hz in the market. Regular smartphones were set at 60 Hz refresh rate, the addition of 120 Hz meant that the display provides a two times improvement in touch response. This improvement leads to the satisfaction of customers and smartphones that adopted this technology had a competitive advantage over the other brands. In the smartphone industry, the feedback of the customers is utilised for enhancing the customer

experience. As per the opinion of Milner and Furnham (2017), taking feedback from the customers is an integral part of customer satisfaction. Smartphone brands such as Samsung, Apple and One Plus are in the lookout for the opinion of the people.

Surveys, social media platforms and fan interaction events are mostly utilised for gathering customer feedback. When one smartphone brand introduces a new innovation or a new trend emerges in the market, other smartphone companies are also expected to follow suit. The need for the addition of new trends is reflected in customer feedback (Fabijan et al., 2015). Smartphone brands that do not adapt to these needs of customers have to face a decline in sales. Thus, the feedback from the customers pressures the smartphone companies for innovation.

Apart from the innovations to the products, there are also other factors of customer satisfaction that can be enhanced by innovation. Customer service, social media activities and transparency can be enhanced through innovations. In the opinion of Jenson et al. (2016), innovative practices may not be successful at certain times, and this can negatively impact customer satisfaction. Even though customer satisfaction generates the need for innovation, failed innovations are not recommended. Innovations are generally a risky affair with a high chance of failure. If the customer does not like the innovations, customers dissatisfied and have a negative impact on the ability of the organisation for innovations. Many stages of testing are done on new technology to evaluate their feasibility.

2.11 Study on the evolution of Smartphone industry in India since last decade

In the past decade, the greatest bet of tech innovation is the smartphone and in the daily lives of the individual's it plays an important role. Sudevan (2019), pointed out that among the global topmost valuable brands, three out of ten brands have their fortune in the smartphone industry that is for the organisations such as Samsung, Google and Apple. At the present moment, the smartphone industry has crossroad in time that is initially the countries such as Europe and the US were focussed by the smartphone sector due to high smartphone penetration. Due to the penetration of smartphone growth rate hardware sales growth had been stunted. In current days the manufacturers of the smartphone industry are highly focussing on the country India due to the fastest-growing rate of smartphones in India.

From the report of Borde (2017), it has been observed that during the year 2014 in the first quarter [Q1] the total smartphone sales was observed as 17.59 million across India. However, in the year 2015 of Q1, it has increased marginally to 18.4% in YoY growth that is improvement 4.6% in growth. In the following years also, there were considerable improvements observed in the smartphone sector that is during the year 2016 of Q1 23.5 million were shipped and indicated a YoY growth of 27.7%. In the year 2017 also, the impressive growth has been observed that is in Q1 of 2017 YoY growth rate of the smartphone industry is observed as 14.9%. From the report of Dudley (2019), it has been observed that at the beginning of the year 2014, the landscape of smartphone sectors has been dominated by Samsung and other local vendors such as Lava and Micromax.

During 2014 of Q4, Samsung has been dethroned by Micromax in their sales. In the upcoming financial years of 2015 also, the dominance of Indian vendors continued, but the situation has changed very rapidly. However, in later years that during the year 2016 in sales subsequent explosion has been observed due to the entry of Chinese smartphones in the Indian market. Asher (2020), pointed out that with the various factors such as competitive pricing, new product features and with aggressive marketing strategy, the vendors like LeEco, Vivo, Oppo and Xiaomi have been developed. In the Q1 of 2017, the dominance of Chinese vendors is continuing, and the demand increases day by day due to the growth and demand of 4G enabled handset and in latter on days Reliance Jio has launched the 4G service at full pledge. From the study, it has been observed that a very consistent seasonal pattern has been followed by a smartphone.

Throughout this literature review, the major insights are gathered on the influence of innovation enablers and innovation performance. The study reveals that to become successful in markets, organisations must include in innovative activities which output profitable performance and to increase the market value. Moreover, the research study mentioned in detail about the key enablers on innovation performance and it is summarised under the internal and external dimensions. This section has addressed those innovations have a direct impact on the performance and competitiveness of organisations. However, the review deals with the influence of innovation enablers on innovation performance of smartphone enterprises.

2.12 Prevalence of Smartphone Addiction in India

India has taken numerous moves toward digital government, beginning with computerization in the 1980s (Jain, Gedam and Patil, 2019) and India had almost 1.5 billion mobile phone users in 2019 (Dharmadhikari, Harshe and Bhide, 2019). According to the statistical analysis Report of Digital Governance of India, India is anticipated to have 829 million mobile phone users by 2022 and, paired with the widespread availability of hybrid smartphones, can connect every Indian person to a mobile device within the next three to four years (Bharucha, 2018).

Mahadevaswamy and D'souza (2016) state that the increased availability and affordability of internet services have been a significant driver of India's digitalization progress. As a result, the number of internet users has risen fast, surpassing 500 million in 2019. This figure is predicted to reach 829 million by 2022, as more Indians access internet-enabled smartphones. According to Khan and Rahman (2019), nearly 97 per cent of internet users in India use smartphones to access the internet. As a result, India's smartphone sector has increased in the previous four years. Increased internet penetration in rural India has fueled this rise, with rural India currently accounting for 40% of the active number of internet users. Increased smartphone affordability, lower smartphone prices, an increase in the number of rural users, linguistic availability, and numerous government efforts have contributed to this increase in smartphone users (Naik, M., Bhatia, A. and Tiwari, K. 2020). Following the 2016 telecom sector upheaval, the cost of a gigabyte (GB) of mobile data dropped from INR 152 to INR 10 in a year, providing mobile internet available to a significantly more significant proportion of Indians than ever before. This shift in cellular data pricing resulted in a 129 per cent increase in overall monthly data usage from 2015 to 2018. With 9.8 GB spent per user in 2018, India set the world record for monthly internet usage, which is expected to quadruple to 18 GB by 2024. This expansion is aided by the continued implementation of 4G technology, which seeks to give consumers more reliable service and incredible speed. Increased local manufacture, aided by the government's Phased Manufacturing Program, and a growing smartphone market have driven down smartphone prices. Manufacturers are growing production and increasing investment in the Indian smartphone industry in response to increased demand.

2.13 Research Gap

From the review of relevant studies, it has been observed that several studies have been carried out based on the smartphone sector. Researchers were trying to find out the technological acceptance of consumer and their notions. In some of the studies by Hubert et al. (2017) and (Baber et al., 2020), it can be clearly found that studies were specifically interested in technological updation and its impact on society. By analysing the product development and influencing factors, researchers were trying to find out the market competitiveness among popular brands such as Apple and Samsung. Additionally, the studies based on the exploration of innovation strategies mainly led to explain the overall business performance of a specific brand.

From Hubert et al. (2017), there has been wide popularity and huge demand among the general public in the corporates for the use of smartphones where it is seen higher demand. It is understood that the utilisation of smartphones in consumers' day-to-day activities is getting influenced in several surprising ways. It is identified that there has been more than 1 billion users and 2.5 million apps approximately. Moreover, research regarding the technological updation has led to discover the adverse effect of smartphone usage in adults (Handa and Ahuja, 2020)

Similarly, the studies of Spittle et al. (2016) and it has been observed that mobile devices have been utilised by 80% of the whole world population and in the US alone, 42% of mobile subscribers use smartphones. Similarly, from Spittle et al. (2016) and (Hervas-Oliver et al., 2017)

It has been observed that researchers explicitly try to disclose ways each depends on the mobile phone and the percentage of consumers depending on such devices. Also, their findings depict that the present generation has been widely using smartphones showing that smartphones are an inevitable part of the current population worldwide. However, it has also been observed that considerable growth is attained from the sides of tablets and smartphones still millions of PC is continued to sell in future.

The past studies were focused on emerging trends and innovation in the smartphone sector. The studies were entirely focused on the smartphone sector. There were less or no studies conducted to identify innovation performance and its use in the various smartphone brands or companies. This shows that studies have to be conducted in each smartphone companies to understand the innovation performances individually

that they adopt.

The present studies showed that Micromax lacked its innovation performance, leading them to face issues in the smartphone sector. In the current study, the study's intention is critically analysing the significant influencers of innovation performance in the Smartphone industry by focusing on the scenario of Indian consumer electronics firm Micromax Informatics. The changes bring out on the society by the smartphone are analysed through the research and to evaluate the complexities of innovation performance in Micromax Informatics' perspective. Besides, countless marketers are battling for highest market share in the smartphone sector, especially in the Indian market. On the other hand, the Chinese smartphone brands have attained unbeatable fame in the market due to the quality of cutting-edge technologies; designs and affordable pricing range, by analysing comprehensively and then aiming to deliver recommendations for Micromax informatics enhance innovation strategy and withstand innovation performance.

Summarising the inferences, the innovation performance was comprehended as the ability or capability of a firm to transform the input into outputs with the effective utilisation of all the available resources in the organisation. Besides, product enhancement is one of the major forms of innovation in the smartphone sector. In addition to this, the literature section also pointed out that one of the major drivers of innovation is considered as the strong customer demand for advanced and cutting-edge products from the marketers. In addition to this, the literature section provided an overview of the hike in sales and production of mobile phones when compared to other electronic accessories in the market. Besides, the change in demographics and the need for better products in the market elevated the interest of marketers to provide best and unique products into the market. The model also pinpoints that the effective use of technology is important for the firm to capture better market attention. Main types of innovations were also comprehended in this study, and besides, breakthrough innovations, sustaining innovations, basic search, disruptive innovations and innovation matrix are categorised of innovation with respect to the Innovation matrix model.

2.14 Proposed Conceptual Frame work

This research's conceptual model is adapted from Roger's Diffusion theory, Dublin's Innovation Framework have been applied. The organisational performance is improved by the innovations implemented in the firm (Spittle et al., 2016). In addition to this, the sales and profit of the smartphone company are enhanced by the innovations and technological improvements of the firm. Besides, the competitive advantage of the company has been improved by innovation performance. The innovation performance is the primary aspect that leverages the achievement of organisational goals. Henceforth, the inferences make it clear that innovation performance is vital for the development and success of the organisation, especially in the case of the smartphone sector.

The study of Erasmus et al. (2015) added that the efficiency of leadership helps in codifying the team's activities and directing the workforce towards the innovative path. Besides, the research and development strategies are undertaken by the firm foster innovation performance. Moreover, organisational culture is an important aspect that supports or obstruct the innovation flow in an organisation. The current study examines the need for innovation performance for enhancing the operations of Micromax Informatics. The marketers should probe deeply into the market competition before undertaking adequate steps in innovative performance. Customer preferences and trends should be examined deeply for adopting the proper method for innovation performance. The conceptual framework shows a significant relationship between the factors influencing innovation performance and the significance. Besides, the current study considers the significant drivers which elevate the innovation performance of Micromax Informatics in the smartphone sector. Therefore, the current study focuses on the intricacies, particularities of innovation, and significant contributors to innovation to improve organisational performance.

Figure 2.6: Conceptual Framework

Source: Created by author

2.15 Summary

This chapter has undergone a literature review, where the literature review was conducted to evaluate innovation performance in the Indian smartphone sector critically. The review has discussed the innovation theories for business development, such as Hall's Concerns-Based Adoption Model, Schumpeter's Theory of Innovation. Besides, the economic development of an organisation is also improved by considering these theories. On the other hand, the Technology Acceptance Model is also considered an effective method that fulfils the innovative performance of an organisation. The types of innovation in the business are discussed in the review in the next section. The study mainly focused on the innovation matrix model and The Dublin Framework or ten types of innovation. The Dublin Framework, which provides broader expertise on the significant ten types of innovation, is also presented in this study. The lack of leadership, R&D issues, lack of investments, planning issues, sudden changes in the customer interest, demand fluctuations, competitors bringing similar products into the market at competitive pricing are some of the significant limitations incurred in the innovation activities of the business.

However, the business ecosystem could be enhanced by adopting prompt and adequate steps of innovation which are also mentioned in this chapter. The current chapter also explained the modern trends in the smartphone sector and the evolution of the smartphone sector in the Indian market. This current chapter also explained the link between the past studies and conceptual framework to fortify the study. The innovation process and the various barriers of performance innovations were also discussed in the review, and the latest trends and technologies were discussed in the next sector. The trends and customer necessities are changing day by day. Hence this review shed light on the current trends in the smartphone sector. The influence of innovation that enables smartphone enterprises' innovation performance was explained in detail through literature. Thus, the report helped study the smartphone industry's evolution since India's last decade and has mentioned the literature's conceptual framework.

Chapter 3: Research methodology

3.1 Introduction

In the research methodology chapter, the various methods used by the researcher for conducting the study on the topic a critical evaluation on the innovative performance of organization in smartphone industry has been deliberated. In the first section of the methodology chapter the rationale for conducting the current study on the topic have been detailed. In the research methodology chapter, the various sections that are detailed on conducting the study are research philosophy, approach, design, data collection method and sampling. These above stated sections in the research methodology are undertaken or the methods are chosen based on the formulated research question.

In the step-by-step format is the various phases of the research methods chosen has been discussed. The samples selected for conducting the study has been detailed in the sampling section and how the data needed for the study has been accumulated has been detailed through the data collection section. Due to the current pandemic situation of Covid-19 the samples needed for conducting interview and survey has been accumulated through e-mail. Moreover, in the following chapter of research study that is after the research methodology chapter the accumulated data through data collection process will be analysed. Moreover, in this chapter while conducting research study the various ethical issues confronted has also been detailed. During the business or any research study the moral conflicts that occurred has been detailed in the ethical issue section. The management's consent before conducting the interview is one example of ethical issues, and the other issues confer in this section of the chapter. Finally, in the last segment of the chapter the limitations confronted while conducting study will be detailed.

3.2 Rationale for selecting the study

The main purpose of conducting the current research study is to conduct critical evaluation on the topic impact of innovative performance of the organization in the smartphone industry and for conducting the study effectively the case of the firm Micromax Informatics in India have been focused. For conducting the study effectively, the primary data collection method have been utilized and the primary

data needed for the study has been accumulated using both interview and survey strategy. The interpretivism philosophy have been utilized by the researcher for conducting the current study effectively. For accumulating the exact data related to the research contexts is the researcher have selected the particular research philosophy and that also helps the researcher in accumulating valid information and data related to the study issue. In the research methodology the various important sections to be detailed over the study are research philosophy, research approach, research strategy and research design.

Cazeaux (2017), pointed out that with the elements such as development of knowledge, nature and source is the concept research philosophy deals with. In addition, it can be stated that research philosophy can be thus understood as the belief with which the data associated with the successful completion of the research can be collected, analysed, and used. However, Cazeaux (2017) noted that there are four main trends of research philosophies that have distinct and unique ideologies. The four main types of research philosophy used while conducting the research study are pragmatism, positivism, realism and interpretivism philosophy.

According to the views of Dougherty et al. (2019), it is mentioned that positivism research philosophy claims with the belief of understanding the social world in an objective way. In this philosophy, the researcher is believed to be an objective analyst and dissociates from accepting personal values and carried out research independently. In contrast to this idea, the philosophy that relies upon the belief that the principles cannot be sufficient to understand the social world can be recognised as interpretivism research philosophy. Further, the interpretivism research philosophy entails that the social world can be interpreted in a subjective manner. Thus Moon et al. (2019) noted that interpretivism philosophy works on the basis of the researcher playing a specific role in evaluating the social world.

On the other hand, the pragmatist research philosophy can be regarded as the philosophy that is based on facts. Thus, this philosophy states the importance of addressing the research problem to choose the appropriate one for a research. Further, the realistic research philosophy can be observed to be followed in researches on the basis of the principles include the positivism and interpretivism research philosophies. De Langhe and Schliesser (2017) pointed out that the realistic research philosophy thus works on the basis of the perceptions of the subjective nature of the humans.

For conducting the current research study, the researcher had utilised interpretivism research philosophy and on using this research philosophy the researcher can critically evaluate the details of innovation performance in the environment of the Micromax Informatics. For conducting the current research study on using the interpretivism philosophy the research study issue can be studied with great level of depth. On using interpretivism philosophy the primary data generated might be related with the high level of validity as the information accumulated on using that philosophy will be highly trustworthy and honest. For attaining the expected research outcomes, the utilization of interpretivism research philosophy is observed to be the suitable one as concerning the innovation performance of Micromax the researcher can attain the expected outcome. The research study that are conducted based on attaining qualitative and quantitative results the more suitable research philosophy to be utilized in the study is interpretivism research philosophy as this philosophy helps the researcher in demonstrating patterns and trends regarding the research issue. Moreover, on using interpretivism studies the primary data gathered might be related with the high level of validity as information in such studies are observed to be highly trustworthy and honest.

Hughes and Sharrock (2016) observed that the detailed plan and procedure that comprises of steps ranging from broad assumptions to detailed methods of data collection, analysis, and interpretation can be termed as the research approach. Moreover, based on the research issue addressed in the study is the research approach selected. Qutoshi (2018) opined that the importance given to hypotheses within researches determines the deductive or inductive research approaches being used for the research. While the deductive research approach is engaged in testing the validity of the existing theories or hypotheses, the inductive approach is about formulating new theories and hypotheses for the carrying out of the research.

On the other hand, Cazeaux (2017) illustrated that regarding the incomplete observations, puzzles or surprising facts that are detailed at the beginning of the study the explanation can be provided using abductive research approach. The absence of any existing literature related to a topic can necessitate the researcher to follow the inductive research approach. The inductive research approach follows steps of observation, observing a pattern, and developing a theory. Conversely, Dougherty et al. (2019) pinpointed that the deductive research approach is applied in contexts that are present with literatures, testing these theories. Thus Moon et al.

(2019) pointed out that deductive research approaches are equipped with the following steps from starting with an existing theory, formulating a hypothesis, collecting the data, and analyse the results as well.

For conducting the present research study on the topic, a critical evaluation of innovative performance of the organization in smartphone industry on focusing the case of the firm Micromax the suitable research approach method to be used is inductive research approach. On using this inductive research approach based on the available evidence a comprehensive data in relation to the current research topic can be accumulated (Cheng and Tisi, 2017). The inductive approach coupled with interpretivism philosophy can explicitly support the carrying out of the research as it is the most appropriate one for studies that require both qualitative and quantitative data to gather conclusions. Further, De Langhe and Schliesser (2017) noted that on using the inductive approach in the research study no any formulation of hypothesis is involved. That is during the research process on using this approach it begins with research questions, aim and objectives that are to be attained on conducting the study. For detailing the casual relationship between the variables involved in the study the inductive research approach has been used. Moreover, on using the inductive research approach the concepts within research and the research findings can be generalized and accomplished.

Lobe et al. (2020) pinpointed that the systematic and structural approach followed by researchers to gather relevant observations and data can be regarded as the data collection procedures. Regardless of whether the research is done for business, governmental or business purposes, data collection can be characterized as the procedures that enable to gather first-hand knowledge linked with a research problem and thus gather original insights related to the research problem. However, Yates and Leggett (2016) opined that in regard to collecting the data, the researcher requires addressing the aims and objectives of the research along with the type of data and the methods that are to be applied for the efficient accumulation of data linked with the research study. However, the research problem determines the type of data that is to be collected for the research. It can be either qualitative or quantitative data. Yates and Leggett (2016) noted that the research that is entailed to be done with figures and statistics can be identified as quantitative research while the word sand interpretations of the respondents directly consider for qualitative researches.

Quantitative researches are majorly conducted to test the theories or assumptions and

thus can be used to set generalised contexts related to a particular topic. The common quantitative methods that are followed in researches can be revealed to be experiments, observations recorded as numbers, and surveys with closed-ended questions. On the other hand, Gill and Baillie (2018) mentioned that the qualitative research can be revealed to be researches that collect data expressed in words thereby being useful to understand concepts, thoughts, or experiences.

Further, the qualitative researches can also be realised to be applicable in studies that are relied upon accumulating in-depth insights on research contexts that are not well understood. However, McLain and Kim (2018) included that the most common methods through which studies conducted are qualitative researches that is interviews with open-ended questions, observations described in words, and literature reviews that explore concepts and theories.

Surveys being the most commonly used quantitative research methods are closed or multiple-choice questions that are distributed among a sample population to gather the most relevant and valid responses. Gundry and Deterding (2019) commented that experiments are another method of carrying out quantitative researches wherein the variables are controlled and manipulated to establish cause and effect relationships. Moreover, observations are quantitative research methods carried out to observe subjects as in natural environments provided the variables are not controlled. Further, the qualitative data collection methods applied include interviews focus groups, and literature review.

Herein, Sadan (2017) noted that the interviews are entailed verbally asking the prospective respondents with open-ended questions, while focus groups are discussions conducted among a group of people regarding a context to collect opinions which can be used for further research. Further, McLain and Kim (2018) suggested that the search and data collection that is done through assessing the published works of others can be regarded as literature reviews as well. In certain researches, there comes a need for both qualitative and quantitative researches for which the mixed method approach is accomplished by carrying out both surveys and interviews or simultaneously covering qualitative and quantitative research methods for the study. The primary data collection methods applied can be observed to be qualitative or quantitative a poor even in some cases mixed and the research methods are decided in accordance to the nature of data involved for the research.

The researcher has used the primary data collection method to collect data through the interview. The interview methods help in gaining actual and up to date data about the Micromax and the amount innovation performance it possess. Moreover, credible data regarding the barriers the company face in innovation, the amount competitive pressure and the factors which hinders their growth can be easily acquired using the interview method. However, the current researcher gathers the most appropriate and relevant data related to the research problem through conducting interviews.

Further, the data collection procedures can also be categorised into secondary and primary data collection methods. Secondary data, as the name suggests can be related to data that is available in published books newspapers, journals, magazines, or any other write-ups. There are possibilities that abundantly rich content related to research contexts is available in the above-mentioned sources irrespective of the research area involved as well, as stated by Gill and Baillie (2018).

Thus, the exploitation of a suitable set of criteria to choose the relevant secondary data for the research can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the research as well. These criteria can be the time of publication, the credibility of authors, reliability, and quality of the source, and many others. Moreover, the primary data is a more flexible approach can be accounted for as the interviews and interviewers can gather a better response than mailed surveys. Further, the interviewers can even judge the nonverbal behavior of the respondents. Additionally, it can also be comprehended that interviews enable the researcher to have better control over the order of questions and can even evaluate the spontaneity of the respondents as well. Apart from this, it can also be observed that through conducting interviews the researcher can gather responses that are directly connected with their feelings and thoughts related to the research, apprehending even over the minute details regarding their statements. Although even if it may take plenty of time, the researchers can carry out the researches with much quality and accuracy when interviews are involved and the respondents have interacted directly with the list of questions., Many of their attitudes and opinions can be guessed out from their body language as well even if they hesitate to give any clear answers for the questions presented before them.

3.3 Research design

Research design can be realised as the framework of research methods and techniques that can be selected to conduct the study in the most effective way. Through the understanding of the research design concept, the researchers can

understand the methods that are best suitable to find answers that are relevant to the goals and objectives of the study undertaken. Accordingly, Schoonenboom and Johnson (2017) commented that the major characteristics that are considered for the appropriate choice of design within a study include neutrality, reliability, validity, and generalisation.

Likewise, there exist different types of research designs that can be made well in utilisation such as experimental, descriptive, correlational, and explanatory. The experimental designs are said to be used in researches that are mainly entwined in defining the causal relationship between the variables included in the study. On the other hand, Rahi (2017) mentioned that the correlational research design can be observed to be non-experimental enabling research to establish the relationship between two closely connected variables.

In addition to this, Tobi and Kampen (2018) disclosed that the explanatory research design is about using the ideas and thoughts of the researcher to further explore their theories. Such researches can be observed to be explaining in detail the unexplored aspects of a subject and review about the why, how, and what questions regarding the research context. Nevertheless, Schoonenboom and Johnson (2017) pinpointed that descriptive designs are majorly linked with describing the situation or the case under the research study and can be found to be a theory-based design that is involved in procedures such as gathering, analysing, and presenting the collected data. Thus, the insights regarding the why and how of the research can be accumulated through descriptive designs. Further, Rahi (2017) opined that exploratory designs are followed by researchers when a clear idea regarding the research topic is not available for the considered research context.

The exploratory research design is referred to as the first step of the data analysis as well as, familiarisation of data done in this step, and also information generated as a next step. Moreover, it has been opined by Thomas and Lawal (2020) by the utilisation exploratory design the researcher deeply exploring the research topic into a wider range. Moreover, the exploratory design is assistive to generating new theories from scratches, and this design well-defined design theories adopted for applying them in certain areas. Munawar et al. (2018) pinpointed that research questions formulated in the study will be explored using exploratory research design. Moreover, when there are lack of studies concerning research study issue for reference then the researcher can use exploratory research design.

Explanatory research design is selected when the investigator has to determine the issue that has not been studied in detail. For getting a final conclusion of the interpretation of the research issue is this explanatory research design used. Subedi (2016) stated that explanatory design is being concentrated on every part of the research context primarily on how and when it is performed. Though, it does not express the essential and actual activities that must be considered in real life. Moreover, the explanatory research is intended to elucidate why certain activities are carried out in such a manner (Bowen et al., 2017). However, the explanatory research design clarifies the reason behind the specific activities performed (Atmowardoyo, 2018).

Based on the formulated research question is the research design needed for the has been utilized. When three research designs are compared, it has been inferred that exploratory design is unstructured while descriptive is structured design; on the other hand, the explanatory design is highly structured. Siedlecki (2020) noted that descriptive design possesses probability sampling and an overall rigid design and has an objective of describing characteristics and functions.

The research design that has been used in this research is the descriptive research design. The selection of descriptive design may assist the researcher in analysing the actual cause and effect of the research issue and also help in identifying solutions for improving the overall performance of the organisation. On employing a descriptive research design on this topic help in easily identifying the characteristics of the population that has been interviewed and from that, the researcher can easily extract the relevant information needed for the study.

Unlike other research design methods, descriptive is most useful for probing the characteristic of problem or the topic in depth and currently, this method is most appropriate for examining the innovation performance in smartphone sector. In addition to this, validity and reliability of the study could be assured through the descriptive research design method. In addition to this, the descriptive research design was helpful for comprehending on innovation crisis in the case of Micromax Informatics. The current research was highly benefitted by the integration of descriptive research method where the researcher was able to attain detailed information of the innovation performance in the context of Micromax Informatics. The descriptive research in the current research work provided a clear-cut overview and

link between the variables selected for the study.

A descriptive research design usually starts with very less knowledge about the topic and this was evident in this topic as well. The researcher had very less information regarding the innovative performance of the Micromax informatics and the challenges it faced in its business. Using the descriptive design, the researcher has first identified the research problem and then described about the problem with the help of qualitative and quantitative research methods. The researcher has developed different themes related to the research question and objectives from the interview data that has been collected. Comprehending these themes with the help of literature review and the findings from the data analysis section, the researcher has ended up in getting the relevant outcome about the study.

The utilisation of descriptive research designs can be involved with the application of the special type of research designs that can be case studies, observation, or surveys. These data collection methods however present a multi-faceted approach for the data collection process thus enabling a broader view of the research context. Further, the research on innovation performance in the context of Micromax using the descriptive design facilitates to be quicker, easy, and cheap to conduct. Tobi and Kampen (2018) regarded that the area level availability of exposure data can be accomplished through descriptive design.

3.4 Staging the research

Selecting the research study topic is observed to be the first stage to be utilized in this study and the selection of the study topic can be done on identifying the research gaps in the study. For the selected topic getting approval from the tutor is the very next stage as after getting approval only further study can be conducted. After the approval, the researcher first identified the research problems, and from that developed the research question and research objective. Further, the researcher has collected data through the interview method and the accumulated data through interview has been analysed using thematic analysis method and acquired relevant information related to the research objective.

In this research, the literature review of the current study has undergone the innovation concept and the various models related to that. The information or data related to the study has been collected using several secondary sources that provided a good and effective information related to the influence of innovation enablers on innovation

performance of smartphone enterprises. Several sources were used to accumulate the data to gain knowledge about the innovation enablers on innovation in the smartphone performance, where it helped in sorting out the issue encountered with efficiency.

The research must be carried out in a structured way, encouraging the investigator to shift from a general concept to statistically rigorous research results that allow the idea to be strengthened with new innovations. Pustulka et al. (2019) noted that research initiatives could be focused on information acquired from past research, and it is important to provide a detailed understanding of the problem to be studied. Moreover, it is important to understand the status quo in that field to progress the limits of information within such a particular area, and this requires familiarity with the philosophy and terms accompanying that subject.

Saleem and Mehmood (2018) mentioned that before the beginning of the investigation, a literature review is generally carried out and reference books may provide the latest information on a subject because of the time required for the report. Furthermore, an assessment of the current results from research papers and conferences can affect the methodology used in the research (Berghaus and Back, 2016). Overall, the technologies currently available ensure that it is easy to scan the literature, and even obtain research papers, with minimal effort. The majority of the literature review commences from one of the many accessible electronic sources, using the name of the author or a mix of properly selected keywords.

A multi-step process in which the steps are interconnected with the other steps along the way has been the scientific research process. In order to guarantee that the improvements are replicated across the process, where changes are made in one stage of the process, the researcher analysed all other steps. From the reports of Pringle Barnes and Cheng (2019), it has been inferred that identifying a topic or creating a study query is the first step in the process. The investigator understands more about the issue under investigation now that the problem is defined, and to do so, the researcher studies the literature relevant to the research issue. Moreover, this step gives a simple awareness of the specific problem. The literature review also reminds the investigator what experiments were performed in the past, how these researches have been carried, and the results in the issue field (Pringle Barnes and Cheng, 2019).

The initial problem found in the first stage of the procedure is always too wide or wide

in nature as well as in stage three of the system, the investigator discusses the issue and shortens the scope of the research. It can be achieved only when the literature has been examined, and the information acquired from the literature review directs the investigator to explain and refine the research project.

Terms and definitions were words or phrases contained in the current study objective statement or the study summary, and when they refer to the study, these elements need to be clearly described. Based on whoever is reading the report, words or concepts often have multiple meanings and, to eliminate uncertainty over what the terms and phrases mean, the writer may explicitly describe them for the research (Mashayekhi and Haji Azimi, 2018). A particular category of persons, services, park growth, staff reviews, initiatives, financial status, marketing activities, or the incorporation of innovation into operations may be interested in research studies. The research plan is referred to as the instrumentation plan.

The instrumentation plan acts as the outline for the research as a whole, defining who participates in the research (Mashayekhi and Haji Azimi, 2018). The exact research starts with the collection of data after the instrumentation plan is finished, and the collection of data is a crucial phase in supplying the information necessary to address the test query. Each analysis entails gathering certain kinds of data through literature or subjects to address the research question. It is also possible to gather data in the form of words from a survey, a questionnaire, findings, or literature.

The final stage culminates with all the time, commitment, and money devoted to steps 1 through 7 of the research processes. Ultimately, the investigator has data to analyse in order to address the study query, and in the instrumentation plan, the investigator defined how to analyse the data, noted by (Sandnes and Eika, 2018). The investigator is now evaluating the data as per the schedule and then reviewing and summarising the findings of this study in a way specifically relevant to the research questions.

However, it is needed to devote time and resources to the preparation phase by undertaking experiments following the eight stages of the experimental study process. If time is short or the work is performed at the last minute, an analysis may not be conducted using the scientific testing method. Moreover, investigators who do this do the analysis that results in either incorrect assumptions or findings that are not useful to the firm. In the end, a report must be prepared and the recommendations and conclusions communicated to management, lawmakers, and program managers for

the planned decision-making intent.

3.5 Overview of the fieldwork procedure

Derakhshan et al. (2019) commented that field research could be termed as the qualitative method data collections carried out by researchers with the intention of observing, interacting and understanding people within natural environments. Just like natural conservationists observe the behaviour of animals within natural surroundings, social scientists carry out field research by interviewing people or observing them and study how people behave or react to situations around them. However, Naveed et al. (2017) noted that field research focuses on several methods like direct observation, limited participation, analysis of documents and informal interviews and surveys etc. Despite, field research is characterised to be involved with qualitative methods, it often comprises of quantitative research in it.

The present research carrying out the primary data collection is equipped with methods of field research like interviews and surveys. Lawal (2019) mentioned that the qualitative interviews are close-ended questions that are asked directly to the research participants. However, these qualitative interviews can be either informal or conversational, semi-structured, standardised and open-ended or even a mix of all these methods.

However, any of these methods enables the researcher to gather an enriched and abundant data required to be sorted. Anyhow, Stankevich (2017) opined that it is also a fact that the intensity of timelines and costs involved for the research, field researches can be characterised to be quite challenging to execute, plan and implement. Therefore, some basic principles that researcher have to take a look in order to carry out field researches efficiently are building the right team, recruit people for the study, data collection methodology, site visit, data analysis and communicating results.

Moreover, Sidel et al. (2018) illustrated that it is important for the field researcher to keep an ethnographic record when conducting field researches. Despite being expensive and time-consuming, most of the researchers prefer to conduct the field researches based on four main reasons that support their research study. Sidel et al. (2018) pointed out that the main reason found to be overcoming the issue of any lack of data it may be quite difficult for the researcher to gather enough relevant previous researches and information related to the research context. Further, the field

researches are also facilitating for researchers to understand the accurate contexts of the study. Additionally, the field researches help to increase the quality of data and also to put researchers in localised thinking positions and open new lines of thinking to gather on the importance of innovation performance in Micromax.

The present investigation on innovation performance in the context of Micromax utilise primary data collection technique for acquiring relevant data. For obtaining primary data, the investigator utilises both survey research strategy and interview research strategy. Furthermore, for effectively gathering the primary data, the researcher chooses main stakeholders of Micromax Informatics like customers and managers.

Besides, that primary data which is attained from the stakeholders help the investigator to study the main enablers of innovation performance in the organisation as well as the influence of the innovation criteria in the firm's business operations. As the managers are close to the organisational activities, they are more conscious and aware about the innovations that are adopted in the organisation. Similarly, the customers are the users of the products and thus they have higher experience on using the Micromax product. Therefore, the researcher expects 100% responsiveness from the managers and more than 90% responsiveness from the customers.

Therefore, the investigator conducts a survey among 100 customers of Micromax Informatics for obtaining the relevant quantitative data. Survey with the selected sample of customers is conducted through online survey platform survey monkey. The advantage of using survey monkey is that it helps in attaining the responses from the sample in a more focused and easy way. The developed questions are added to the platform and a URL created for accessing the link of the survey will be attained. This URL can be used for sending the survey link to the participants through emails and social media.

Moreover, for attaining the qualitative data, the investigator interviewed the ten managers who are working at the different section of Micromax Informatics. The researcher interviewed the ten managers such as operation manager, HR manager, marketing manager and relationship manager for collecting precise data in order to understand the accuracies of the innovation crisis confronted by Micromax Informatics.

Stankevich (2017) opined that the researcher has been highly benefitted on conducting the fieldwork as this helps the researcher to attain first-hand experience and knowledge regarding the topic they handled. Further, the researcher has also benefitted through conducting interviews and surveys to understand the role of social contexts in shaping

the daily life of people, along with exploring the complexities and confusions of daily life. Therefore, Dinglas et al. (2018) mentioned that the fieldwork procedures had facilitated the researcher to gather very detailed data and emphasise the role and relevance of social contexts. Moreover, it has also made available for the researcher to realise social facts that may not happen in the near future.

Further, the surveys being easy to administer and cost-effective can streamline the researcher to gain many accurate and valid data for the respondents directly even if the participants are located in remote areas. Further, Yue et al. (2019) noted that the standardised surveys are relatively free from errors. Further, through interviews, the researcher can collect the correct and accurate data related to the research by having face-to-face conversations directly with the authorities of the organisation. Through building a relationship between the interviewer and the interviewee, the information collected can be more trustworthy and sincerer. However, Buffel (2019) pinpointed that being less costly than any other methods involved in researches, the interviews can help the researcher to increase knowledge regarding the contexts under study and also carry out an in-depth analysis of the existing problems and their solutions. Yue et al. (2019) figured out that an additional advantage that can be experienced by the researcher through conducting interviews with the managers of the concerned company is that a flexible approach can be followed by framing questions and the order of them at the particular situation itself.

3.6 Identifying the stakeholder participants

In the research study the stakeholders are nothing but the organization or people involved in the study and realized that in the study they have important role. The people who are supportive for the research study is not only the stakeholders instead the people who are less supportive for the study but involved in research are also stakeholders as noted from Ismail (2018). For conducting the research study in more effective way the stakeholders involved in the study plays the significant role. Further, the stakeholder analysis also helps the researcher to gather insights about how the interest of each stakeholder supported by the research along with assessing the level of influence that can be made to them. Further, Ismail (2018) disclosed that it is also important to have a clear picture regarding the stakeholders to explore how they have to be communicated and managed throughout the research.

In order to identify the relevant stakeholders related to a research project, it can be

considered important to brainstorm all the stakeholders as the researches can have more stakeholder than expected and all sorts of people and organisation can emerge from this process as well. Yates and Leggett (2016) noted that the relevance of identifying and understanding the potential stakeholders involved in research lies in many reasons that ultimately form to be advantages for the researcher. By including the active involvement of the potential stakeholders, the researcher can benefit being put forth with more ideas than it would be if the study is done focussing on particular organisations of a small group of like-minded people.

Further, Hilton (2017) attributed that identifying and analysing the stakeholders also support to address varied perspectives from different sectors and communities, thus giving a more transparent picture of the concerned community. Further, Hilton (2017) opined that through identifying them most accurately, the researcher could facilitate by gaining their maximum support and contribution towards the accomplishment of the research. It can also expect that potential stakeholders identified with respect to a research context can support for attaining success in the research. At the same time, Naveed et al. (2017) illustrated that it could also be beneficial for the concerned organisation when they are into addressing and considering the concerns and thoughts of the communities around them as fair, ethical and transparent process of researches can also gain trust in them.

Thus, Stankevich (2017) noted that irrespective of the purpose of the researcher's efforts, it can be claimed that the identification of the appropriate stakeholder has to be one of the few important items involved in the research processes. Further, as in the case of the present study anticipating the participation of the stakeholders for the research study, it is important to include the potential stakeholders for the assessment and preplanning activities along with the planning and implementation actions for the research.

Further, to assure transparency for the research, it is necessary for the researchers to make sure that the stakeholders participate from the beginning as well. Moreover, Rodríguez-López and Souto (2020) commented that the consideration of the involvement of stakeholder could also be considered necessary from the beginning of the research process as any changes that may affect people in diverse ways are to be addressed and taken into account well before without affecting the research process in any forms.

Anyhow, the stakeholders with regard to research can be categorised as primary

secondary and key on the basis of the beneficiaries as a result of the research study. Boaz et al. (2018) disclosed that the primary stakeholders could be identified as ones that can gain direct benefits from the research while the secondary stakeholders involve those directly involved with the beneficiaries or targets of the research. Additionally, government officials and policymakers fall under the category of key stakeholders. However, the present study is observed to have involved all three categories of stakeholders for the research.

The study includes two supplier groups also for gathering additional primary insights on the influence of the partnerships and networking in enabling the innovation performance of Micromax. This additional stakeholder groups considered include a distribution-based supplier group and a R&D partnership. The key advantage of integrating these groups for this primary research is that the different innovation areas and influential factors could be revealed. Another important mediator of innovation performance is the development capabilities of the R&D department. Hence, in this context, it is necessary to assess the influential factors, synergies and co-creation of innovation of Micromax with the R&D partners. Another stakeholder group selected for conducting the interview is government officials from National Informatics (Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology-MeitY).

The significance of considering this group is that the interview with them generate primary information on the extent of the role of government support in leveraging the innovation performance of smartphone companies (Singhania and Jaitly, 2017). The knowledge on available schemes and policies, supportive of the innovation performance of the smartphone brands can be developed. Additionally, from the responses, it is able to know the challenges faced by smartphone brands in the Indian market. It is also possible to know whether Micromax Informatics has been utilising this support. Furthermore, the revelation of the areas of challenges can inform the future directions of Micromax Informatics.

The profile of the selected stakeholder groups is summarised in the below table:

<i>Stakeholders for interview</i>	<i>Designation</i>	<i>Department</i>	<i>Number</i>
1. Managers of Micromax	Manager	HR	1
	Manager	Operations	1
	Manager	Marketing	1
	Manager	Relationship	1
2. Suppliers	Manager	Distribution of company X	2
3. R&D partners	Assistant head	R&D of Company Y	1
	Manager	R&D	1
4. Sales manager	Manager	Sales	
5. Production manager	Manager	Production	1
<i>Stakeholders for survey</i>			
5. Customers			100

Thus, the interview sample constitute a size of 10 as shown in the above profiling. Due to Covid 19 scenario, the interviews with all of the selected groups carried out through emails. The email interview processed through three phases. Initially, the participants briefed on the purpose of the interview. A participation consent form is also be delivered through this initial email (Singhania and Jaitly, 2017). Open-ended and semi-structure interview questionnaire sent to the responded participants in the second phase. The third phase involve the examination of the responses of the participants received through emails. In this phase, it is checked whether additional probing is required for eliciting more responses. From the locations of Chennai, Gurgaon, Delhi, Bengaluru and Bhiwadi units in India was the managers for interview have been selected. The questions of interview have been mailed and asked them to respond for the questions as in current Covid-19 situation it was tedious to conduct the interview by direct means. On the other hand, for conducting survey the link of questionnaires that is formulated through survey monkey have been sent approximately to 160 customers but the response attained was only from 100 customers of Micromax informatics and thus the final samples selected for conducting survey was 100

customers.

3.7 Piloting

From the study of Singhania and Jaitly (2017), it has been noted that before conducting the main study the process of conducting the preliminary study is piloting. Ideally for the conduct of the pilot the research timetable should not allow but this pilot study has been conducted for assuring whether the proper analysis of data have been undergone or not and have to ensure that all the potential lessons of pilot work have been fully absorbed or not. In addition, it has also been noted that a pilot study can be referred to as the small study that test research protocols, data collection instruments, sample recruitment strategies and other research procedures and techniques to prepare for alarger and wider study. In the research study one of the important phase is marked as pilot study. The major advantage of using the pilot study is identifying the potential issues in the study, the insufficiencies in the research instruments and certain procedures that have to be considered before the initiation of the entire research study.

Moreover, Junyong In (2017) identified that the various steps to be carried out during the research can be well-identified and understood using the pilot study and also help them to understand the differences between the two competing methods such as the interview as well as the self-administered questionnaires. Thus, it could be understood from various researchers' findings that pilot study acts as an essential and vital part in understanding the protocols. These protocols are understood through small studies that help develop and carry out the large and main research study.

The pilot study is mainly carried out to analyse certain critical elements' feasibility in a research study. The three major regions focused on the utilisation of the pilot study include process, resources and management. The process includes the pilot study based on the recruitment rate, retention level, and eligibility criteria for conducting the participants' primary data (Enago academy, 2020). The resource allocation includes the time required to accomplish the study within the deadline, the utilisation of equipment that helps in faster and more flexible for carrying out the study, and the evaluation criteria chosen for the study to be feasible. The management uses the pilot study to understand whether there would be any issues in the collected data for future research or analysis and the variance in the collected data as time varies (Enago academy, 2020).

From the observation of Enago academy (2020), one of the major advantages of conducting a pilot study is that it gives prior information and evidence about the research study's condition depicting the areas where the study has failed. Additionally, the pilot study depicts the areas where the research protocols have not been followed. The proposed methods or procedures were inappropriate or challenging to conduct for the study. Pilot studies are conducted based on the type of data collection method used, either qualitative or quantitative. Large-scale studies might utilise several pilot studies before the main survey conducted.

Further, it could be understood that a pilot study helps the researcher to recruit the important subjects required for the study and also obtains consent for participation. The needed and required time and information must be given to the participants to make their decisions and provide written consent. With the pilot study, it is suitable to understand the accuracy and preciseness in the consent form, recruitment rates, time required to receive written consent, and the number of researchers and assistants required to complete the research. The insufficiency in the number of participants contributes to lower statistical power, limiting the study at the earliest (Friesen et al., 2017).

As per Atmowardoyo (2018), the word rehearsal can be linked with the pilot study, as a rehearsal or testing of research is conducted before the occurrence of actual research. For example, a researcher may have a plan to interview the managers of a company. However, a similar interview conducted before the actual one with friends or peers. This is useful to identify the errors and required changes. Before interviewing the chosen three stakeholders, the researcher approached friends and peers with similar interview questions. The test process had completed. The validity of the present research could understand after interviewing peers (Eldridge et al., 2016). The carrying out of a small study apart from the carrying out of a larger study points out to the need for conducting a rough or sample interview with friends and peers so that an overall idea of the ways of getting into and accomplishing the interview could be attained. Similarly, the process of primary data collection was well-identified through the sample done with friends and peers.

As per Eldridge et al. (2016) observation, pilot studies are critical and significant in a

good study design. However, from Eldridge et al. (2016), pilot studies do not mandate the main study's success. Nevertheless, it can increase the probability of success. The pilot studies are an important factor that meets a wide range of important functions and offers valuable insights into another researchers' study. The researchers have to carry out a more valid and needed discussion among the team so that both the process and outcomes of pilot studies can be analysed and evaluated.

A pilot study can be used in places of research methodology at the highest. The data collection process is considered the most significant and vital factor in the research. The data collection process determines the credibility and accuracy of the study. Thus, it is essential to carry out a prior study before starting the main study and understand the major concepts in a research methodology (Atmowardoyo, 2018). Thus, it could be understood that when primary data is used within the study, it is mostly recommended to conduct a pilot study so that the occurrence of errors can be eliminated. As observed by Atmowardoyo (2018), a pilot study can be used to analyse and estimate the cost and time required to efficiently and adequately accomplish the study. It could also be understood from various researches that a pilot study implemented into a larger project benefits the researcher in identifying and resolving the major potential issues or problems during the study. This helps eliminate these issues during the main study, which helps improve efficiency and, at the same time, reduces the time needed to conduct the main study.

The data or information is collected from the participants such as peers or other colleagues, where the views and opinions raised by them are considered into the pilot study. However, data collected from near groups such as friends can result in bias in the study, leading to inefficiency in getting the respondents' feedback. Moreover, the feedback gained from peers and friends may not be the same as the actual participants. Similarly, the questionnaire prepared for the peers and colleagues may not, at times be able to influence the actual sample participants positively. Thus, there is a need to prepare two sets of questions: the peers and the other for the actual participants. This can result in time consumption and effort to be doubled.

Thus, it could be inferred that pilot studies are, at times, an important and most vital factor while conducting the main project. Based on the type of study conducted like the interview or survey with a higher number of participants, a pilot study is vital in reducing the number of errors or defects in the study. Further, it could be understood from the findings that the pilot study helps align the resources with the needs of the

research study. The resources required for conducting the main study with efficiency can be well identified and analysed using the pilot study. However, it has to be noted that the pilot study is used for a project that requires a higher number of samples where it is necessary to understand and analyse the type of methodology used.

The pilot study helps the researcher in recruiting the important subjects required for the study and obtain consent for participation. The study participants are first interviewed with the help of the peers or other colleague's so that feedback from them is collected to improve the data collection required for the study. This can be considered a vital factor for improvement; however, it also poses bias in the study.

Several feedback and responses were gained from the pilot study. Many peers thought that the sample interview was effective and comfortable, which would help get the needed and required data related to the topic. The peers suggested being polite and humble when interviewing the intended stakeholders. Based on this feedback, some changes in the questions have made. However, the pilot testing was a time-consuming process in between the literature search. Moreover, an additional cost wanted to spend on pilot testing.

However, Edwards and Meagher (2020) contradict several disadvantages while using the pilot study into the research. Ismail et al. (2018) argued that pilot study results in lengthy delays in disseminating the research findings. Further, it could also be identified that the researcher may be accused of protecting established opinions. At the same time, several restrictions would be there to get into genuine and valid ideas. Moreover, from Ismail et al. (2018) findings, the most challenging factor that affects the pilot study is time-consuming. More time is wasted in getting responses from the peers regarding the study.

3.8 Observing and interviewing informants

According to the observations of Yu et al. (2021), it is pointed out that before carrying out the data collection process, it is important to verify the situation involved to make sure that time and money is not wasted on account of the research. The basic principles that the researchers have to abide by are to keep things as simple as possible, planning the entire process of data collection, ensuring that all data collected is valid, reliable and credible and that the ethical issues are taken into account as well. Lawal (2019) pinpointed that basic monitoring has to be carried out by the researcher; however, in some case, some complex methodologies may be involved in the process

as well. However, as suggested by experts and scholars, it is also beneficial for the researchers to keep every aspect related to the research as simpler as possible.

It is an equally imperative measure to plan the entire research process well before involving in the data collection methods. Mkandawire (2019) mentioned that a usual error happened from the part of the researcher is not exploring how the collected information analysed or used. There are chances that data that are not collected from the right people at the right time and from the right place may be difficult to be properly analysed. Hence it can be regarded as critical about being clear of what information is being accumulated through the research study rather than collecting details about all sorts of issues. At the same time, Yue et al. (2019) noted that the credibility, reliability and validity of the research have to be maintained in extensive levels. A research can be commented to be reliable if the same data collection process is repeated within the same periods using similar methods can bring about similar results. Apparently, it can also be noted that research conclusions can be set out to be valid if the objectives planned for the research was met by the same. Furthermore, Buffel (2019) noted that the research could be pointed out to be credible when the research results attained are believable and consistent with respects to the common sense of the common people.

A more important aspect to be taken into account by researchers is the addressing of the ethical principles associated with data collection. Some of the general principles that are to be considered by researchers to avoid harm to an external along with considering the benefits and costs to the different stakeholders involved. Moreover, Ismail et al. (2018) included that it has also to be ensured by the researchers that their participation towards the research methods is voluntary and not pressurised to take part. Confidentiality is also a vital element of consideration in terms of research as equal is the anonymity to be maintained to disseminate results shared by the respondents.

Thus, considering the present study that engaged in conducting both primary and secondary data collection methods required being involved in observing and informing its research participants with the best possible information related to the research. However, Dinglas et al. (2018) mentioned that the primary data collection methods included surveys and interviews with the customer and managers of Micromax Informatics, respectively. Hence the researcher had to assure that the research participants are provided with the fundamental information regarding the research.

The research participants were initially comprehended with the information sheets described regarding the purpose and aims of the research study. Derakhshan et al. (2019) noted that This could convince the queries of the participants about their participation as well. All those details, including the benefits and losses that they may happen to come across through participation, are discussed through the participation information sheets. However soon after they are done with having a look at the information sheets, they are provided with consent forms that enable the researchers to have a confirmation from the part of the participant that they are well informed of the research and its purpose before taking part. However, Yates and Leggett (2016) mentioned that their involvement in the research does not have any pressure or compulsions from the part of the researcher as it is completely up to them to agree or disapprove the request to participate in the research.

However, if the participants become willing to involve in the study, the consent forms can be returned duly signed. The responses gathered from the respondents have to be maintained with strong confidentiality and privacy so that the participants do not have a fear that it would harm them in any means or the other. However, the employees of the organisation may feel it difficult to disclose their identity through a public platform like a research report. So, the researcher has to take adequate measures to assure them that the responses and thoughts shared will only be disseminated as anonymous quotes or opinions (Stankevich, 2017).

Clear observation of the respondents is important to collect answers that is used to assess with the literature reviews (Stankevich, 2017). In the present research, the answers of the respondents were recorded in a digital device, as well as notes were made by the researcher for future purposes. The researcher asked the respondents to speak further if any answers are unclear. Confidentiality of information is highly important in the research, especially in the primary data applied research. Thus, the respondents were informed regarding the way personal and professional information is protected. These aspects are conveyed prior to the completion of the interview.

Concerning this, the data collection strictly adhered to the Data Protection act 2018 and the information assembled were considered for research purpose alone. Besides, the participants informed about the study by providing PIS (Participant information sheet), and the consent form was provided for attaining permission to take part in the interview (Kumar, 2019).

3.9 Interpreting, reducing and analysing data

In the methodology chapter in the section of data analysis how the accumulated data in the study has been analysed has been detailed. For any research study one of the significant part is data analysis. The accumulated data has been summarized in the section of data analysis. In the research study for determining the trends, patterns and relationships and for interpreting the data gathered the researcher have to use various analytical and logical patterns and the process is data analysis. From the reports of Mackieson et al. (2019), it has been inferred that the data interpretation and data analysis quickly being the most prominent with the advancement of digital communication that is accountable for a huge amount of data. It has been remarked from the studies of Nimmagadda et al. (2018), that the data interpretation denotes the execution of a process by the data which is studied to reach into a clear conclusion. Moreover, the data interpretation entails taking the advantage of data analysis from the results of examined results and these all are utilised to make a conclusion. Gaur and Kumar (2018) implied that data analysis is the process of ordering, classifying, controlling and briefing the obtained data for attaining results for the research questions

As well as the analysis of data were regarded as the primary step before carrying out data interpretation. However, it is clear that the data interpretation is a substantial section; thus, it has to be effectively carried out. Hence, the investigators have determined certain methods for interpreting data that is assistive for the process.

Several data analysis methods can be seen to interpret and analyse the primary or secondary data, and the interpretation and analysis are the important steps before reaching the research conclusions (Flick, 2015). The present research included primary data collection method for accumulating the data related to the study. The data accumulated from interview is qualitative data and the qualitative data accumulated has been analysed using thematic analysis method.

As part of this, few key themes were developed based on the information that has been attained through the interview responses. The possibility to assess the data by incorporating the experiences of the respondents and thereby reach in conclusions led the researcher to opt interview method and thematic analysis method. Likewise, putting a large quantity of secondary data is confusing during the analysis. To avoid this, a clear description with justification is important. By considering this, the descriptive analysis method was used in this study (Sidel et al., 2018).

The research study has collected qualitative and quantitative data by carrying out an interview and survey; these both strategies are identified as the best data collecting method. Moreover, the fundamental need for gathering the essential data for conducting the research, and it is for clearly interpreting the research questions. The research utilised survey strategy, and it has been carried out among 100 customers and interview among ten managers.

Moreover, the survey is with close-ended questions, and the customers is participated in the survey through an online platform survey monkey. As well as, Sivarajah et al. (2017) remarked that survey monkey possesses the capability to track participants; thus, they could contact participants for ignoring worrying of the participants who are involved in it. Moreover, the data attained from the survey has been analysed with the assistance of descriptive data analysis and the data acquired from the interview has analysed with thematic analysis.

The reduction or inclusion or exclusion criteria are used in this research when the secondary data is selected (Boaz et al., 2018). As part of this, the works published after 2010 and before 2020 September were only used. The article published in the reputed journals only searched. The secondary data utilised in the literature findings has been followed to gather relevant and efficient data related to the research issue. As well as it has been opined by Boehmke et al. (2020) that accurate data reduction and quality control measures which have implemented for the certain data gathering methods.

3.10 Appraising and the research design

The current study focuses on the valuation of innovation performance, and the case chosen for the study is Micromax. The case Micromax was taken in order to meet certain objectives. Mardani et al. (2018), suggests that innovation performance leads to the enhancement of the performance of an organisation. Micromax was considered to be an innovative company during its prime years. It was one of the few Indian smartphone companies and successfully catered to the Indian market. Providing innovations in the Indian smartphone market at a reasonable price was the main reason behind the growth of the company. But after an impressive run, Micromax had to shut down its operations in India despite having an innovative background. Thus taking the case of Micromax can help the researcher to analyse the different aspects associated with innovation performance.

Lovarelli and Bacenetti (2017), opine that the primary data collection method enables the study of a topic in a more authentic and reliable manner. Both interview and survey are conducted for the current research, and this allows the researcher to focus on the intricacies of the research variable. As the primary data was collected from the officials related to Micromax, the research have a better understanding of the problems that occurred in Micromax. The analysis of this data using the specified research design can generate more information useful for the study.

The researcher has appraised or judged the collected data to understand whether the data is sufficient to explore the research objectives. Before coming up with the interview and secondary data collection strategy, the researcher had a clear idea concerning the way the research objectives could be met. Anyway, the researcher established that the secondary data and interview results would be sufficient to meet the research objectives.

The present study has gathered the required data related to the research topic with the help of interview and survey as well as the interview has been carried out among ten managers and survey conducted among 100 customers through survey monkey. As well as the research topic is the critical examination of the innovation performance in the Indian Smartphone sector, and the research has been focused on Micromax Informatics. The selection of qualitative and quantitative data collection methods was greatly assistive for studying the present research topic. Moreover, as a result of the adoption of interview research strategy and survey research strategy, the research design utilised by the investigator is the descriptive research design.

The critical appraisal is a structured process that is used for determining the weakness and strength of a research study for assessing the validity and usefulness of the research findings. From the reports of Valle et al. (2017), it has been inferred that a substantial element in the critical appraisal is the examination of the effectiveness of the research design of the research question and an effective examination of the prime methodology aspects of the design. It has noted by Brice et al. (2020), that certain other factors which must be taken into consideration such as appropriateness of statistical methods utilised and its following interpretation and also the relevance of the research study.

However, the undefined difference within the critical appraisal and reporting standards could be portrayed by the account of certain tools. As well as, it could be reached into the conclusion that the research issue could be effectively studied with the help of both

the qualitative and quantitative data collection methods. Moreover, the basic understanding is required for the critical appraisal of both qualitative and quantitative research study.

3.11 Ethical issues

In all the phases of the study that is from designing to reporting researchers confront with ethical challenges. The ethical issues that are confronted in the study will be related to the factors such as confidentiality, anonymity, researcher's potential impact on participants and vice versa and informed consent. The strict ethical guidelines were adopted throughout the study. While accumulating the primary data the researcher has strictly followed the ethical guidelines. Before conducting the interview or survey the purpose of conducting the study and students' details has also been provided to the participants involved in the study. Moreover, before conducting the interview and survey participant information and consent form have been sent to participants and on attaining consent from participants only the research study has been conducted. Moreover, throughout the study high importance have been provided to the confidentiality of information accumulated from participants such as their personal opinion and details concerning the study issue. Further, Data Protection Act 2018 has been adopted for upholding information confidentiality throughout the research study.

In addition to this, the participants were convinced regarding no harm to them by the research and research findings (Kumar, 2019). In the current study while accumulating the secondary data the appropriate references for the information have been provided throughout the study. That is in at the end of the report list of references that are cited intext has been provided in the final reference list. Moreover, no manipulations or changes have made in the secondary data apart from paraphrasing.

The current study has utilised the primary data collection methods with the assistance of interviews and surveys. As primary data was involved, the consent form and participant information sheet has been filled and attained from the participants before beginning the interview. Moreover, the data has to be collected from the participants with accuracy and care. Therefore, the data has been kept under security in a data server to validate confidentiality. Further, the researcher has also ensured the participants that the data accumulated from the participants will only be used for academic purpose and after the use it will be destroyed and the participants confidentiality will also be maintained

throughout the study. The participants' information included in interviews and surveys will not be disclosed to anyone without the participants' permission or consent and it has been informed clearly to participants before involving them in the process of interview or survey. Finally, to reduce ethical issues in the future, the data collected through the research study by interview and survey will be used only for academic purpose and after the completion of the study it will be destroyed.

3.12 Limitations of the study

When the secondary data was used, some limitations were anticipated by the researcher, and these limitations were detailed through this section. Firstly, it was difficult to collect secondary data from some websites that seek payment. Thus, the researcher missed some of the relevant articles to the study topic. Similarly, more secondary data could have integrated into the study; however, time constraints did not allow to do so (Flick, 2015).

In between the completion of the interview, the researcher realised the additional cost needed to collect data by conducting interviews. The secondary data collection was possible by using a laptop and visiting libraries. However, the interviewing process consumed much time for the researcher. Further, formulating an interview questions related to the study topic was a time-consuming process, and that made a delay in the data collection process. As part of this, the researcher wanted to take permission and appointment from the interviewees before directly approaching them (Flick, 2015).

3.13 Summary

It can be summarised here that the present research has completed with the help of secondary as well as primary data collection methods. Interviewing three stakeholders was the primary data collection strategy. As usual, books and articles and other published materials were the secondary data. The thematic analysis method was used to analyse the interview results, and here, secondary data is also utilised. A pilot test was conducted to anticipate the feedback, errors and mistakes in the planned interview. The pilot test was an opportunity to rectify the errors. The researcher has given significance for ethical research, and thus, high priority had given for the confidentiality clause and principles in the data protection act.

The researcher is acknowledging here that there were justifiable limitations for the present study. Further, the next chapter of the research study is discussion chapter and here the accumulated information through primary data collection method that is through survey and interview will be presented and analysed in the upcoming chapter.

Chapter 4: Research Findings

4.1 Introduction

The current chapter is intended in explaining the issues that were discussed in the course of the data collection process conducted in regard to the research context. The following section give transcripts of the interview apart from the paternal observations or responses gathered from the surveys carried out concerning the research study. Furthermore the chapter includes the judgements of the findings thus made from the data collected in the research. The chapter also includes a section that discusses the findings on the whole from both the data collected from the prospective respondents.

4.2 Plan of analysis

The current research is done applying both qualitative and quantitative studies. The study is done with the aid of the primary data collection methods. Regardless of the data collection methods used in any research, it is critical to interpret the findings in the most appropriate way and reach up with the most valid and accurate conclusions and results. However, as the surveys and interviews are conducted in the present research, the case of the Micromax is assessed through observations and responses from the managers and customers. The data thus collected were analysed critically to understand the pros and cons of the operative specification and modifications and improvements measures that should be ascertained by the brand. However, discussing through findings of the study the present chapter also judges the findings made by comparing it with the literature.

4.3 Quantitative Analysis

1. Gender

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
Male	59.60% 59
Female	40.40% 40
TOTAL	99

Chart 1: Gender of participants

The research study has gathered the data by carrying out a survey of 100 customers, and this section discussed the gender proportion of the participants who have taken part in the survey. The given chart implies the gender of customers of Micromax Informatics who have taken part in the survey for obtaining the relevant quantitative data. It has been inferred from the chart that 59.60 % of male customers, along with

40.60 % of females have participated in the survey. Moreover, the female participants of the survey were less compared to male participants, which indicate the unwillingness of female participants in sharing their views and opinions. The survey was intended to perform among 100 customers, but 99 participants have answered this survey question one of the participants has been skipped.

The survey was conducted through the SurveyMonkey, which is an online survey development cloud-based software which was beneficial for the research in gathering the data in an easy manner. The survey questions were sent to the participants through mails, and they have marked their responses in it, and also understood males possess more knowledge regarding technological aspects. Almost 20 % difference is found in the number of participants who have been taken part in the survey; moreover, it is not a big difference but not also a small difference. For the successful completion of the survey, both the male and female participants involved in the process were equally supportive.

However, the male and female customer of Micromax Informatics is considered to be a great asset for their advancement.

2. Age

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Less than 25	59.60%	59
25-35	33.33%	33
30-35	6.06%	6
35-40	1.01%	1
Above 40	0.00%	0
TOTAL		99

Chart 2: Age of the participants

The research has assembled the data by carrying out a survey of 100 customers, and this section discoursed the age proportion of the participants who have taken part in the survey. The chart given above illustrates the age of customers who have participated in the survey as well as it has been inferred from the chart that 59.60 % of the participants are having age less than 25 years, 33% of are from the category of 25 to 30, 6.06 % is among 30 to 35 years and one of the participants is from the age among 35 to 40.

Moreover, no participants are with the age of 40 and above it, which implies that more customers of Micromax Informatics are young peoples. As well as, the survey was intended to carry out with 100 customers, but one has skipped this question then, 99 answers have been marked. The participants within the age group of 25 and below has shown more willingness in sharing their opinions and viewpoints, which were beneficial for the data collection process.

Moreover, the customer in a younger age are aware of the technological advancement and its influence on society; thus, their responses will have a high significance. Therefore, interpreted that majority of the customers of Micromax Informatics comprises

the age category of 25 and less than 25.

3. Do you own Micromax smartphone?

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Yes	69.70%	69
No	30.30%	30
TOTAL		99

Chart 3: Proportion of customers with Micromax smartphone

The study had accumulated the data by the implementation of a survey within 100 customers, and this section discussed the proportion of the participants who own the Micromax smartphone who have taken part in the survey. The chart implies that 69.70% of participants own a Micromax smartphone, and 30.30 % do not have a Micromax smartphone. This survey question has been skipped by one participant among 100; thus, 99 responses were attained for this question.

The survey results have indicated that many customers have purchased Micromax smartphone and they are using it. Moreover, Micromax possesses a wide range collection of smartphones under 10000 Rupees with modest performance, one-day battery life and usable cameras. As well as, it has been inferred that their product line will be suitable for the middle-class population, especially for the middle-aged peoples. The youngsters will purchase a smartphone by considering various features like battery life, storage, camera quality and many others. Thus, the young customer range of Micromax is less when compared to the middle-aged population, and Micromax was not involved in the activities of expanding into the 4G market at the right time.

Moreover, there will be a possibility of more female customer who is using Micromax smartphones. A person who is searching for a budget smartphone can select a Micromax smartphone but, Micromax is not grasping the basic market shifts in the Indian market.

Since the survey was performed with the aid of SurveyMonkey, an online survey was conducting application. It was useful for study to collect the data in a comfortable manner, as the participants were able to participate in the survey from anywhere at any time with their smartphone.

4. When buying a smartphone, which of the following factors do you consider?

Chart 4: Factors to be considered while purchasing a smartphone

The research study has gathered the data by carrying out a survey of 100 customers, and this section discussed the factors that considered by customers while purchasing a smartphone by the participants who have taken part in the survey. From the chart 4, it has been understood that eight factors are considered by the customers, which influences the buying behaviour of the customers. The factors portrayed above are the design performance network connectivity and call clarity, storage, camera quality, financing options, friends or family and many other factors.

Moreover, the chart implies that 76 % of customers who have participated in the survey have revealed that they consider performance a major factor that will be considered while purchasing a smartphone. The second factor identified from the chart is the camera quality which is 63 %, and currently, youngsters are more stick to the camera quality of the smartphone as the photography interest in them is enhanced. The third factor determined from the chart is the storage capacity of the smartphone, remarked as 56 %, which has high significance as it could have an impact on the performance of the phone.

As per the survey results, the fourth factor is identified as the network connectivity, and call clarity, which is 46 %, in present scenario network connectivity has high significance as the customers will be using various social medial applications. For the function of every social media application, internet connectivity is essential moreover, the basic need of buying a mobile phone is for calling thus call clarity also will be considered by the customers. According to the survey, the next factor taken into consideration by the customers are the design of the smartphone, which is 37 %, as well as every individual, may have different interests some will like small size with a sleek design, on the other hand, some people like to use phones with the big screen. The financing option is the next factors as per the survey findings it is 28 %, and all individuals do not have equal financial capability thus they will be seeking for various sources like loan, instalment, personal savings and others for funding. 17 % of the customer participated in the survey opined that they would consider the viewpoints and opinions of their friends and family while purchasing a smartphone.

5. From the following, which factor you consider as best in the Micromax smartphones?

Chart 5: Factors which is best in Micromax smartphones

The research study has gathered the data by carrying out a survey of 100 customers, and this section discussed the best factors that considered by customers while purchasing a Micromax smartphone by the participants who have taken part in the

survey. This survey question has been skipped by three participants among 100; thus, 97 responses were attained for this question. The best factor considered by the customers in the Micromax as per the survey results, with 51.55 % is the battery life. Customers are so extremely concerned regarding battery life that they roll down the brightness of the phone, put on battery saver mode, close battery-consuming battery saving applications. The second factor that taken into consideration by the customers is design and durability, and as per the survey results, 26 % of customers opined that factor as best.

The third aspect found from the graph is the camera features, which is 14.43 per cent, and young people are actually more adherent to the smartphone's image quality as the involvement in photography in them is increased. Storage is the final factor identified from the chart, which is 7.22 %, which has high importance as it could have a direct influence on the performance of the phone. Besides that, prior to buying the Micromax smartphones, the design, hardware and cameras are disappointing for the young customers and will make the customers think twice.

However, everyone expects a decent battery life smartphone, and this typically suggests more use and less time wasted charging it. Micromax feature phones are usually low-end phones that, as compared to smartphones, have limited functionality.

6. Do you find Micromax as an innovative company?

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
▼ Yes	74.00%	74
▼ No	26.00%	26
TOTAL		100

Chart 6: Innovation level of Micromax

By conducting a survey of 100 consumers, the study collected the data, and this section addressed the extent of innovation of Micromax Informatics marked by the respondents who took part in the survey. Between 100 consumers, the survey was supposed to be carried out, as well as 100 participants answered this question from the survey, none of the participants omitted this question. From the survey findings, it has been interpreted that 74 % of respondents opined that Micromax informatics is an innovative company, on the other hand, 26 % of the participants remarked that Micromax is not an innovative company as well as they are not supporting Micromax as an innovative company.

People began to know Micromax as a brand that offers to the consumers, and it was pointed to as one of those brands that emphasised mainstream innovation. Compared to the middle-aged demographic, young consumer range of Micromax is lower, and Micromax was not interested in moving into the 4G market at the right moment. When Reliance Jio started selling its services at a low rate, the industry switched to 4G, and this culminated in a major decline in market share of Micromax.

7. How satisfied are you with the products of Micromax?

Chart 7: satisfaction level of Micromax users

The above figure depicts the satisfaction of the customers in regard to the products offered by Micromax. It can be observed from the above graph that around 40% of the research participants have opined that they are very dissatisfied with the products and around 46% of them being somewhat satisfied with the products and services rendered by the company. However, in addition to this, a small group of people accounting to about 8% of them are dissatisfied with the products of the company whereas another 8% of them are completely dissatisfied with the services made by the company. Thus, it can be regarded that the company requires being involved with strategies and activities that would facilitate the company to uplift the small group of dissatisfied consumers with enhanced satisfaction regarding the products and services offered by the company. Furthermore, it is noted by Zhao et al. (2019) that customer satisfaction can be the most integral element of consideration to acquire long term relationships with the customers.

Through ongoing satisfaction, it becomes streamlining for the business enterprises to gather loyalty of the customers. Saini (2018) mentioned that once customers have gained enough trust and loyalty regarding the products and services offered by a business enterprise and assures the consumers that they would deliver the similar level of performance throughout its lifetime.

On the other hand, if any dissatisfaction arises with the commodities or any other services provided by the business enterprises to its customers, a significantly remarkable negative influence can be made on the reputation and image of the brand in the market. Thus, it is crucially vital for the company to have a close eye on the satisfaction levels of the customers to assure that the company does have longer survival and existence in the market (Zhao et al., 2019).

8. In your opinion, how efficient are the products of Micromax in meeting your expectation for your purchases each time?

Chart 8: Level of Micromax meeting the customer expectations

The above diagrammatic representations demonstrate the opinions of the customers concerning the product efficiency offered by Micromax. Accordingly, it can be revealed from the above graph that around 47% of the research participants are of the opinion that the company has engaged in offering its consumers with efficient products. However, around 19% of them have pinpointed that the company has strived to offer highly efficient products to its consumers. Anyhow, it is also revealed through the graph that around 30% of them has the opinion that the company has only involved in offering its customers with products of average efficient and a group of 4% of the participants have opined that the company has not at all rendered its consumers with products of enhanced efficacy. Thus, it becomes quite impulsively responsible for Micromax to engage itself in activities and strategies that would help them render its customers with higher efficacy products.

Regardless of the size or nature of business being delivered, it is a crucial aspect that is to be considered by business to assure that customers are offered efficient and high-quality products. In regard to this, regular evaluations and testing of the products can be performed to make sure that the products sold through the brand are of high quality and efficiency.

Moreover, it is also an important fact that the business companies also require ensuring

highly efficient products, especially in the electronics sector, to gain customer expectations and reputation meeting the standards and of affordable costs as well (Rasche et al., 2018). Product efficiency and quality is also directly related to customer loyalty and a strong brand reputation

9. Do you find the product features of Micromax similar to as its competitor products?

Chart 9: Similarity of features of Micromax with its competitors

The above figure depicts the thoughts of the research participants regarding the similarity of the product features of Micromax to its competitor's companies. As per the figure displayed above, it can be realised that while around 67% of the research participants have opted that the company services product features similar to its competitors about 33% of them opined that the company is not similar to that of its competitor products. However, this can be considered as a need for the company to implement strategies and activities within its R&D department to bring about uniqueness and peculiarities in its products.

The innovation and creativity among the staff and engineers of the company have to be encouraged in significant extents so that the company can implement changes and updations in its products that let consumers to gather a new and pleasant experience. Most of the electronic products available in the present days have numerous similar features (Silva et al., 2018). However, while the key players of industry outstand themselves in the market with the unique signature in their aspects, maybe the product design, quality or specifications, Micromax has not observed to have delivered any distinct features for its consumers.

Being able to deliver consumers with unique and distinct products can enhance the reputation and awareness of the brand in the market. Thus, it is always beneficial for organisations to involve in selling its products with a unique selling point. This will enable businesses to withstand the current competitive business market and handle the possible future comers in the market (Rasche et al., 2018).

10. According to you, what feature of Micromax makes the products of the company unique compared to *the competitors*?

Chart 10: Unique features of Micromax

The above chart demonstrates the opinions of the consumers of Micromax about the unique features of the products served by Micromax to its consumers. However, the above figure demonstrates that the company has uniquely offered its customers with products with affordable pricing. Around 54% of the participants have opted that the pricing strategies of Micromax have showcased to be a remarkable aspect of its products.

Further, the design of the products of the company was also observed to have showcased significant acceptance and acceptability among the consumers, accounting to about 27% of the customers. Moreover, around 13% of the participants have stated their opinion that the battery life of the products of Micromax is notable. However, only around 5% of them have stood with the camera quality of the devices of Micromax.

Although even if consumers purchase Smartphone with the aim of having connectivity with others, the wide and diverse features available on Smartphone have made consumers highly demanding and aware of how the Smartphone are to be chosen for their use. Consumers always expect their products to be equipped with the best possible features, most particularly the product design and camera specifications to have the best experience (Shabrin et al., 2017). Thus, it becomes critically important for Micromax to get involved in strategies and activities that would ultimately enhance the quality and efficiency of the product features.

11. What are the major shortfall you identified in Micromax smartphones?

Chart 11: Short falls of Micromax smartphones

The above figure indicates the participant perceptions about the major drawbacks of the products of Micromax. As per the observations gathered through the survey, it can be revealed that the majority of the participants forming around 41% of the participants have opined that the company is prevalent with weak technology up-gradation in its products. Furthermore, it was also opined through the research that among 20% of the participants that the devices of Micromax are present with certain kinds of storage issues. Additionally, it has also been observed that the products and devices of Micromax were prevalent with low battery backup and weak sound clarity as well as accounting to 9% and 10% respectively.

Rasche et al. (2018) noted that consumers are always preferred with devices and products that are efficient and well-performing in certain aspects.

The most notable among them is the long battery life and the speedy processing of the devices. However, other features that attract consumers to choose the most suitable devices for their use are the crystal-clear display and the camera quality offered. Apart from these options, the consumers are also concerned about aspects like storage capacity, fingerprint sensors, wireless charging and many other peculiar characteristics. However, Micromax has found to have discrepancies in upgrading its technologies and innovations.

12. Would you like to recommend Micromax products to your friends and family?

Chart 12: Recommendations to friends and families to buy Micromax

The above pictorial representation denotes the recommendations that the research participants would suggest their friends and families to use the products of Micromax. It was revealed from the above figure that while around 73% of the research participants have opted that they would recommend the products of Micromax to its families and friends.

Around 27% of them have opined that they would not suggest their families or friends to try using the products of the brand. Thus, it can be concluded that even if a majority group of customers would engage in recommending their experience of using Micromax products to their families and friends, a significant group of people have started to disagree this as well.

Thus, it becomes critical for Micromax to involve in activities and strategies that would also transform this small group of consumers to suggesting the products of the companies to others.

Shabrin et al. (2017) mentioned that the customers who approach a brand or store on account of the recommendations from their peers or relatives are found to be more engaged with the brand for longer terms. Previous studies have proved that while around 61% engagement rate was shown by customers who entered a company due to recommendation only about 47% of engagement displayed by consumers approached without recommendations. This can be accounted on the emotion of the consumers that a brand suggested by a friend can never be wrong as it would indicate that their friend is wrong as well. Thus, every business companies are to be involved in activities that would let them gather maximum word of mouth campaigns. It is because the result that word of mouth publicity can make cannot be done by any other advertising activities (Rasche et al., 2018).

13. What recommendations would you like to provide Micromax for improving their innovation performances?

Chart 13: Recommendations to Micromax for improvement

The above figure showcases the diagrammatic representations that figure out the recommendations provided by the research participants in regard to improve the innovation performance of Micromax and thus provide enhanced product efficiency and quality. While around 44% of the participants have opined that the company can enhance its innovation performance through implementing regular technology updates in its products, around 24% of them have stated that the company urgently requires looking into executing actions that would improve the speed and performance of the processors

used in their devices.

Along with this, around 21% of the research participants have regarded that the company require improving their design features. It is also pointed out through the research, with 11% of the research participants opting that the company requires making its products user-friendly. Thus, the company has to explicitly involve in strategies to advance and improve the innovation performance of the company. This is significantly required to deliver enhanced performance and efficiency than its competitor's rivals, along with facilitating the customers to experience unique and distinct products features from its devices. Further through offering customers with enhanced products and services, the company can gain satisfaction and loyalty of their customers which in turn enable to promote the brand awareness and reputation within global markets.

Therefore, it can be concluded that Micromax has to engage in showcasing enhanced innovation performance through adopting strategies and actions that would ultimately transform the product to be user friendly with high-speed processing, enhanced product design and improved camera quality and battery life as well.

4.4 Qualitative analysis

Question 1: How significant is innovations in the smartphone industry?

Manager 1: "Well, satisfying the employees by identifying their strength and weakness is important for maintaining the employees' productivity. Here I have noticed an interesting fact that if we manage the resource properly, it can provide guidance to the employees on how to work with the operational process. When I analysed the effectiveness of technology, it could contribute more to resource management, enhancing the quality of the outcome. So far, I had submitted a detailed report on how to manage the resource properly to increase our employee engagement in the organisation".

Manager 2: "I can say that innovation in the smartphone industry is also adequate for meeting customer demand. It may look strange at first glance, but I had seen it many times on how the innovation is satisfying the customers. When the technology is advanced, it could reduce the overall product development cycle and adequate for implementing new changes in the process. Since customer demand is changing continuously, we are responsible for implementing new changes wisely. So, innovation is a great method for satisfying various customers across the global market. Also, in my

perspective, if any company is not able to manage those changes, they cannot build a sustainable business. We have seen many examples like Nokia, which was not sustained in the business due to the lack of innovation. Hence, I am considering innovation as an effective tool for enhancing the innovation rate of an organisation”.

Manager 3: “As a marketing manager, I have many opportunities to analyse customers' demands in each market. The interesting fact here is the demand of customers is not staying constant. It is changing continuously based on their living conditions. So I have understood that consistent changes in the products are always necessary for the customers to satisfy in the business. Innovation is suitable for any company in the smartphone industry to bring regular changes in mobile phones. We all know that many large companies are widely invested in the innovation process to enhance the company's market performance”.

Manager 4: “As a senior manager in the company, I consider innovation a tool for effective resource management. The global market is facing issues with the unavailability of resources which are necessary for production purposes. When I am leading a project, I prioritise managing the resources properly and conveying it to my team employees. Sometimes, there is opposition from the employees, but guiding the team is much flexible when they are adjusted to it. Apart from the resource management, I can also say that innovation is suitable for increasing customer satisfaction. As a person working in the service sector, I believe customer satisfaction could contribute to a company's profitability”.

Manager 5: Enhancement of innovation is highly beneficial for us to satisfy our customers. Supplying raw materials is a major challenge in the business since it needs to satisfy the customers well. When the innovation rate has improved well, we can provide enough raw materials within less time. Moreover, I have noticed that with the help of innovation, we are able to provide high-quality resources to the customers, which are essential for business growth”.

Manager 6: “Maintain your customers with you is the advice which I am always giving to my team-mates during the training programs. So, it is the responsibility of the companies to manage the customers properly in the business. Due to existing competition, alternatives for the customers is high in the smartphone industry. When the rate of innovation is reduced, it will reduce the attention of customers. Technology is beneficial for smartphone companies to reduce the operation time in the supply chain. It is

beneficial for us to increase the accuracy in the final product delivery to retail customers”.

Manager 7: “Well, before coming into my answer, I would like to share my previous sales department experience. Size of smartphones is the major issue for the customers, and they need to reduce it for high flexibility. On the other hand, when the smartphone industry's innovation goes up, the size of the product has reduced considerably. Hence, I see the innovation in the smartphone sector as an opportunity to satisfy the customers by meeting their demands”.

Manager 8: “Well, in my opinion, innovation is the gateway of product creativity. If we want to manage competitive rivalry in the market effectively, the creativity of products is an important factor. Coming into internal factors, innovation in the smartphone industry could enhance resource management effectively. As we know that the circular economy has become very popular in the corporate world due to unavailability of resources. The exploitation and mismanagement of resources have increased the necessity of proper resource management”.

Manager 9: “While handling the customers in the business, I am always trying to enhance customers' satisfaction. I have noticed that when I communicate about the latest innovation about the project, they were excited to hear about that. Hence, for myself, innovation is the perfect way for meeting customer demand in the business. While analysing the overall business, resource management is another area in which innovation is more significant. Innovation is beneficial for our company to reduce the wastage of resources in the whole supply chain operations. Our company is also trying to invest more in the innovation process to increase sales performance”.

Manager 10: “Oh, it is quite tough for me to give a direct answer, but I can assure you that innovation is the fundamental need for every company in the smartphone industry to enhance the profitability. In my perspective apart from satisfying the client, innovation could enhance a company's sustainability in the global market. It means that innovation in the product could provide a better brand image for the company, and it is beneficial for managing competitive rivalry”.

Question 2: What in your opinion are the main factors that drive Micromax to launch innovations?

Manager 1: “In my opinion, different factors drive the company towards innovations. We adopt innovations based on the demand of the customers. The demand of the customers

changes every day as per the changing needs. Secondly, competition in the industry makes us choose innovations. Smartphone industry undergoes great competition. In order to make competitive advantage for company, we make innovations to produce high quality products in the market with new features. I found that due to these factors we are forceful to adopt innovations.”

Manager 2: “I find that there are different driving forces for bringing innovations in our company. In my opinion, the major factor that led our company towards innovation is the changing trends in the smartphone industry. From my experience I understand that the customers are attracted by the new trends that arise in the industry. Along with this, the level of competition is a driving force towards the adoption of innovations in our company. Being the operational manager, I have the opinion that many of our operations involved innovations because of increased efficiency and speed in the operations of our competitors.”

Manager 3: “When I think about the major drivers of innovation in our company, I feel that the level of customer attraction and sales growth are the factors that lead our company towards innovations. The adoption of many innovations are raised based on how effectively we are able to attract the customers. When the customers are less attracted by the existing marketing techniques and tools, we introduce innovative tools for effective marketing of our products. We also depend on innovations when the sales growth is low. The sale of products is controlled to a great extent by innovations.”

Manager 4: “As of my experience, the major driving forces of innovations are customer expectations, increased competition and changes in the lifestyle of people. I understand that the competition in the smartphone industry has been increasing to a great extent and it has created a need for the adoption of innovations. It is also true that the changing lifestyle of customers have brought the need for innovations. Increased accessibility of the internet and social media usage has created the need for bringing novelty in the products. The customer expectations have brought changes in the manufacturing, production, distribution and various services of our company as they demand the need of innovations in all the areas of our operations.

Manager 5: “From my experience as a supply manager, I find that the major reasons for many of our innovations are increasing demand for our products, technological advancements and increased competition in the smartphone industry. Increased demand of our products demands that changes need to be developed with regard to supply chain

activities for increasing the efficiency and speed to meet the increasing need for the products. Secondly, technological advancements have increased the demand for innovations because the customers are aware of various technologies available in the market and they choose products which go with the current technology. I also feel that the competition in the smartphone industry has forced towards the adoption of innovations.”

Manager 6: “In my experience, the major factors that affect the adoption of innovations in company are the changes occurring in the market with regard to the price and quality of the products, the existing trends in the market and the availability of advanced technologies. In the current era, the most advanced technologies are available in the market which helps use to go for innovations. The trends in the market changes according to the changing demands of the people. Therefore, these changes force us go for innovations in the production and distribution of products.”

Manager 7: “As f my knowledge, that major factors which bring innovations by our company are the changing life style of people, technological innovations and the variations in the demands for certain selected products. The products which are available in the market may not be having demands as the customers find that there is availability of new and, innovative products as per the preferences and taste of different customer segments. The life style changes in the current era makes people to choose new and latest products in the market by other companies. This makes us go for innovations as it is necessary to exist in the competitive market.”

Manager 8: “According to me, innovations are made in our company on the basis of increase in the customer needs, lack of efficiency and increasing demand for high quality products. Certain products have increasing demand due to the quality of those products. Increasing demand for the quality products made us go for innovations for the production and distribution of quality products. Lack of efficiency is also one of the driving forces in adopting innovations. Innovative methods help us to increase the speed and efficiency in company operations.”

Manager 9: “As of my knowledge and experience, I think the changing lifestyle has increased the need for innovations. The people of different cultural backgrounds and educational backgrounds choose products with advanced features. This makes us bring innovations in our products. Along with this, competition has been increased in the smartphone industry which is also considered as one of the major reasons for bringing

innovations in the operations of the company.”

Manager 10: “When I think of the adoption of different innovations in our company, the main driving factors of innovations were the increasing competition, changes in the preferences and the lifestyle along with the variations in the product demands. When the people go with the changing lifestyle, it makes them choose advanced products. This force us to go for innovations. The preferences of the customers are also a driving force towards innovations in our company. To meet the needs of the customers and to meet the quality of products we adopt innovations in various operations of our company

Question 3: According to you, what are the main factors that impact the innovation performances of Micromax?

Manager 1: “As a leading company in the industry, many factors contribute to the innovation performance of Micromax in the market. In my view, leadership is the most influencing factor that I have noticed to enhance the company's innovation performance. Many employees from different background are working here and keeping all the employees motivated can be done through proper leadership. I trying hard to develop leadership skills based on the change happening in the industry”.

Manager 2: “Leadership and time management are the most admiring factors for me to increase the company's innovation performance. Micromax is producing smartphones on a large quantity, and we must maintain a schedule properly to manage all the works in the organisation. On the other hand, leadership is very important for making effective time-management in the production process. Micromax is conducting special programming and training sessions to enhance both time- management and leadership skills among all the company employees”.

Manager 3: “While analysing the innovation performance from the perspective of marketing, I could say that leadership and cost are the most influencing factors in the innovation performance of Micromax. Here cost means the operational cost invested by the organisation to produce innovative products. When any smartphone companies in the market are launched any innovative products, I always used to analyse the product's investment cost and most of the cases; it will be more. I believe proper leadership is necessary for taking adequate decisions relating to the investment cost”.

Manager 4: “Customer handling is a process that I have enjoyed well in my career because it can provide customers' exact emotion in the market. Micromax believes that

proper leadership skill is the major reason behind the innovative performance of the organisation. Our management is working with great vision, and it is motivating the employees working in the company. However, leadership cannot work as stand-alone to increase the innovation performance of the company. Hence, In Micromax, we have developed a framework for proper time-management in the production process. It has influenced us very well for enhancing the innovation performance of the organisation”.

Manager 5: “R&D department is primarily responsible for enhancing the innovation performance of any organisation in the industry. Since I am working in the R&D department of Micromax, I have seen how innovation impacts the performance of Micromax in the global market. I think both cost management and leadership are influencing our innovation performance of Micromax in the global market. In leadership, we are not intended to follow hierarchical positions because we need to satisfy our employees well in business. Our management believes that motivating employees could enhance the innovation rate in the business. Cost-management is an important factor for us to enhance the innovation performance of our company because the lack of cost-management could enhance the liability in the company”.

Manager 6: “Since Micromax is our important customer in our business, we didn't compromise in the organisation's innovation performance. Our raw materials have influenced the innovation performance of Micromax well, and that has helped ourselves to become the regular raw supplier of Micromax. Moreover, as a supplier company, we are highly inspired by managers' leadership traits working in the organisation. They are highly committed to taking adequate risks in the business, and it is the major reason for the innovation performance of Micromax in the industry. Personally, I have adopted certain methods in their leadership and cost management to implement as it in our organisation”.

Manager 7: “From my personal experience, I could say that leadership is playing a significant role in the innovation performance of Micromax. Moreover, time-management is also identified as an important factor in enhancing the innovation performance of Micromax. Our management has developed a framework for time-management in production work. After following the framework in time- management, we have got consistent results in the production process. Our marketing team will analyse all the major innovation done by our competitors in the market related to smartphones. The analysis will bring us information about the necessary changes required for Micromax to

enhance the innovation performance of the company. We have done all these processes within a fixed time-framework, and it has helped us deliver the products within the time limit”.

Manager 8: “I am very concerned about the time-management because time-management is effective for satisfying our customers well. Moreover, our management is also striving hard to increase the potential of time- management to enhance our organisation's innovative performance. Besides, time- management resource management is also playing a significant role in our company's innovative performance in the market. The availability of resources is reducing heavily for us, and we have introduced a circular economy to manage our resource properly. Since it was implemented last year, we didn't receive the exact result for the new changes. However, we strongly believe that the changes we are implemented can enhance our performance heavily”.

Manager 9: “While interacting with the customers, I am getting information on their demand for the product we are delivering. When I conveyed it to the management, I got positive response all the time from the senior management. So, I think leadership is playing an important role in the innovation performance of Micromax. There could have many other factors which influence the innovation performance of Micromax, but effective leadership traits from the senior management are motivating us to innovative something on smartphones. We are also conducting adequate programs among the junior level employees to take the responsibility of various organisational activities in the company”.

Manager 10: “In my opinion, the production unit is the place where you can see the innovation of a company well. Hence, I could say that the leadership from our management is the primary influencing factor of innovation performance of Micromax. Apart from leadership, our resource management is also influencing well on the innovation performance of Micromax. We have implemented a framework for a circular economy in the production unit, which has reduced the amount of waste in the process. The profit we got from the circular economy is solely used for enhancing innovation performance of Micromax to handle competitive rivalry in the market”.

Question 4: In your opinion, how efficient are the innovation performances of Micromax?

Manager 1: “In my opinion, innovations have been the stepping stones to our company's success. Apart from feature phones the company has produced tablets and two in one

devices which has increased the brand reputation of the company. Through the introduction of Yu brand, our company could enter into health and fitness segment also. The latest launch of Note 1 with 6.67 inches touch screen display has attracted the customers and this further increased the number of customers to a great extent. Our company is efficient enough through various innovations as we are now the 10th largest phone maker in the world.”

Manager 2: “Our innovations in the Smartphone industry has helped us to become India’s largest phone firm by market share. As of my knowledge, we are able to produce 50 different mobile phones every year. However, the company has been facing lot of competition in the smartphone industry with the innovations made by Samsung and Apple Inc. We could improve our distribution channels and it helped us to focus on small cities to increase the sales. Therefore, we have become efficient in the industry due to innovations in different areas of operations.”

Manager 3: “In my opinion, Micromax is the first company in India to have maximum number of innovations. Long battery phone, dual sim phone, gaming device and many other features have been introduced in India by the company. These innovations have improved the market presence of the company. However, the company could not grow as per the expectation in China as the company had to face high level of competition in the country with Chinese brands. By increasing our focus on research and development we could gain the trust of the customers and meet their changing preferences and demands in India. But it is recognized that the company needs to grow further since other companies bring lot of innovations in various operational areas in the smartphone industry.”

Manager 4: “As of my knowledge, the innovations made by our company helped to become more efficient because the company had become the second smartphone player in India. But the Chinese companies have entered into Indian smartphone industry by 2016 which brought lot of decline in the sales growth as they more focused on innovations and selling their products at an affordable price in India. The company could focus its innovations on featured mobile phones. Therefore, the innovations by our company could lot of growth in the earlier times.”

Manager 5: “In my opinion, our innovations in the smartphone industry are valuable and they helped us to become one of the companies with large market share in India. The innovations by our company helped us to increase our market presence in India as we

have retail presence in 10000 outlets and 1000 service centers in India. However, the entry of Chinese mobile brands has affected the growth and market presence in India. Therefore, we are planning to make more innovations with the product quality and more number of features to compete with the Chinese brands to retain our position in the smartphone industry.”

Manager 6: “When I think of the innovations made by our company, I am proud to say that we have achieved a strong position in the smartphone industry. With the help of innovations, we could become the second smartphone maker in Indian smartphone industry by market share. Long battery phones, dual sim phones and gaming devices were the innovations we brought to the industry of smartphone in India in the initial stages. We could increase our market presence in India with the help of innovations. However, we could not compete with the Chinese brands with their pricing strategy as they sell their products with an affordable price.”

Manager 7: As of my experience in the company, Micromax could bring lot of innovations and they have helped us to become one of the leading smartphone manufacturers in India. The developments we brought in the area of innovations in India, we could increase our market presence in the country. We could attract the customers and gain customer loyalty in the initial stages of our innovations. The entry of other mobile manufacturers in the country has affected growth and the market share in the industry had a great decline. However, we are planning to our investment on research and development which will be helpful in coming back to our former position in the smartphone industry.”

Manager 8: “When I think of the innovations made by our company, I should say that Micromax is the company in India which has brought more number of innovations. Product features such as high battery backup, dual sim and game devices were brought to the Indian smartphone industry for the first time. However, we could not continue to make innovations due to the growth of Chinese brands in the country.”

Manager 9: “Being the third largest handset selling companies in India, I can say that Micromax has gained from its innovations. The innovations brought by our company helped us to become one of the leading mobile manufacturers in India and we could compete with other smartphone manufacturers in India. Our efforts to introduce smartphones with specific features were successful and we could gain the trust of the customers and increase our market share too.”

Manager 10: "In my opinion, innovations were our secret to become the second smartphone player in India by market share. Our investments in research and development were the highest in the Indian smartphone industry. Innovations such dual sim phones, long battery backup and other features helped us to increase our market presence. Now our company has its presence India with 10000 outlets and 1000 service centres in the country. On the other hand, the emergence of Chinese brands, the market share of Micromax was diminished and the sales growth was also decreased."

Question 5: Could you please mention the innovation crisis confronted by Micromax?

Manager 1: "I certainly feel that every departments had avital role in contributing to the welfare and development of an organisation. Yes, we had certain crisis previously especially due to the challenges in tech arena. We also tried to introduce many significant changes in our HR department but we confronted issues to assist most of the employees while trying for a change."

Manager 2: "In my perspective, Micromax was selling rebranded smartphones bought from China into Indian markets which caused a major issue that is After Sale Servicing. Obviously, smartphones bought from China lacked in quality and cheap parts were fitted inside the phones which often lead to repairing the phone. So, if you ask me, I think Micromax encountered challenges to establish Service centres as well as the servicing of the smartphones were not up to the buyer's expectation. Customers were often dissatisfied with Micromax Smartphone Service Centers and this was because of the cheap quality of the phones manufactured in China and Micromax couldn't stand up to the competitions put by other's

Manager 3: "I think competition played a big role in the crisis of Micromax. Micromax was already falling behind upgrading their smartphones as well as their services offered to the customer didn't turned out to be the best when compared to other cellphone manufacturers like Samsung, which has over three thousand service points all over India. Other companies also started to introduce cheap and value for money smartphones which was the major factor behind Micromax phones initial success. Micromax just couldn't keep up with the tough competition with their cheap Chinese imitations and that's the main reason I think lead to the company's collapse."

Manager 4: "I think domestic competition was higher and we failed to anticipate the quick changes which are occurring in the market. I have heard a lot on the entry of Chinese

market but I don't think that is the real case of Micromax but the competition especially many companies by 2015 had a better competitive advantage in the Indian market. I also think that the changes and trends towards the 4G technology was another significant reason for the loss of Micromax and lack of innovative leaders worsened the situation."

Manager 5: "According to me, Software updates had a major impact on the downfall of Micromax smartphones. No software updates were ever available to a Micromax smartphone. As android started introducing new features and updated their security patches, Micromax phones started to get outdated because of their software and security patches. Google which owns android that has 91 percentages of Indian smartphones working on it introduced their own smartphones which started receiving software updates and regular security patches faster than any other android device started getting attention in Indian market. I think, other companies also started giving customers faster updates while Micromax failed in this scenario too."

Manager 6: "I can say for sure that technological updates has a definite hand in the loss of Micromax Informatics Ltd. Micromax Informatics failed to produce quality phones and continued importing smartphones and simply rebranded to Micromax for selling in Indian markets. Technology has already grown so far and so fast that Micromax just couldn't keep the pace with their competitors who regularly updated their smartphones to the latest technology by manufacturing upgraded variants of the same phone without over pricing for the latest variant. Micromax after realising their mistake took steps to improve their technology and they did it as well, but it was too late for them as customers migrated to smartphones offering latest technology in a fair price."

Manager 7: "I am sure one of the reasons for Micromax Informatics's demise is the entry of new brands like MI, Oppo, Vivo, Oneplus to Indian markets. These were Chinese brands which had much more quality over Micromax's rebranded Chinese smartphone copies. I also think that these brands kept the phone's pricing similar or less than Micromax smartphones which had customers thinking whether to buy Micromax smartphones or these new brands which offered better quality than Micromax. I feel that most of the customers started opting for the new Chinese brands over Micromax, which decreased the sales and brand value of Micromax. We decreased the price of their smartphones which further amplified their stock values."

Manager 8: "We have been constantly supporting Micromax for many years. I feel that company was more concentrated towards many cost reduction strategy and pricing

scheme. While most of the companies were concentrated on innovations, Micromax mainly concentrated on pricing and operational cost reduction. I think, Micromax had even renewed their operational method to attain a good market recognition. I certainly feel that company could have utilised technologies to improve business performance."

Manager 9: "I have been working in this organisation for many years now, I certainly feel that we could have done better in the sales performance. As a sales manager, I think we could have invested some time on knowing the pulse of the customers. The sales decline of Micromax is mainly due to the lack of expertise on customers' interest. Besides, I also think that many marketers have come up with similar products which negatively impacted the stability of our company. I also think that many customers have switched their interest to Chinese smartphones which also impacted our firm."

Manager 10: "I think we had lost our focus on innovations and technologies. When other companies started investing in 4G technology, we consciously modified our 3G mobile editions. We also had stocked some of the new 3G mobile phone products for selling it to the customers. I think we had to plan necessary strategies to elevate the chance of business success in the market. And, many stocks were unsold after introducing 4G technology as our company lacked quality leaders. I think we have to produce something unique and distinctive products from our competitors to create a significant change in the business performance."

Question 6: What are the major upcoming trends and the planned innovations that can be expected from Micromax in the coming years?

Manager 1: "In my opinion, our company has been increasing our investments in research and development which opens room for innovations. Our company is planning to launch three mobile phones in India. The products include budget phones with premium features and modern outlook. The new phones will be available at Rs. 10000 which is an affordable price for all the customers. Therefore, it will be profitable for the company. We are also planning to develop smartphones with flexible frames which will have great demand in the industry."

Manager 2: "As of my knowledge, our future innovations in different operational areas will consist of using technologies such as Internet of things, Artificial intelligence. In addition, we will be producing smartphones with features such as better processors and mobile phones which support high quality visuals. These innovations will benefit the company with the capability to compete with Chinese brands in India. The future

innovations of our company will be focusing on improvement on photography, cyber security and battery life.”

Manager 3: “In my opinion, the current era has already entered into 5G network and therefore, our innovations will be focusing on producing 5G mobile phones in the market. Better processors will be used in our smartphones to enhance graphics performance. In addition, improved chips will be used in the smartphones with advanced cameras, audio systems and gesture recognitions. Such innovations in smartphones will help in gaining competitive advantage in the industry. Besides these our future innovations will be focused on improving camera efficiency and increased battery life for our smartphones.”

Manager 4: “As of my knowledge, the future trends in the smartphone industry are better batteries, wireless charging, unbreakable phones, stronger screens and flexible frames of smartphones. Micromax will be investing more on research and development to meet these needs of smartphone users. The company will be focusing on producing mobile phones with these features and it will be helpful for the company to come back to the former position in the smartphone industry by competing with the Chinese smartphone brands in India.”

Manager 5: “In my point of view, we need to focus more on innovations in the production of smartphones to gain competitive advantage in the industry. We will be launching smartphones such as Micromax IN 1 and Micromax IN 1a. This series of phones will be useful and more advanced with improvements in high quality cameras and increased storage and better processor. Premium features and modern outlook of these phones will attract the customers and improve customer loyalty as well. Further, we are planning to improve and expand our distribution networks in India. The launch of these three mobile phones will help to compete with Chinese smartphone brands in India. We will be utilising technologies such as Internet of things and Artificial Intelligence which will be beneficial to meet the changing demands and preferences of the customers in the current era.”

Manager 6: “In my opinion, I consider that the integration of artificial intelligence has penetrated the mobile world, which resulted in many advanced features. Many smartphones are integrated with Google Assistant, Siri, Cortana and Alexa into its phones. All these can be integrated into smartphones so that they can improve their innovation capability. Hence, I would state that the integration of AI helps Micromax to develop their technologies. Similarly, I opine that many smartphone companies install Augmented Reality to develop brand awareness, app downloads, engagement and

revenue. Micromax can thus implement either of these two or a combination so that innovation can be upgraded into their products. Hence, these trends can be estimated for Micromax to develop their products. “

Manager 7: “As far as I am concerned, I opine that internet of things play a vital role in deciding the trends and the planned innovations in the smartphone industry thus are in the case of Micromax. The storage will be more likely focused on a cloud platform, which paves the way for the company to improve its innovation and performance. Similarly, I opine that artificial intelligence has been a very widely used technology that helps develop a more space for innovation to exist. I also opine that automation can be another feature or trend that would boost the company's sustainability. “

Manager 8: “I opine that chatbot assisted mobile technology apps is the technology that can be integrated for improving innovation in Micromax. The chatbot assisted mobile technology can be integrated with AI that can be useful in targeting potential customers and figuring out the customer requirements with updates. Further, the smartphones that support digital payment apps are more recognised and needed for the current socio-cultural people. The innovation to implement chatbot assisted mobile technology with AI helps Micromax to sustain in eth market. These trends are thus expected from Micromax.”

Manager 9: “According to me, I believe that artificial intelligence can be considered one of the major trends and upcoming innovation that can be planned in Micromax. Micromax can be entirely changed with sustainability in the market by developing various technologies into their products. This can be done with ease using artificial intelligence. Moreover, the company can also employ the internet of things into their application. I consider that the internet of things plays a vital role in helping smartphones emerge as one of the biggest giants among competitors. “

Manager 10: “In connection with the major upcoming trends and the planned innovations expected from Micromax, I would point out that the internet of things is a valuable technological support that the company can use. The internet of things helps exchange the data from one to the other through various sensors, software and other technologies. The major aspect of using the IoT into Micromax is to connect and exchange data with other devices and systems over the internet. Thus, it would be more advantageous for Micromax if they integrate IoT into their products. Moreover, IoT can be integrated with other technologies such as AI or augmented reality.”

Question 7: How in your opinion can smartphone companies improve their innovation performance?

Manager 1: “In my opinion, I would recommend that Micromax could recommend that building a culture of innovation involves leaders and other higher officials where they help in providing a clear mission that the employees understand. Through inspiration, the individuals of Micromax will be motivated, and they would opine about the various ideas and approaches that have to be considered while designing and innovating the company. The employees are interested in working in an environment that supports and inspires them without letting them down. This results in developing more creative innovation in Micromax that helps the company for improving the innovation performances.”

Manager 2: “As per the viewpoint of mine, I consider that connecting with the different people at different company locations helps the company improve its innovation performances. This is because; the creative process associated with design and innovation helps the organisation concentrating upon, connect with people, and expect the demands and requirements of the customers. Through the process of connectivity with people helps get various opinions from the people regarding an issue or situation that helps sort out the issues at the best possible time. “

Manager 3: “From the observation of mine, I would point out that the company's leadership style determines the company's innovation performances. Thus, in my opinion, I prefer that the democratic leadership style would be suitable for Micromax. This is because; the democratic leadership style helps the organisation integrate the views and opinions of the various employees, which results in the development of creative innovation within the company regarding certain aspects. I also opine that the leaders can actively boost the employees to create innovation that leverages and uplifts the organisations brand image and credibility. “

Manager 4: “I opine that communication skills act as a major factor in improving the company's innovation performance. With effective and good communication skills helps the organisation not only to exchange the information. However, it also helps in conveying the right information at the right time. Thus, the communication efficiency determines the efficiency and productivity level of the company. All dealings and interactions related to innovation performance are well- carried out using communication efficacy. During the innovation development, the managers and the employees engage and communicate effectively so that visions and mission of the company are rightly

reached to the stakeholders of the company. “

Manager 5: “From my perspective, I believe that resource maintaining is an essential factor in improving innovation performance within the company. The resource capability of Micromax determines the company to adopt the level of innovation performances. The resources can be everything that supports the productivity and efficiency of the organisation. For innovation to support the organisation, it is must that organisation have the needed and required resources. Thus, the major factor that contributes to the innovation performance improvement would be according to my opinion, is the resource maintaining.”

Manager 6: “From the perspective of mine, I recommend that communication skills are vital and important to improve the company's innovation performances. Communication acts as a major channel to exchange and interact feasibly and flexibly depending upon the company's innovation criteria. The communication between the employees and the employees and the managers determines the level of engagement each individual has, thus actively implementing the innovation performance of Micromax. Moreover, the leaders can effectively share the organisation's mission and vision through p[roper communication. Thus, innovation goals and demands can be effectively communicated to improve the innovation performance. “

Manager 7: “From my perspective, I would opine that resource maintaining act as a major factor that supports improving the company's innovation performances. When the company develops innovative, it is essential that there are relevant and needed resources to implement the developed innovation into practice within the company actively. Several resources, such as technical support, employees, time, financial capability, and other management criteria, play a vital role in improving the organisation's innovation performance. Micromax has to thus focus upon the maintaining of the resources with the right and accurate measures.”

Manager 8: “According to my point of view, I recommend that the appropriate leadership style adopted within the organisation improves the organisation's innovation performance. Thus, I would suggest that democratic leadership would suit them best and apt leadership style in improving the innovation performance within Micromax. The democratic leadership style helps take all the view and opinions and the ideas of the various employees and managers. This helps get a diverse number of views and ideas about a subject that results in innovation development. Thus, the innovation improved

using the leadership style, as the leaders under democratic style support the stakeholders to contribute their ideas to innovate the operations of the organisation effectively. “

Manager 9: “In my opinion, I would recommend that leadership style determines the improvement in the innovation performance. I would suggest that the democratic leadership style would help the organisation's exchange opinions and views freely. This is because the democratic leadership style helps the employees and other higher officials to be directly involved in the decision-making process and freely decide about the subject. The democratic leadership focuses on developing diverse ideas from diverse employees, contributing to developing the innovation that suits the organisation's vision and mission. Thus, according to me, I suggest that a proper leadership style within the company helps the company to improve its innovation performance. “

Manager 10: “From the observation of mine, I would opine that organisational cultures play a vital and essential role in improving the company's innovation performances. Micromax has to follow a culture that develops the same and common culture for every employee to follow. The right message and mission are transferred to other employees and officials within the company. The organisational culture must be such that it motivates and supports the employees' views so that many new creative ideas can be developed and used for improving the company's innovation performance.”

4.5 Judgement of findings

On the basis of the research findings the current section is engaged in judging and analyzing the findings made from the data collected through different data collection methods. Deep insights can be gathered through proper and critical analysis of collected data. In the same way, the consideration of one of the major players of the telecommunication sectors like Micromax will help the analysis to make enhance its organisational performance, Through analysing the data collected through the research in regard to the objectives considered for the study, it is possible for the researcher to provide appropriate recommendations as well Moreover, judgment and analysis is an opportunity for analysing the accuracy of the data gathered from different data collection tools.

As the first objective is solely about analyzing the contributors to the innovation performance of the Smartphone section, the company details are not explicitly required,

rater it is essentially important to gather a general perspective regarding the innovation performance and the related strategies associated with the Smartphone industry. However, this can be identified to be a vast area to be analysed, it requires immense research into understanding the same.

Nevertheless, the second judgment of analysis is on the basis of gaining insights on the intricacies related to the innovation performance of the brand. However, this is of key interest for the present research as the recommendations to improve the innovation performance of the Smartphone brand. Even though the company has been able to create its own position in the market, the company is known to face serious issues of innovation and model specifications.

For making judgments in this portion, the researcher has analysed information from the survey, interview, and literature review. Since the survey and literature review is based on the response from the individual, the literature review could provide information from the previous studies. It is beneficial for the researcher to compare the factual data identified from the survey and interview.

Alongside, the third objective primarily discussed the fathom of the innovation crisis that occurred in the Micromax. From the data collected about the company, it is clear that Micromax is facing certain innovation issues which have reduced the sales performance of the organisation. Since the project focuses on the innovation performance of Micromax, discussing more the innovation crisis is highly adequate. It can deliver suitable guidance on providing a recommendation for Micromax.

Since the analysis judgment combines information from the three major aspects, the researcher has provided the most adequate recommendation for Micromax. The opinion from the customers is more important for the company to identify how to increase the innovation performance of Micromax in the industry. Since customers are the biggest asset of a company, analysing the views from those customers is very crucial for increasing organisational performance. While combining the interview information, it is possible to gather the staff's viewpoint of working inside the company. From the customers, the researcher can gather the lack of services from the company, but from the management, the reason for improper services can be evaluated effectively.

Objective 1: To gain insights into the contributors to innovation performance in the Indian Smartphone sector

For the current study data was collected through both interview and survey strategies. Two primary methods were chosen for the study in order to gain a more detailed understanding of the research objectives and conduct an in-depth analysis of the research topic. Additional to the data collected through the primary data collection methods, necessary data was also collected from the literature related to the various variables of the study.

The intention of collecting data from the literature was to identify relevant theories and models for the research. In this section, the data collected from all the sources will be cross-examined and compared to lead to the final output and conclusions of the study.

Various factors were identified throughout the thematic analysis and survey analysis. The main contributors to innovation performance in the Indian smartphone sector were found to be customers, market competition, technological advancements, and current trends. Each of these factors needs to be analysed on the basis of the data from the three sources of data. That is the data from the interview, survey, and literature, resulting in a triangulation of data. The triangulation analysis compares the factors with the three different sources and thus confirming the validity of these factors.

Customers were one of the factors that can have an impact on the innovation performance in the Indian smartphone sector. The excerpts from the interview point towards high importance given to the customers by the managers of Micromax. The demand of the customers is the main driving factor behind innovations in the smartphone market. The current generations of customers are very familiar with the latest technologies and are attracted to using new technology.

Attracting customers is the first step in increasing the sales performance of a company. The peculiar thing with innovations is that they provide an experience of using something new to the customers. Even if the innovation is gimmicky people use these innovations due to the tendency of experiencing something new.

The lifestyle of the customers is also changing rapidly. Technology in home appliances, music systems, and other daily usage equipment is progressing at a rapid pace, and if the smartphone industry does not keep up with the rest, then they will have to face drawbacks in the performance.

An increase in access to the internet has also made customers demand more innovations in smartphones. The customers want smartphone brands to utilise the maximum potential of the technology that is available now. Incorporating the possibilities of AI, VR and AR into smartphones can provide an enhanced experience for the customers.

The survey analysis was conducted on the basis of the answers collected from the customers of Micromax. Certain questions were specifically designed to find the importance of innovation among the customers. The customers were asked to identify the factors that they consider while purchasing a smartphone. The majority of the customers chose performance and camera quality as the main determinants of making a smartphone purchase. Performance and camera are two aspects of a smartphone that undergoes regular technological updates. Innovations are constantly happening in the smartphone camera and processors.

Thus, the result of this question indirectly points to the importance of innovation for smartphone customers. This analysis can be further consolidated from the result of another question. When customers were asked to identify the major shortcomings in Micromax, the majority response was the weak technology up-gradation provided by the company. This indicates that the lack of technological upgrades was one of the reasons for the downfall of Micromax, and the smartphone customers give high significance to innovations. The importance of innovation is also stressed in the recommendations given by the customers to Micromax to improve its product lineup.

Analysing the data from the literature, there are several pieces of evidence that lead to the relation between customers and innovation. According to Arpacı et al. (2015), the smartphone industry undergoes innovative upgrades in order to satisfy the needs of the customers. The main objective of innovation is gaining customer satisfaction. Cecere et al.(2015), add that catering to the changing needs of the customers through innovation enables smartphone companies to create better sales and profits. In short, the inference from the literature review also points to the impact of customers on innovation.

The triangulation of data indicates a similar pattern for the customer variable as a contributor to innovation performance in the Indian smartphone sector. The trend is visible across all three types of data. Managers of Micromax repeatedly stress the importance of customers as contributors to innovation performance. Every decision made by the organisation was leading to the satisfaction of customers.

Also, most of the managers opine that the strategies that they adopted were for customer satisfaction and innovation was among them. The data from the survey gave a quantifiable base to the influence of customer needs on innovation. Additionally, with support from the literature review, it can be inferred that customers are the main contributors to innovation performance in the Indian smartphone industry.

Another variable that may have an effect on innovation performance is the competition in the market. Market competition is a significant variable in the measurement of the performance of an organisation. In the opinion of the Managers of Micromax, market competition is seen as an extension of customer satisfaction. The competition in the market is to attract more customers, and customer satisfaction is necessary for attracting new customers. The managers unanimously agree that the competition in the smartphone market is very high, and technology can be utilised to gain a competitive advantage in the current market. Smartphone customers are attracted to the number of features and specifications of smartphones. They also consider the price of the product.

According to the data from the interview, innovations can be used to produce smartphones rich in features at a much lower cost. There are many brands in the Indian smartphone industry that sells high spec smartphones at an affordable rate. This exerts pressure on other smartphone brands to come up with devices similar to the competition in the market. Thus, market competition contributes to innovation as per the data from the interview.

In the survey analysis, it can be seen that competition in the Indian smartphone market significantly affected Micromax. Approximately 70% of the customers opined that the products of Micromax matched up to the customers. Another survey question asked the customers about the features of Micromax that made it unique when compared to the competition. The majority of the customers suggested that the pricing of Micromax was the main feature of the brand that made it unique. Micromax focused on gaining a competitive advantage through pricing and did not focus on innovations. Even though the pricing strategy did help the company to survive the market competition to an extent, but the lack of innovation pushed it backward in the market. This indirectly indicates the relation between market competition and innovation.

In the literature, the impact of market competition on innovation is specified. Arpaci et al. (2015), specifies that innovations of smartphones determine the competitive advantage and survival of the companies in the smartphone industry. Cecere et al. (2015) state that

the effective use of innovations can enable companies to gain a competitive advantage and generate better sales.

Similar to the case of customers, market competition is also seen to have an effect on innovation in the smartphone industry. The data from all three sources confirm this with data from authentic sources. Moreover, the validation from the literature further consolidates the relation between market competition and innovation. As competitors start to introduce innovative products in the market, people get more attracted to these products. As the number of competitors is high, the number of innovative smartphones also soars high. This motivates smartphone companies to innovate their products and gain a competitive advantage in the market.

Focusing on the interview responses, it could be analysed that one of the major reasons analysed as a factor to innovation performance is the increasing demand for our products, technological advancements, and increased competition in the smartphone industry. However, while analysing the interview responses, it could be understood that the major factor that can contribute to innovation performance in the Indian smartphone sector is a lifestyle. Moreover, one of the managers, like the R&D manager, pointed out that the smartphone industry's current trends have played a vital role in contributing to innovation performance.

Moreover, the operations manager's responses depicted that the major factor that led the company to attain innovation is the changing trends in the smartphone industry. It could be understood that the customers are heavily attracted by the new trends in the smartphone industry. The smartphone industry's competition has been mainly due to the changing trends in the industry towards the taste and preference of the products. Similarly, the R&D manager stated that the increasing demand for Micromax products, technological advancements, and increased competition led the company to adopt innovation.

The interview responses obtained from the Assistant Head R&D of company Y elucidate that various trends occur in the market about the technologies and varying customer needs. To fulfill those needs, it is essential that the customers have to be given the products and its specification by following the current trends in the market. This leads to innovation performance within the company in India. The current trends are such; it is difficult to follow; however, it is challenging to understand what innovation has to be integrated by Micromax to attain innovation without the current trends follow-up.

Likewise, emphasising the thematic analysis, it is depicted that the R&D manager through interview focused on the significance of technological advancements in Micromax innovations. The manager opined that the customers' changing lifestyle demanded them to purchase products with high quality and advanced technologies to maintain social status. The manager responded that Micromax could utilise India's technological advancements to produce products with increased quality and innovation.

Similarly, the Assistant Head R&D of company Y responded that the technological advancements are adopted mainly based on the demands in price and quality of the products, the existing trends in the market, and the availability of advanced technologies. Moreover, it is identified that Micromax has been utilising artificial intelligence and the internet of things for their innovations. The interview response also portrayed that since technologies lead human beings to purchase products, it has created the need for smartphone companies to bring innovations in their products.

Focusing on the literature review, it could be identified that in the context of businesses and industries, the manufacturers use technological advancements and innovations to enhance the product quality and gain a competitive advantage in the market. From the reports of Cecere et al. (2015), the companies that will be effectively utilising the innovation for gaining competitive advantage are more likely to gain better sales and profit by fulfilling the customers' demands and needs.

However, on the other hand, Clarke et al. (2018) contradicted stating that the real innovations in organisations are highly challenging and are thus, impacted by several factors such as cultural beliefs and business environment. The various factors that contribute to an organisation's innovation performance include corporate culture, leadership, employee commitments, and organisational environment.

The secondary data collected for the literature review mentioned that in the smartphone industry, the major factors that motivate the operations of the companies to integrate with the innovation are changing customer buying behavior and cut-throat competition. The customers' trends are such that they prefer and desire to experience updates in technology trends from time to time. Therefore, the trends are the most notable factors in the case of the smartphone industry while implementing innovation into its products (Arpaci et al., 2015). As a part of the changing trends in the customers' purchasing behavior, Arpaci et al. (2015) stated that innovations are a significant factor that determines the survivability and competitive advantage of Smartphone manufacturers in

the industry.

According to Cecere et al. (2015) reports focusing on existing and upcoming trends, Micromax focused more on launching innovations that do not compromise on quality and affordability. The company's current trends include that the latest launch of smartphones from Micromax mainly focussed on fulfilling the connectivity, camera quality, battery backup, and storage expectations. Cecere et al. (2015) studies identified that Micromax is already leading in the smartphone market with groundbreaking innovations in its manufacturing service and hardware segments.

Similarly, the survey responses depict that battery life is one of the major factors considered the best in Micromax smartphones. Through the survey, it was responded by the customers that they focus on battery life while selecting the smartphones, depicting that innovation plays a role there. Besides, the performance, camera quality, and storage are other factors focused on by the customers in purchasing a smartphone. The next factor that the customers consider while purchasing a Micromax smartphone is design and durability, which can also be an innovation factor for the company.

Among the 100 customers surveyed, it could be understood that more than 70 percent of the customers responded that Micromax is an innovative company. However, it could also be identified through the survey that the major drawback identified in Micromax smartphones is the weak technologies used by the company in its products. This leads to less attraction from the customers, leading to a decrease in sales and profit.

The interview and the literature review responses depicted that the changes in the preferences and lifestyle and the variations in the product demands have contributed largely to the Micromax smartphones' innovation. Certain products have increasing demand due to the quality of those products. Increasing demand for quality products made us go for innovations to produce and distribute quality products. However, the survey pointed out that technology is the most influencing factor while purchasing smartphones, such as performances, camera quality, and storage.

Thus, from the comparison made from the literature review, the interview, and survey responses, the major factors that can be understood are the technological advancements and the current trends based on the customers' lifestyle approaching smartphone companies. The smartphone sectors mainly adopt innovations due to the varying customer trends and attitudes towards the brands' selection and preference. From these findings, it could be understood that the customer, competition, technology

advancements, and current trends equally impact the smartphone sector's innovation.

This implies that the customers and their preferences and taste determine Micromax's current trends in attaining innovation. Similarly, the customers are attracted to the smartphone, when it is integrated with various technologies so that the ease of using those smartphones is increased. Moreover, to attain maximum competitive advantage in the competitive business environment, it is attained by integrating various technologies that help in following the current trends of the market and meeting the customer demands and needs.

The survey results depicted that battery life with design and durability is the major factor considered in the Micromax smartphone while purchasing. Besides, the performance, camera quality, and storage are other factors focused on by the customers in purchasing a smartphone. The same results have been found out in the interview and the literature review.

Objective 2: To analyse the intricacies of innovation performance in the context of Micromax Informatics

The objective of analysing the intricacies of innovation performance of Micromax is essential for the current research to get adequate research outcomes. Since Micromax is a technology company, innovation performance is crucial for the organisation to sustain itself in the market. Hence, data from the literature review, interview, and analysis are significant for forming valid research outcomes.

The innovation performance of Micromax is influenced by various factors, and some of the factors are very complicated to implement in the organisational performance as it is. Before coming into the judgment of intricacies of innovation, analysing the competitive rivalry existing in the market is important. Based on the competition existing in the market, the intricacies of innovation performance can be judged properly. Since the smartphone industry is changing continuously, the competition existing between the smartphone companies is very high. Hence, complications of innovation performance of smartphone companies would also be very high.

Analysing the customer response about the performance of Micromax is beneficial for developing a significant opinion about the innovation performance of the organisation. From the customer's response, 74% were replied to Micromax as an innovative company, whereas 26% of customers are not satisfied with the innovation performance

of the company. So, from the customer's response, it can be concluded that Microsoft is an innovative company and delivers suitable smartphones in the target market. However, there will be some complications or barriers that will always exist for the company against the innovation performance.

From the opinion of the HR manager, technical complications in the organisation are creating major complications in the innovation performance of Micromax. In the smartphone industry, the technical ability of an organisation is more important for the company to enhance its profitability in the business.

Hence, mitigating the complications in the technical performance of the company is essential for Micromax to survive in the business for the long term. As per the observation of Economic Times (2017), even though the marketing cost is high, the innovation performance of a company can enhance the profitability of the company. In the case of Micromax, the company is doing marketing at a high expense, and it has enhanced the awareness about the company and its products in the market.

However, when the rate of innovation is less, effective marketing cannot enhance the innovation performance of the organisation. The crisis faced by the company is directly reflected in the satisfaction level of Micromax. Even though most of the customers were responded Micromax is an innovative company, the customers are somewhat satisfied with the products delivered by Micromax. 46% of the customers are somewhat satisfied with the products of Micromax, and 40% of customers are highly satisfied with the products of Micromax. Even though there are not many differences in the percentage of the customers, analysing the issues in barriers could bring more insight into the performance of the company.

From the words of Cecere et al. (2015) in the literature review, the innovative model in the business could enhance the innovation performance of an organisation. The innovation model includes the activities from procurement to final product selling to increase the organisation's efficiency. From the analysis of the operational manager, the mobile parts received from China are not adequate for meeting the standard product quality of Micromax. Since the smartphone technology is advanced well, the quality of the parts should be higher in order to satisfy the customers in the market.

Competition is also playing a crucial role in the intricacies of innovation performance of Micromax in the global market. At first glance, competition and intricacies of innovation performance cannot be combined. While analysing the competition and changes required

in the organisation, then the role of competition in the intricacies of innovation performance of Micromax can be identified well. The technology in the smartphone industry is well advanced, and it is changing continuously based on the technological advancement happening across the globe.

The level of competition can be understood from the rating provided by the customers on the expectation of Micromax. 47% of the customers were opined that the service from Micromax is somewhat satisfied and only 19% were reported high satisfaction. As mentioned above, even though Micromax is an innovative company in the global market, the company is lagging in satisfaction and expectation in services to the customers. Cecere et al. (2015) opined in a literature review about how the innovation attracts the customers towards the services offered by a company.

The research said that incremental changes happening in the smartphone products enhance both attraction and expectation of customers about the company. Hence, before resolving the intricacies of the innovation performance of Micromax, the company needs to identify the reason behind the increase in innovation performance. Enhancing customer satisfaction should be the prior consideration for the management to increase the innovation performance of an organisation. It can be clearly understood from the opinion of an operational manager during the interview. The manager says that enhancing innovation performance for satisfying the customers could increase the profitability of the business.

Among the customers, 30% of them said that the company is offering average services to the customers. While comparing with the total population, 30% of the population is cannot ignored as it is. The relationship manager has provided an adequate answer about that issue. The manager says that competition existing in the domestic market is high, and it has created issues in the innovation performance of Micromax.

While analysing the existing market condition in India, the country has become an open market for the largest companies across the globe. Moreover, customers in India are getting alternatives to products, expecting quality for the customers will be high. Hence, even though the innovation rate of Micromax is very high, the company needs to enhance the potential of innovation performance of the organisation. Here, the scope of innovation performance of Micromax has enlarged, and the organisation needs to manage several aspects to reduce the intricacies of the innovation performance of the company.

The marketing performance of the company needs to enhance wellness to manage the intricacies of innovation performance. Even though the innovation performance of Micromax is high, the lack of marketing has reduced the appreciation of customers on the innovation performance of the company. While comparing the market performance of Micromax, the company is not creating much add in the domestic market like other smartphone companies. Asher (2020) pinpointed that smartphone companies' marketing strategies are highly important as implementing innovation in product development. Innovation in product development can contribute to increasing the quality of products, whereas marketing can contribute to enhancing the product awareness of the customer. Since the lack of support from the shareholders and stakeholders is a major issue for many smartphone companies, Micromax is highly affected.

As per the observation of Mura et al. (2015), if the support from the shareholders and stakeholders is reduced for the management, the company could not make effective innovation performance in the market. Since the managers from Micromax didn't complain about that, the organisation has all kinds of potential to remove the intricacies of innovation performance of the company. Regarding the technical advancement, developing a proper framework could remove the intricacies of innovation performance of Micromax up to some extent.

When analysing the results of the interview and literature regarding the complexities in the innovation performance of Micromax Informatics, it is found that there are different barriers and challenges the company faces when aiming at innovations. Data from the survey revealed that the majority of the respondents opined that the unique features of the products of Micromax are found to be price. This is an indication that the company has different barriers to innovations. The company which has been focusing on innovations will have unique features for the products. Very few respondents had opined that the product design and camera features and battery life are the unique features of the company. It is found that the process of innovation is complex for Micromax.

The company is not able to meet the changing needs and demands of the customers. When compared to the competitors in the smartphone industry, Micromax is not efficient enough to bring innovations in the products. Unique features of a product are the result of the innovations brought by a company. In the case of Micromax, the company needs to focus on various features expected and demanded by the customers in the smartphone

industry. However, the company could focus on battery life features and dual sim mobile, which brought many changes in the smartphone industry.

One of the major factors that affect the company towards innovation is market competition. Due to the high level of competition in the smartphone industry, the organisation is not able to enter into innovations. Since the companies in the smartphone industry are able to access advanced technologies, they become competitive with each other. The entry of new companies into the smartphone industry is also making the process of innovation complex for Micromax.

From the response of the customers, it is identified that the handsets of Micromax have a lot of issues. Weak technology is one of the major issues which was opined by the majority of the respondents. It is also found that low battery backup and weak sound clarity are also issues found in the smartphones of Micromax. All these issues found with the products of Micromax are evidence of the complexity that the company has towards innovations. The company needs to adopt measures to solve such issues to make competitive advantage in the industry.

When analysing the interview responses, it is found that there are intricacies in the case of Micromax towards innovations. The majority of the managers believed that innovation was the major focus of Micromax as they started their operations in the Indian smartphone industry. The smartphones with various features such as battery life and the dual sim were first introduced in the Indian market.

The entry of smartphones with such features created a platform for the company to operate in India. The effectiveness of these innovations was helpful for the company to attract customers, but the entry of Chinese brands in India was made the industry more competitive. Many of the interviewees pointed out this information. The use of advanced technologies helped Chinese brands to grow fast in the country. This became a threat for the company to exist in the market. The products manufactured and distributed by Chinese brands were at affordable prices. Innovative products at an affordable price by Chinese brought intricacies for Micromax to enter into innovations.

The opinion of many of the managers in the interview was that Micromax had a good beginning in their operations in India with a large number of innovations. But the problem was that the company could not maintain its performance due to the lack of innovations.

This reveals that Micromax is not efficient enough to make innovations like other companies in the industry. The process of innovation became complex for the company at present. The changing demands and trends in the smartphone industry also have a significant role in making the process of innovation more complex for Micromax.

Effective utilization of the technologies could have helped the company to gain a competitive advantage for the company. The market share of Micromax was too high in the smartphone industry. But later, it decreased to a great extent due to various reasons. Furthermore, the innovations of Micromax were completely focused only on featured products. On the other hand, other companies focused on different areas of operations when they entered into innovations.

In the opinion of managers of Micromax, the performance of the company is moderate. It is necessary to focus on research and development to increase the number of innovations. A high level of competition has affected the company to innovate. The expectations of the customers could not be met by the company. From the analysis of the findings of the interview, it is found that the information received from the survey and the interview is similar.

When evaluating the data from the literature in comparison with the survey and interview response, it is understood that there is a high level of complexity for the company to enter into innovations. Different barriers were found in the literature that a company has when trying to adopt innovations. The use of various technical issues constitutes one of the major barriers to innovation.

The technical errors and issues that happen with the technologies used for innovations can affect innovation. As per the observation of Friesen et al.(2017), efficiency in the technology used for innovations has a major contribution towards innovations by a company. It is found that the lack of support from the stakeholders and shareholders are the main barriers to innovation for every company. The use of various technologies and changes in a product's features need the consent of the shareholders. Furthermore, the consent of the customers and other stakeholders is also an important aspect that plays a significant role in determining the scope for innovations for a company

It is also noted from the literature that lack of effective leadership is one of the major barriers to innovation (Laport-López et al., 2020). The leader has a specific role to play in the adoption of innovations. The leaders and the top management of a company have the right to decision-making, especially in the case of going for innovations as they are

time-consuming and need a lot of investments. Leaders need to analyse various aspects associated with the innovations and their impacts on the organisation as well as the stakeholders. The effectiveness of such innovation is discussed with the employees and all the other members of the organisation. The acceptability and suitability of the innovations are evaluated and made a final decision by the organisational leader. The role of the leader in bringing innovation is significant in an organisation. It is found from the literature that the inability to change with the business's market and economic needs is another barrier towards innovations (El Kadiri et al., 2016). When analyzing the intricacies in Micromax in association with the innovations are found to be competitive in the industry. The company could not compete with other companies in the industry, especially Chinese brands.

Lack of leadership and lack of consent from the stakeholders is also one of the most important barriers which are involved in the adoption of innovations. The lack of efficient marketing was also one of the major barriers to innovation. From the managers' opinion in the interview, it is found that the marketing operations were weak and the customers were not able to know about the operations of the company and the product awareness was also less. The marketing operations should be efficient enough to support growth and efficiency. Based on the data from the literature and the survey it is found that Micromax needs to improve the marketing operations for attaining a competitive advantage in the industry and also for making innovations on the products and various operational areas. The human resources and other related assets of the company should be utilised for attaining a competitive advantage. The opinion of the managers in the interview and the opinion of the survey respondents also were found to be similar. Thus, it is understood that the data received from the literature, survey, and interview are similar in many aspects.

Objective 3: To fathom the particularities of the innovation crisis confronted by Micromax Informatics.

The analysis of the current research was also involved in the discussion about the depth of innovation crisis of Micromax. The information about the depth of innovation crisis was found from the data in the literature, survey, and interview. The findings of data from these sources showed that Micromax had faced a lot of challenges while entering into innovations. The innovations made by the company, in the beginning, did not last for many years. In the initial stages of operations in India, the company had made

innovations on battery life and dual sim mobile. Micromax was the first company to introduce dual sim phones in the Indian smartphone industry.

The company had the third position in the industry in terms of market share. The company could not maintain this growth and innovation for longer with the entry of Chinese brands in India. In the opinion of managers in the interview, it is found that the entry of Chinese brands created a lot of competition in the Indian smartphone industry and it affected the growth of the company in many ways. The Chinese brands were able to produce quality products at an affordable price which helped them to attract customers in the Indian smartphone industry. The use of different methods by the organisation in different operations also had significant impacts on the innovations and for gaining competitive advantage. The innovation crisis is deep in the organisation due to internal and external factors.

Therefore, high competition in the smartphone industry is one of the major factors which increased the depth of the innovation crisis. However, the organisation had faced some other issues also, which may also have an impact on the innovations of Micromax.

Based on the results from the survey, it is found that the product features of Micromax are similar to other brands which is evidence that the company does not focus on innovations after an extent. It is true that the customers in the smartphone industry choose products with high quality and a variety of features. Micromax could not produce products with different features and high quality.

When considering the uniqueness of the product feature of Micromax, it is found from the response of the survey respondents that the customer price of the product is the unique feature of the products by Micromax. On the other hand, today, the customers in the smartphone industry are not at all concerned about the price of the product instead, they are highly bothered about the product quality and the features of the handset along with the modern outlook. This shows that one of the major reasons for the innovation crisis is the priority that is given by the company. The company could have depended on innovations instead of focusing on price reduction. The current trend of the market could not be identified, and the innovations were not made by considering the changing demands and preferences of the customers.

The survey helped to identify the main issues associated with the handsets of Micromax.

The majority of the respondents in the survey had the opinion that the major issue associated with the handset is weak technology. Technology weakness of the handset of Micromax reveals that the innovations made by the company are not effective enough to meet the changing demands of the people, and they are not according to the market trends. The second issue found by the respondents with the products of Micromax was low battery backup and weak sound clarity. These issues with mobile phones have a significant impact on the quality of the product. The company has to bring innovations to make improvements in these areas. The use of improved technology is required, which involved the process of innovation.

The issues associated with the products of Micromax are severe, and they need to be attended to by the company with the utmost care. When analyzing the survey respondents' recommendations, it is understood that regular technology up gradation, improvement in the design, and improvement in the speed and performance were given as the recommendations. This is an indication that the company does not focus on technology up gradation, which is part of innovations. Technology up-gradation is important for innovations. From the opinion of these respondents, it is made clear that the lack of technology updates, inefficiency in the performance, and improper design are the factors that affect increased the gravity of innovation crisis in Micromax.

The managers in the interview mentioned the efficiency in the innovation performance of Micromax. The efficiency of the company was high in the earlier stages of operations, whereas it was decreased due to the entry of Chinese brands in India. The majority of the managers had opined that the company's innovations consisted of dual sim and battery life. But focusing only on such factors will not help to gain a competitive advantage in the industry. The company plans to introduce three new mobile phones in the industry in the coming days. Ineffective use of the available technologies was one of the major reasons for the innovation crisis. The innovations made by other companies insisted on Micromax to focus on innovations. The innovations on the featured products were not enough to gain a competitive advantage and to satisfy the increasing demand of the customers. Similar information was found in the literature, as it was noted that market competition is high in the smartphone industry. A high level of competition has affected the growth and innovations of the company to a great extent, and it was difficult for the company to compete with other companies in the industry. The entry of new companies and the efficiency and growth of the existing companies also had a severe impact on the stability

of the company in the industry.

In the opinion of Friesen et al.(2017), leadership ability is one of the major areas where the company was weak. Ineffective leadership brings issues in the adoption of innovations in organisations. Innovation and creativity are supported by efficient leaders, whereas the leaders who are highly concerned about their authority and power do not support innovations. Furthermore, the leaders and the management of an organisation have specific duties to ensure that the creativity and the innovative ideas of the employees and the technologies are effectively utilised for the purpose of innovations. As per the opinion of Teece and Linden, (2017), the use of technologies and human resources are major aspects involved in the innovation process.

Therefore, the capability of the leader determines whether innovations are made in the company. In the case of Micromax, the availability of technology and human resource was enough for the innovations. The leadership in the company is ineffective to manage the resources available for the company.

While analysing the literature, interview, and survey findings, it is found that the high level of competition in the smartphone industry has a great impact on the innovation crisis of Micromax. The company was affected by the entry of Chinese mobile brands in India. The initial innovations of Micromax were effective, but they could not be continued for a long time due to the lack of support from the stakeholders and the leader's inability. The data received from the survey findings and the literature were similar.

Factors affecting innovation performance in the Indian smartphone industry, the intricacies of innovation performance in the context of Micromax Informatics and the particularities of the innovation crisis confronted by Micromax Informatics were the major topics discussed in the current research. The analysis of findings from the literature, survey, and interview was focused on these topics.

The data collected from the primary and secondary sources were found similar. Issues such as market competition, technology issues, and lack of efficient marketing were found to be the intricacies related to the innovation in Micromax. Micromax was one of the leading companies in the Indian smartphone industry with the second largest market share, but the company could not maintain its growth and innovations in the industry due to the impact of increased competition in the smartphone industry. When considering the case of Micromax in terms of its innovation crisis, the market competition was a major factor that played a significant role. Now the company is trying to launch three new series

of smartphones which will be innovative with different features and modern outlook in order to attract the customers in the smartphone industry.

The lack of proper leadership was also found as an element that affected the innovation of the company. The key driving forces leading Micromax to innovation were found to be market competition, changing customer purchasing behavior of the customer, existing trends in the market, and technological advancements and their availability in the market. Comparing the findings from the literature, survey and interview show that the data from different sources are similar.

4.6 Discussion of findings

The present research is intended to evaluate the innovation performance of Micromax Informatics, although contextualising the concepts within the entire Indian Smartphone industry as well. The conceptual framework of the present research draws insights on the major factors that can create influences on the same. It can be assessed from the conceptual framework of the current study that the innovation performance of the company is highly influential on its organisational structure. In the same way, it can be analysed from the theoretical framework of the study that factors like product innovation strategies, innovation drivers, and sources of innovation can alter the innovation performance of the company. From the analysis of the literature review, it can be identified that innovation is the process of transforming the creation of a new idea into a practical reality. However, it is also identified from the literature review analysis that the innovations strategies are formulated and implemented to improve the performance of the market needs serving an integral role to bring success to the organisations irrespective of the nature or size of the business.

Analysing through the survey results, it can be assessed that the demographic peculiar features of the participants of the survey recognised to be major of male and age group between 25-30. These indications can give a detailed analysis of the demographic features of the participants who wish to share their views of Smartphone and their experiences. Thus, it can be also evaluated that the innovation performances and creative integration of electronics devices can be of greater interest for the male users who fall between the ages of 25 to 30 years. It can be evaluated from the findings of the survey that the major factor that is taken into account by the people in regard to their purchase or opinion of a Smartphone is the overall performance that it showcases. Further, it is also examined that the survey findings point out the relevance of efficient

battery life as the most important feature of the Smartphone that has made them buy and use the same. Although in regard to the participant's observations regarding the innovation performance of the company, it can be investigated that the company has exhibited optimal performance in its innovative capabilities.

Anyhow, it is also stated that the majority of the users of the phone include those of the Middle Ages people who are not very much aware or updated about the technological advancements happening around. Thus, it can be noted that the Smartphone is existing within low average levels of innovation performance not being able to satisfy its younger customers. In the same way, the investigation on to the satisfaction levels of the products of the brand seems with insights that they are optimally and satisfactorily meeting the expectations of its users. Furthermore, it can be assessed that the similar features that are observed in the Smartphone and its competitors deprive its competitor value in the market. It is assessed from the quantitative analysis of the study that the price range made available only makes the brand outstanding from its competitors and weak technology utilization can deteriorate its performance as well.

In the same way, the qualitative analysis of the viewpoints of the different managerial positions of the company also gave insights into the way the innovation performance is carried out within the company. It can be derived from the analysis of the qualitative data collection methods that innovation is critical within any organisational environment through which only the employee productively can be enhanced. However, it can also be noted from the interview findings that the change in the customer demands and competition within the industry has enabled the company to drive and launch innovative programs within the company. It is also noted from the findings of the interview that the changing lifestyle and demands of the customers have also facilitated the company to launch more innovative and creative development in their products. On the other hand, it is revealed that leadership and time management has significantly affected innovation performance within any organisational environment. In the same way, it is also analysed that the motivation and encouragement offered to the employees have enabled them to be involved in innovative procedures within Micromax. At the same time, the interview findings point out the relevance of time management skills in the employees to adopt innovative development [procedures in their manufacturing and production processes. However, analyzing through the innovation performance of Micromax, it can be noted that the company has been involved in the latest specifications and product features

available in the Smartphone industry, though there is still room for improvement for the company as well. Thus, the findings of both the qualitative and quantitative analysis of the research can be linked to the theoretical frameworks of the company that points out that the elements like organisational culture, innovation strategies, and rivers of innovation have influenced the innovation performance of the company.

4.7 Summary

The present chapter elucidated on discussing the findings of the qualitative and quantitative data collection methods applied for the present research. Analysing and evaluating the observations of the survey, the chapter pointed out the observations and discussed them critically along with representing the results in graphs. In the same way, the interview responses, presented as transcripts also described the perspective of innovation and creativity within the concerned company. However, evaluating through these findings, a discussion is presented through the chapter along with judging the findings with respect to the literature review.

Chapter 5 Discussion

5.1 Introduction

The current chapter of research findings details the findings that are attained through the data collection process. The data needed for the study has been accumulated using survey and interview strategy. The survey has been conducted among 100 customers of the organization Micromax Informatics and interview has been undertaken among 10 managers of the firm Micromax Informatics at different locations of India. Most of the customers have fully participated in the survey that is around 99 % of customers answered all questions and a very less number of customers omit some questions. The outcome of the research is mainly included in this chapter of research findings.

The survey among the customers was conducted through survey software called survey monkey. The quantitative and qualitative results attained through the data collection process has been detailed in this chapter. The outcome attained through the survey has also been detailed in this chapter but the results with detailed graphical representation has been elucidated in the next chapter. The relevant questions used for the research purpose and that questions and answers will include in this chapter one by one. This chapter will disclose the replies of the managers of the Indian smartphone sector for different questions asked in a detailed way.

The thematic analysis, it is the most common feature of the qualitative research (Clarke et al., 2015) it will discuss in the chapter that discusses the different themes based on the innovation, factors that impact of innovation, changing buying preference of the customers etc. The managers' different view towards the concept innovation in the smartphone industry will be explained based on the themes that are formulated through the interview results.

5.2 Plan of analysis

In the current section of plan of analysis how the data needed for the study has been accumulated and how the accumulated data that are going to be analysed are detailed over this section. For conducting the current study on the topic evaluation of innovative performance of smartphone industry on focusing the case of the organisation Micromax Informatics in India the researcher had used primary data collection method. That is the primary data needed for study has been accumulated using interview and survey strategy. The interview have been conducted among 10 Managers of the organisation

Micromax Informatics in India in different locations such as Chennai, Bengaluru, Gurgaon and Bhiwadi and Delhi and the managers selected were from the various divisions such as HR, Marketing, Operations, sales, Relationship, distribution, R&D and production. On conducting the interview, the qualitative data needed for the study has been accumulated and collected qualitative data has been analysed using thematic analysis. Similarly, the quantitative data needed for the study has been gathered using survey analysis. The survey has been conducted among 100 customers of the firm Micromax Informatics through the Survey Monkey software that is through online mode. The attained survey results has been analysed using descriptive analysis method that is representing the attained data through tables, graphs, charts and images.

5.3 Survey findings

In the current section of survey findings, the results accumulated on conducting the survey have been detailed and explained. The survey have been conducted among 100 customers of Micromax Informatics and by that quantitative data needed for the study has been accumulated. Survey with the selected sample of customers is conducted through online survey platform survey monkey. The developed questions are added to the platform and a URL created for accessing the link of the survey will be attained. This URL can be used for sending the survey link to the participants through emails and social media and survey responses have been attained. On using survey monkey, it helps in attaining the responses from the e sample in a more focused and easy way. From the attained results it has been observed that on comparing with the female customers most of the participated customers in the survey was male. Moreover, the majority of customers participated in survey attained almost all questions. The customers of Micromax between the age group a18 to 25 years was highly participated on comparing with other age groups. The expertise and knowledge of customers who are belonging to the age group less than 25 years are higher, and this inference indicates that the major customer base includes the age group less than 25 years. In addition to this, the current survey mainly considered the customers of Micromax and subsequently, around 69% of the respondents chosen for the current survey either have a Micromax smartphone or had from the same company before.

The current study is based on the innovation performance of Micromax and thus, choosing the customers who have a better knowledge of the innovation performance of the Micromax smartphones will be beneficial for the current research. Through the

current survey, the researcher tries to investigate the major factors that influence the purchase of smartphone companies. While analysing the results, the performance of smartphones is the major factor which is considered by every buyer in the market. The inferences clearly show that smartphone marketers should provide high performing mobile phones as the customers tend to compare the best performing smartphones in the market.

The customers will only prefer buying phones which have higher performance in the market. The performance option was selected by 76% of customers of Micromax for the current survey. Simultaneously, camera quality, storage and design hold the succeeding positions in the case of customer's buying preferences. The marketers who are providing products in the smartphone sector should consider this quality, such as higher performance, camera, storage and design for attracting more customer base in the Indian market. However, the recommendations from peers and family and financing options are considered only meagre compared with other options provided in the current survey.

Through the current survey, the major factor considered while making a purchase of Micromax was also portrayed in the current study. The study mainly examined the prime features of the Micromax phone, which acts as the main driver of customer purchase. In the current study, most of the customers pinpointed on battery life and design and durability as the major influential factors that contribute to the purchase intention of Micromax. Besides, during the purchase, most of the customers are likely to choose the products which are having higher battery life and innovative designs. Therefore, the survey results focus on the need for developing products with high-end quality, high durability and battery life. Additionally, in the current survey, more than 50% of customers have pointed on the significance of battery life, and 26% of customers have selected design and durability as the main factors that improve the performance of Micromax in the Indian market.

The researcher also tries to analyse whether Micromax is an innovative company or not. The outcome of the survey response pinpoints that the customers think that the company is innovative; however, there is scope for improvements in the innovations. When the customer satisfaction of the Micromax products is considered, most of the customers rated that they are somewhat satisfied with the products of the firm. However, many customers have also rated that the customers are also not completely satisfied with the products of Micromax. The scope for innovation is important for

improving the performance of Micromax in the Indian market. Through the current survey, 46% of customers rated that they are somewhat satisfied with the products and services of Micromax.

While considering the survey response, most of the customers have mentioned that they think the products and services of Micromax are efficient. In the current study around 47% of customers rated that they are highly satisfied with the products of the company while, 30% of the customers also think that they does not think that the products are highly effective when compared with the other smartphone giants in the market. The higher competition rate and any number of market entries are the significant reasons for the issues in the performance of Micromax in the Indian market. This could be underlined as the major reason for the lack of customer interest in the products of Micromax. Besides, some customers have also opined that the products of Micromax are not at all effective. The rise of other marketers with higher-end products in the smartphone sector is a major reason for the negative impression of customers of the products of Micromax.

The customers also responded that the products of Micromax are identified to be similar when compared with the products of the competitors. For the current question, around 66% of the customers pointed out that the Micromax maintains the features of their product portfolio similar to that of the competitors in the Indian market.

Most of the Chinese companies in smartphone sector have come up with much advancement in technologies, and therefore, Micromax should focus on bringing diversification in the product portfolio as most of their products are having similar features like other smartphones sold in the Indian market. For the current question, around 66% of the customers responded that the features of Micromax mobiles are seen in many other marketers in the smartphone sector. The researcher also tries to comprehend various aspects that make the Micromax products unique and best in the smartphone market, and they are the pricing factors. When compared with other smartphone companies in the Indian market, Micromax is able to provide the same quality products at a lower pricing scheme. In the current survey also, around 53% of customers have rated that price is a significant factor that contributes to the customer buying intention of the smartphone.

Moreover, the survey response indicates that Micromax was able to provide customers with quality products and services in the Indian market. In addition to this, the design

of Micromax products was also considered the main reason for propelling the customer interest in purchasing. Through the current survey, around 27% of customers rated on product design significance. However, Indian customers are highly concentrated on using high-quality camera features like the number of social media users is higher in the market. In addition to this, highly surviving and sustaining battery is also employed by many other marketers in India. Henceforth, the customers are not feeling any uniqueness towards the camera quality and battery life of Micromax, which needs to be improved.

In the survey it was inquired that whether the services and products of Micromax is innovative. Most of the customers also responded that the Micromax has a weak technology which is one of the major causes that resulted in lower customer interest in buying their products. In the current survey, 41% of the customers responded that technology is the weak point of the Micromax which needs to be enhanced. In addition to this, the storage issues are also noted in the case of Micromax from the customer's response. The company need to undertake strict strategies for overcoming these issues. On the other hand, 73% of the customers are likely to recommend the products of Micromax to others. On the other hand, 27% of customers are likely not to recommend the products to other consumers.

The company should be able to make the customers buy and recommend their products to others. In fact, through the current survey, the customers have also mentioned that they are not completely interested in making purchase decisions based on their opinions. Through the current survey, 73% of customers are interested in recommending Micromax products to customers while 27% of the customers are not interested in recommending products. Besides, the researcher has also gathered various recommendations for improving the innovation performance of Micromax in the Indian market.

5.4 Thematic analysis

A qualitative data analysis method is thematic analysis that involves reading through data set that is from transcripts conducted through in-depth interviews and identify patterns based on the accumulated data through the interview. In the current section of thematic analysis based on the responses accumulated from the interview various themes related to the study issue has been formulated. For qualitative data analysis thematic analysis is observed to be the flexible approach as that enables the researcher for producing new

concepts and insights that are derived the accumulated qualitative data. In the research study on using thematic analysis several benefits can be attained and that is the researcher who are entering into research newly it helps in learning how to evaluate and analyses qualitative data in effective was as it is observed to be one of the accessible approach for the researcher. Moreover, in the thematic analysis the attained responses and results from interview will be cross-compared with the literature findings and link in the below section of thematic analysis. Based on the responses and questions asked in the interview the four main themes identified are importance of innovations in the smartphone industry, factors impacting innovation of Micromax Informatics, Changing buying preferences of the customers, market competition, technological advancements and current trends and influence of leadership role in enhancing innovation performance of the organisation are the four main themes identified from study results and it has been detailed below.

Theme 1: Innovations in the smartphone industry

The information collected from the managers of Micromax points towards a similar trend for the smartphone industry. In their opinion, innovations are found to assist in resource management by reducing the overall time taken for the processing of raw materials. Efficient resource management will eventually lead to profitability for smartphone companies. The relation between innovation and resource management was pointed out by many participants in the interview. However, from the literature results it has been observed that the use of innovative strategies and new creativity on market product, processes or procedures benefits the organization in increasing the market rate, usefulness, significance and performance of the products or services. Moreover, it has also been noted that innovation strategy is the ability to transform innovation inputs into outputs which results innovative market success (Gault, 2018). For the question how significant is innovation in smartphone sector, the R&D Manager opines that *“Supplying raw materials is a major challenge in the business since it needs to satisfy the customers well. When the innovation rate has improved well, we can provide enough raw materials within less time.”* The opinion of the supplier manager further consolidated the impact of innovation on resource management. Moreover, from the results of literature review has also stated that innovations in the smartphone industry are found to enhance the efficiency of resource management (Suroso and Azis, 2015).

The production of smartphones contains various complex stages and innovation can

significantly assist them as inferred from the excerpts of the interview. One of the managers states that *“When the technology is advanced, it could reduce the overall product development cycle and adequate for implementing new changes in the process”*. On the other hand, the results of literature results has stated that there is several standardisation in terms of product features and technology, there is still a lot of innovation in this industry (Cecere et al., 2014). Thus, from these results it can be stated that in the smartphone industry technology innovation plays the significant role. Also, the importance of the circular economy as stated by one manger *“As we know that the circular economy has become very popular in the corporate world due to unavailability of resources”* leads to the reduction in the product development cycle. The efficient product development cycle is found to reduce the carbon emissions and cost of production.

Another significant variable of organisational performance that was repeatedly pinpointed throughout the interview is customer satisfaction. Due to the high competition in the market, customer satisfaction was the one aspect through which companies tried to gain the upper hand in the market. Most of the participants stressed the importance of innovation, leading to customer satisfaction. The literature study results also states that the company failed to achieve its monthly outcome due to less customer satisfaction. Thus, every organisation needs to concern about customer satisfaction factor by providing better services to them (Namboodiri et al., 2019).

The relationships manager and marketing manager of Micromax has a similar opinion on the link between customer satisfaction and innovation. In the word of the relationship’s manager *“While handling the customers in the business, I am always trying to enhance customer’s satisfaction. I have noticed that when I communicate about the latest innovation about the project, they were excited to hear about that”*. The marketing manager further adds that *“I have understood that consistent changes in the products are always necessary for the customers to satisfy in the business”*.

While looking at the literature, it can be understood that various trends and innovations are continuously emerging in the smartphone industry. When one company comes out with innovations, the customers are attracted to them. Also, smartphones that do not incorporate the new trends in the market or innovate in any way are found to be rejected by the customers. Thus, leading to the inference that innovation can lead to the satisfaction of smartphone customers.

For the question on significance of innovation, Operations manager opines that *“We*

have seen many examples like Nokia, which was not sustained in the business due to the lack of innovation. Hence, I am considering innovation as an effective tool for enhancing the innovation rate of an organisation". Lack of innovation is considered as a downgrading element in the smartphone industry. Various companies such as Nokia have lost their market due to not following the latest trends and innovating their products. The same opinion has been obtained from the literature study results also that is stating some of the industry's long-standing giants, including Nokia, Motorola, Sony Ericsson, and RIM, are fast losing market share and are currently battling to develop viable innovation plans that will ensure a long-term competitive edge (Cecere, Corrocher and Battaglia, 2017).

As stated by the marketing manager, *"Innovation is suitable for any company in the smartphone industry to bring regular changes in mobile phones"*. The competition in the smartphone market depends on the degree of innovation in the market. Companies that are associated with innovative products do have a competitive advantage in the market.

Theme 2: Factors that impact the innovation performance of Micromax

Innovation performance is an important aspect for a company to survive in the market by managing the existing competitors. In the case of Micromax, there are many influencing factors which determines the innovation performance of Micromax. From the interview, most of the opinions from the managers are pointing into certain common aspects. While comparing with the opinions of managers from the literature review, certain similarities and differences are identified. Among the seven managers, most of them were talked about the leadership and time-management and its impact on the innovation performance of Micromax. From the opinion of the sales manager, leadership is motivating the staffs working in the organisation and leads to the enhancement of innovation in smartphones. From the words of assistant manager, development of a framework for time-management has provided adequate result for Micromax in the production of smartphones.

Similarly, from the results of literature studies states that leadership is playing a crucial role in the development of innovation performance of smartphones companies (Sakkthivel et al., 2020). On the other hand, Erasmus et al. (2015) mentioned that effective leadership in an organisation could provide the vision for a company essential for performing well in the market. While combining findings from both

literature review and interview leadership can contribute to the more innovative smartphone companies' performance.

The managers from the different department are provided with a different opinion about the leadership and its impact. As mentioned by R&D manager *“in leadership, we are not intended to follow hierarchical positions because we need to satisfy our employees well in business. Our management believes that motivating employees could enhance the innovation rate in the business”*. Similarly, as per the observation of relationship manager *“Our management is working with great vision, and it is motivating the employees working in the company”*. Overall, in the future also, leadership can act as an important influencing factor for Micromax to increase innovation performance. Likewise, the results of literature study indicate that leadership skills play a vital role in improving the innovation performance where the leaders motivate, create new ideas, communicate and inform the entire workforce of the organisation and take appropriate actions for it (Bagga et al., 2016). From interview analysis, Time-management is another most discussed influential factor of innovation performance of Micromax. Like leadership, many opinions are coming from the managers explained the role of time-management in the innovation performance of Micromax. That is the literature findings states that the customer does expects more from the Smartphone manufacturers as their preferences and the desire to experience updates in technology change from time to time. From the words of relationship manager *“However, leadership cannot work as stand-alone to increase the innovation performance of the company. Hence, In Micromax, we have developed a framework for proper time- management in the production process. It has influenced us very well for enhancing the innovation performance of the organisation”*. Microsoft was giving high priority for time-management and implemented it at the commercial level.

However, Micromax has taken time-management as an important factor for enhancing the innovation performance of the company. It means that the company is making a new way of enhancing the innovation performance of Micromax in the business. As mentioned by assistant manager *“After following the framework in time-management, we have got consistent results in the production process”*. These results in the production unit show that in future time-management can also contribute more to the innovation performance of Micromax.

Some managers are also opined about the cost and resource as the influencing factor of the innovation performance of Micromax. However, these opinions are not common among the ten managers who participated in the interview. It means that Micromax is not considering well about the resource and cost management in their business performance. As mentioned by marketing manager “*Here cost means the operational cost invested by the organisation to produce innovative products. When any smartphone companies in the market are launched any innovative products, I always used to analyse the product's investment cost and most of the cases; it will be more*”. Here the manager opined that investment cost is more effective for managing the existing competition in the market. As per the analysis of Economic times (2019) in the literature review, the effective investment cost is the proper way into increasing the profitability of the organisation. Moreover, Erasmus et al.(2015), opined that innovation performance in the organisation is suitable for reducing the expense rate in the business. In the overall, both cost and innovation performance are directly proportional to each other and incrementing any factor could enhance the efficiency of an organisation. Likewise, Sakkthivel et al.(2020), opined in the literature review that innovation could reduce the exploitation of resources in the business. Even though previous studies are highly supporting cost and resources related to innovation performance, Micromax didn't consider or implemented these two aspects well.

Theme 3: Changing buying preferences of the customers, market competition, technological advancements and current trends are the major drivers which leads to innovations in the smartphone industry

When analysing information from literature and interview, it is found that changing buying preferences of the customers, competitors, technological advancements and current trends lead smartphone manufacturers to innovations. Majority of the managers had the opinion that the changing preferences of the customers affect the demand for certain products in the market. The availability of social media and internet has created the need for the customers to depend on smartphones which have large storage and efficiency in accessing networks. Therefore, smartphones with such qualities have brought a need for the smartphone manufacturers to produce smartphones with high quality and new features.

Smartphone manufacturers are adopting innovations to improve the quality of products

and gain competitive advantage in the market. In addition, the innovations made by smartphone manufacturers have also increased product quality and customer satisfaction too (Arpaci et al., 2015). Similar information was found in the interview responses also as manager 7 and manager 10 said that the preferences of the customers has created the need for production of high-quality smartphones. New and innovative products attract the customers to a great extent and the availability of such products.

From the response of the manager 7 it is understood that the demands and preferences of the customers are changing according to the emergence of different technologies, Thus the changing preferences of the customers is one of the major factors which leads smartphone manufacturers to innovations. From the finding of literature, it is found that the market competition is also one of the major driving forces towards innovations. Innovations are brought by companies in the smartphone industry to exist in the market. There is high level of competition in the smartphone industry due to the emergence of new companies and adoption of new technologies by the companies. Majority of the managers interviewed in the current research felt that market competition is an important driving force towards innovations. In the literature it is noted that competition has been one of the major aspects which leads organisations to choose innovations in the production of smartphones. Customer needs are satisfied when organisations adopt innovations. Such innovations help organisations to gain competitive advantage. Long term success is achieved by organisations through innovations. Therefore, innovations play a significant role in gaining competitive advantage in the industry. Moreover, it has also been noted that organisations in the smartphone industry investments on research and development to enhance technology in various operational areas. This indicates that creative ideas can be better applied in the products through innovations.

Furthermore, technological growth is an important factor which improves the quality of products and its features. New features of products are introduced by companies through the adoption of new technologies. Quality chips and high-quality cameras are used by smartphone manufacturers with the use of advanced technologies. Therefore, the role of advanced technologies is an important factor in bringing innovations in organisations (Sakkthivel et al., 2020). The technological advancements in India could be better utilised by Micromax to produce products with high quality through innovations. Technology upgradation is one of the main aspects in the innovations of

Micromax. Similar information was shared by manager 6 as he said that the availability of advanced technologies helped the company to make innovations in different areas of operations. Micromax has been utilising artificial intelligence and internet of things for their innovations.

In addition, the customers of current days demand products which are produced out of advanced technologies which has diverse features and modern outlook. Since technologies lead human beings in the purchase of products, it has created the need for smartphone companies to bring innovations in their products. Therefore, it is identified from the literature and interview responses that technological advancements and the availability of advanced technologies is driving force for the companies to produce innovative products in the market.

The findings from the literature and the interview responses showed that current trends in the smartphone industry is one of the driving forces towards innovations by smartphone companies. When analysing the literature review, it is understood that, the trends in the smartphone industry change by the availability of various technologies. The social media and internet has even changed the purchasing behaviour and selection of products. It is necessary to meet the changing needs of customers for smartphone companies to exist in the market. As a result, companies make innovations in the products with advanced features. The research and development made by organisations depends on the changing trends in the industry. The customers after technological growth and it put pressure on the smartphone companies to make innovations (Arpaci et al., 2015).

The customers gain satisfaction from the purchase of products with high quality and variety of features. Since the companies need to satisfy the customers, they are forced to make innovations in the products. Customers are attracted to smartphones with new features such as high screen display, high quality cameras and additional features. Innovations are required to meet these demands of the customers. Therefore, the trends in the industry is one of the major factors that leads organisations to adopt innovations.

It is clear from the responses of the managers that trends in the smartphone industry affect innovations to a great extent. Majority of the managers opined that the trends in the smartphone industry change along with the emergence of new technologies and the changing lifestyle of the people. It is important that smartphone manufacturers

need to satisfy the changing needs and demands of the customers to increase sales growth and improve the performance. Manager 2 said that customers are attracted towards the changing trends in the industry and it has become necessary for smartphone manufacturers to adopt innovations. Competitive advantage is gained by Micromax by manufacturing products which are in line with the existing trends in the industry. Manager 6 also had similar opinion as he said that the changing trends has significant impact on the adoption of innovations.

Micromax gives priority to the preferences of the customer which determined by the existing trends in the smartphone industry. The feedback from the customers regarding the products and their quality help them to identify the trends. Therefore, from the response of the managers, it is found that the market trends are one of the major drivers of innovations in the smartphone industry. The element behind the success of Micromax is that the company could meet the changing demands of the customers by considering the market trends. The data from the literature and the interview showed that the trends in the industry lead smartphone companies to bring innovations in their products. Based on the findings from the literature and the interview it is found that changing buying preferences of the customers, market competition, technological advancements and current trends are the major factors which leads smartphone manufactures towards innovation.

Theme 4: Leadership plays a vital role in the innovation performance of smartphone companies

From the interview results one of the managers working in R&D division mentioned that *“leaders can effectively share the mission and vision through proper communication. Thus, innovation goals and demands can be effectively communicated to improve the innovation performance.”* Similarly, from the literature results it is mentioned that the leaders possessing innovative ideas and thoughts would be transformed to the other employees in the organization (Nekmahmud et al., 2017). In addition, from the results of literature findings it has been noted that the innovation capability of the organization has been impacted by several factors and among them important role is played by leadership as this helps the organization in developing, supporting and ~~en~~ ^{en} innovation in the organization (McDowell and Kalidindi, 2016). Likewise, for developing innovation in the firm the main barrier is marked as lack of strong leadership capability (Nekmahmud et al., 2017). That is from the interview results it has been observed that for the loss of market share of the firm

Micromax and lack of innovative leaders worsened the situation as they do not focus on trends and changes that occurred in 4G technology.

While analysing the response, the leaders of Micromax lacked efficacy in implementing significant steps that helps the company to strive forward towards the path of innovation. When other Chinese and domestic companies in India probed deep into the possibilities of innovation and quickly fluxed into the world of 4G, Micromax was still lagging behind these companies. In the interview, Production Manager also pointed out that lack of focus on the innovations especially the rise of 4G and the dawn of 3G should have been focused by Micromax for improving their innovation level in business.

The Production Manager also spoke on unsold stocks in the company as there were leadership issues in the company. Only a limited number of leaders in Micromax had the idea on the market changes in the smartphone sector, which eventually led to the downfall of the company.

Relationship Manager responded that *“I think domestic competition was higher and we failed to anticipate the quick changes which are occurring in the market”*. The response enlightens on the leadership issues in forecasting high market competition in India, which was a major reason for the market loss of Micromax. Schumpeter’s Theory of Innovation also enlightened on the need for understanding the issues of high market competition for gaining competitive advantage for the firm (Malerba and McKelvey, 2020). Based on the response of Marketing Manager *“Other companies also started to introduce cheap and value for money smartphones which was the major factor behind Micromax phones initial success.”*

The response indicates the inability of leaders to understand the changing market scenario. The lack of leadership capability was identified through the response from the interview. The quality of leadership is an important factor that leverages the innovation performance of the firm.

The interview response portrayed on the significance of leadership for the innovative performance of a smartphone company. For the question on recommendations for improving the performance of Micromax, the HR Manager responded that *“I would recommend that Micromax could recommend that building a culture of innovation involves leaders and other higher officials where they help in providing a clear mission that the employees understand.”* Similarly, Marketing Manager of Micromax also responded that *“I would point out that the company’s leadership style determines the*

company's innovation performances." The interview response indicates the need for leadership for improving innovation performance.

In the literature review it has been observed that innovation performance is related to the efficacy of leadership in an organization (De Gooyert et al., 2017). Fabijan et al. (2015) added that the vision and mission of the organisation are created and executed by a leader, and henceforth, innovative visions propelled by the leader in an organisation is beneficial for the success of the organisation. A leader should be able to lead the employees towards the direction of innovation which is also highly significant for the development of the organisation. The interview response of Marketing Manager also pointed out that "*I also opine that the leaders can actively boost the employees to create innovation that leverages and uplifts the organisations brand image and credibility.*". Naranjo-Valencia et al. (2016) also added that the leadership is considered as the key enabler that significantly influences the innovation performance as the individuals in charge of the innovation process will also concentrate on educating other employees to direct them towards innovation.

On the other hand, the awareness of the need for innovation in the organisation is also the responsibility of a leader. In addition to this, the literature review also pointed out that the leaders are highly capable of developing an efficient network to induce the intention to change towards new innovative business roads (Naranjo-Valencia et al., 2016). The response of Supplier Manager similarly pointed out that "*I recommend that the appropriate leadership style adopted within the organisation improves the organisation's innovation performance.*" The Marketing Manager through the interview similarly pointed out that "*I prefer that the democratic leadership style would be suitable for Micromax.*". Fabijan et al. (2015) pointed out that research and development is a significant department which requires complete monitoring of the leaders for enhancing the outcome of business through the innovation method. The literature review also pinpointed out that the leaders can develop a better platform by playing a significant role in tying good relationship with stakeholders, suppliers and partners (Zhai et al., 2018). The interview response also pinpointed out that the leaders should be able to integrate diverse viewpoints of their employees for attaining best innovative idea. The leader should motivate and develop the employee skills and talents to improve their expertise and viewpoints that help the organisation attain success.

The Supplier Manager similarly pointed out that *“the innovation improved using the leadership style, as the leaders under democratic style support the stakeholders to contribute their ideas to innovate the operations of the organisation effectively.”* The significance of effective leadership style was pointed out both in literature and interview session.

The Sales Manager pointed out that *“I suggest that a proper leadership style within the company helps the company to improve its innovation performance.”* Clarke et al.(2015) in the literature review noted that the innovative leaders are capable of organising, managing workforce and also shows high interest in the innovative development process. Besides, the innovative leader the primary contributors to the innovative performance of the workplace. The interview response from the Sales Manager *“While most of the companies were concentrated on innovations, Micromax mainly concentrated on pricing and operational cost reduction. I think, Micromax had even renewed their operational method to attain good market recognition.”*

The lack of proper leadership is one of the major factors that limited the efficacy of business performance in the market in the case of Micromax. In the interview response, most of the respondents pinpointed out that the lack of forecast and decisions of leaders led to the challenges and barriers in the company. The inefficacy of the leaders also explained the challenges which were encountered by the Micromax for providing higher customer satisfaction.

In addition to this, customer satisfaction which is an imperative aspect of the development of every firm was lacking in the case of Micromax. The continues crisis in the tech arena was another significant reason for the issues in the company. The leaders should be capable of boosting the skills and talents of the employees for accomplishing better results in innovation performance of the company. The response of the Marketing Manager also detailed that *“Micromax just couldn't keep up with the tough competition with their cheap Chinese imitations and that's the main reason I think lead to the company's collapse.”* The above inferences pointed out the need for stringent leadership for improving the business performance of the firm.

5.5 Summary

For evaluating the research findings critically was the main objective of this chapter. Therefore, the chapter has undertaken both qualitative and quantitative analysis of the data. The survey findings were explained in detail to depict the results of the findings.

The surveys were depicted through the help of charts and tables. The survey was conducted among 100 customers of Micromax through survey monkey. Moreover, the interview was conducted among ten managers of Micromax.

Therefore, the interview responses were analysed and founded out using the thematic analysis. Thus, this chapter was very useful in gaining information related to innovation performance, and its implications for the company was understood in detail. Besides, the present chapter provides a detailed outline of all results collected from the survey and interview analysis. The survey analysis indicated that most of the customers of Micromax showed a positive attitude towards the products; however, the current market trends and newly updated in the mobile phone are becoming serious, and due to this reason, most of the products possessed by Micromax is also available in other series of smartphone marketers.

In addition to this, one of the major factors that trigger customer interest in buying products is noted as the pricing of smartphones. In addition to this, design and durability, performance, camera features are some of the notable qualities that make a smartphone product alluring to the customers. Besides, the company should maintain a better performance as the smartphone market is developing day-by-day. The customers are the key stakeholders of every organisation, and the smartphone company should keep a regular update on the upcoming trends and necessities of customers in the market. The interview response also provided a detailed perspective of Managers working across different departments in Micromax.

Chapter 6: Conclusion and Recommendation

6.1 Introduction and summary of the thesis

The sole objective of the present research is to critically analyse the extent of innovation incorporated in the Smartphone industry analyzing the case of Micromax Informatics in India in particular. Further the research is comprehended in analysing the need for innovation performance of the Smartphone industry.

The main objectives thus set for the research include to analyses the intricacies for the innovation performance of the Micromax Informatics brand within the wide field of innovation and also to study the position of the brand in comparison to the developing nations.

This was particularly intriguing as it could be argued that the world as a whole is becoming a knowledge society, driven by the advancement of smartphone innovation. A more pragmatic justification was to provide some scholarly support, albeit very minor, to developing nations' academic institutions that are under pressure from the wider local and global forces as ICT is described as an important factor in terms of facilitating more interactive pedagogic practices around the world.

However, in order to gather the relevant data for the research both survey and interview thereby gathering the information related to the innovation performance of the brand in the Indian market. The data collected through the interview have been analysed using the thematic analysis. Moreover, the chapter also recommends suitable measures that would facilitate the brand to enhance the innovation performance.

Further, the researcher adopted the interpretivism philosophy with the intention to gain the actual information regarding the innovation performance of the brand and thereby offer more reliable and accurate results supporting the accomplishments of the research objectives more successfully. The interpretivism philosophy can be identified to be. realize the trends that are followed by Micromax in their innovation performance. Additionally, the interpretivism philosophy can benefit the research to carry out the qualitative and quantitative analysis proficiently

However, the researcher was engaged in using both explanatory and descriptive research design that facilitates to study the issue involved in the research in detail. The research design can enable the researcher to understand the reason behind the causes and ore specifically understand the causes behind the failure of the innovation performance of the brand.

6.2 Objectives

Objective 1: To gain insights into the contributors to innovation performance in Indian Smartphone sector

The researcher's primary objective was to gain insights into the contributors to innovation performance in Indian Smartphone sector. It was observed from the literature review that the critical specifications that determine the exterior and interior factors of the smartphone industry are knowledge management, economic status, leadership skills and networking that are included in the essential enablers of the innovation performance (Jung, 2015).

The findings of Cecere et al. (2015) states that the firm that makes effective utilisation of innovation for gaining competitive advantage will be able to generate better sales and profits by meeting the changing customer needs and requirements. However, on the other hand, Jung (2015) argued that the real innovations in organisations are truly challenging and is impacted by many factors such as cultural beliefs and business environment. Further, it could be identified that many factors drive the organisation's innovation performances, which includes corporate culture, leadership, employee commitments, and organisational environment.

Likewise, in the Smartphone industry, some of the major factors that motivate the firms operating the industry to come up with the innovations include changing customer buying behaviour and cut-throat competition. The Smartphone manufacturers have to be more conscious in understanding the preferences and the desire to experience updates in technology change from time to time. It could be founded out that the realisation of the customer experiences and their preferences drive the Smartphone industry pools to increase the investments towards R&D and aims to bring updates in the technology and launch new products and services that cater to the changing needs of customers. Thus, Arpaci et al. (2015) mentioned that innovations are the important factor determining survivability and the competitive advantage of Smartphone manufacturers in the industry.

Hence, it could be understood from the findings on the literature review, that the major factors that affect the smartphone industry include competition, customers, technological advancements and current trends in the smartphone sector.

Further, the survey analysis results portrayed that the major factor that customer prefers while purchasing smartphone includes performance, camera quality, and

storage showing the current trends and technological advancements used in the smartphones. These trends show the varying trends and styles and the preference of smartphones by the customers. However, focusing on the case of Micromax, it could be understood from the survey results that the storage capacity of the company is very weak along with the camera features. Nevertheless, the smartphone's battery life was identified to be high, stating that the technological advancements and current trends followed by the company are very weak.

Besides, it could be understood that price is the major unique factor considered by the customers while they opt for Micromax smartphone to purchase. This is because the pricing for the smartphones under Micromax is such that it is available at a low cost that its competitors, which increases the sales of the product.

However, the findings reveal that the design and camera features and battery life are less competing for the company to sustain in the competitive smartphone market. This shows that customers highly prefer technology and trends apart from the pricing offered by smartphones. The less technological advancements adopted by the company made them face several challenges in a similar industry.

The reports of the survey findings also elucidated that the major drawback identified within the selection of the Micromax smartphones is the weak technology they adopted. The weak technology they adopted has resulted in several issues within the company leading them to face a decrease in sales and less customer attraction and engagement. Moreover, smartphones had less battery life, stating that the smartphone failed to follow the customers' current trends. They preferred smartphones with high durability and design with long battery life.

Thus, through the survey, it was understood that technological advancements and current trends were highly impacting the customer's tastes and preference which determined the competition in the industry. Hence, it could be understood from the findings of the survey that the major factors that affected the smartphone industry include competition, customers, technological advancements and current trends in the smartphone sector.

Moreover, the interview responses conducted with the ten managers of Micromax smartphones mentioned that the major factor that impacted Micromax to launch innovation included the demand of the customers, where the demand of the customers change every day as per the changing needs. Moreover, competition is also a vital factor that drives innovation within the company as opined by the HR manager and

the marketing manager. Moreover, the operations manager's findings commented that changing trends in the smartphone industry determines the innovation be adopted.

The managers also opined that increasing demand for products, technological advancements and increased competition in the smartphone industry are main factors in the smartphone industry to contribute to innovation performance in the Micromax smartphones. The response of Assistant Head R&D of company Y mentioned that the adoption of innovations in the company changes the market's price and quality, the existing trends in the market, and the availability of advanced technologies.

Similarly, the one of the managers through interview have opined that people's changing lifestyle, technological innovations, and the variations in the demands for certain selected products. The interview responses pointed out that people of different cultural and educational backgrounds choose products with advanced features. This makes us bring innovations to our products. Along with this, competition has been increased in the smartphone industry, which is also considered one of the major reasons for bringing innovations in the company's operations.

Hence, from the results attained through the interview, survey and literature findings stated that the current trends and customers preference were the major drivers that led the company to adopt innovation performance. The changing customer trends and lifestyle made the companies adopt technological advancements to stay competitive in the market. Therefore, the interview responses elucidated that the smartphone industry's major factors include competition, customers, technological advancements and current trends in the smartphone sector.

Objective 2: “To analyse the intricacies of innovation performance in the context of Micromax Informatics”

The interview section, survey and literature review pointed on the major complexities which were encountered in the case of innovation performance of Micromax. In the interview, most of the respondents indicated that Micromax had encountered strict competition in the market which is one of the major reasons for the issues in their innovative business performance. In addition to this, Micromax also encountered a strict decline in innovative business performance due to research and development practices.

A smartphone company has to be updated with latest trends and technologies in order to accomplish a better market position (Ajibade, 2018). Besides, most respondents in

the interview section who have direct contact and link with the organisation pointed out that the complexities of innovation activities were a major threat to business development. From the results of the literature review it has been stated that the innovation is one of the imperative aspects that fortify the competitive advantage of the business and besides, the innovation level is also significant for a smartphone company to accomplish customer satisfaction (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018).

In addition to these inferences, Geissdoerfer et al. (2018) also added that brand fame would be higher for the companies which tend to change with the market needs. In the literature review, Sundararaj (2015) examined that Micromax lacked higher financial support and gain, which could be examined as the major reason for the inability to execute the innovation strategies. In addition to this, the Micromax also encountered a crisis in innovation due to the similar replicated technologies introduced by Chinese smartphone brands. The lack of uniqueness of the products was a major issue seen in the case of Micromax. The failure in planning and systematic steps were the major issues that triggered the complexity of innovation performance in the market.

Through the survey response, most of the customers also mentioned that the technologies and advancements utilised in the smartphones of Micromax are also seen in many other smartphone brands. However, pricing is the major factor which makes Micromax unique and different from other mobile phone sellers in the market. While taking the design, camera quality and battery life, most of the other marketers are also providing similar quality of mobile phone products. The survey response pinpoints that the Micromax products are efficient; however, there are many other marketers with greater performance at the same price in the Indian market. The inability to differentiate the products from other smartphone brands is one of the major complexities encountered by Micromax in the Indian smartphone sector. In the literature review, Namboodiri et al. (2019) added that Micromax failed to accomplish the business expected target due to the decline in customer purchases.

Besides, Micromax showed incapability to target the customers as their product portfolio and technologies were offered by many other competitors in India. The lack of précised steps taken in the planning and innovation performance elevated the complexities in innovation performance of Micromax. The survey and interview result similarly pointed out that the Micromax faced intense competition, which negatively affected customer satisfaction. The literature review also clearly pointed on the need for minimising the complexities that put limits on the innovation performance of an

organisation. The complexities in innovation performance should be overcome by Micromax for gaining competitive advantage and customer satisfaction on their products in Indian market (Thimmaiah, 2016). Henceforth, the second objective on the complexities encountered by Micromax for improving their innovation performance in the Indian market was studied through the analysis of the survey, interview response and literature review.

Objective 3: “To understand the particularities of the innovation crisis confronted by Micromax Informatics”

The response of the survey and interview indicates that Micromax encountered many crises in the Indian market. Based on the survey response, most of the customers consider performance and camera quality are the major drivers of purchasing a mobile phone and however, Micromax has a competitive advantage only in their pricing strategy.

Based on the survey results, most of the customers pointed out that the company is lagging behind unique and specific mobile features and besides, most of the competitors in Indian smartphone sector are offering products which are similar to the Micromax. Based on the literature findings, Agwu et al. (2017) argued that the products and services offered by the marketers should be regularly updated for gaining competitive advantage.

However, in the case of Micromax, the company has products which are similar to their customers and also lacks updates in technology. In the interview, most of the respondents pointed out that leadership was one of the major crises confronted in the case of Micromax, which negatively affected the implementation of innovative strategies. From the literature review from the conceptual framework, it is noted that the efficiency of leadership helps in codifying the team's activities and directing the workforce towards the innovative path. Besides, the research and development strategies are undertaken by the firm foster innovation performance.

Sundararaj (2015) in the literature similarly pointed out that the innovative leaders show the tendency to come up with new ideas and solutions which are beneficial for the organisation. In the interview response, the participants mentioned that the leaders of Micromax failed to examine the trends of 4G while they were still producing 3G and 2G mobile sets. The domestic competition was also triggered after Reliance introduced their 4G sim, which provides higher upload and download speed (Kiani et

al., 2020). The smartphone brands have taken quick initiatives to flux into the new realm of 4G, which led to the abandoning of 3G smartphones. However, Micromax failed to understand the threat of new technologies due to the lack of innovative leaders.

Besides, in the interview response also, most of the participants highlighted that company lacked innovative technologies when compared with other domestic and international smartphone brands in the Indian market. The technologies offered by international companies were high-end, and Micromax failed to catch up with these companies. Based on the literature review, the companies in the smartphone sector are hopping behind innovative and advanced technologies to serve the rising consumer demand for new products (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018). Besides, smartphone companies are trying to update their technology by implementing innovative strategies. The lack of innovative strategies and systematic planning could also be realised in the case of Micromax in the Indian market.

The financial capabilities and resources were also limited in the case of Micromax, which negatively impacted the business performance and quality of products and services offered to the customers (Sharma and Sharma, 2020). The interview response similarly pointed out that the company encountered a constant decline in sales and business performance, one of the major issues that impacted innovation development. The survey respondents also pinpointed out that Micromax needs to improve their technologies because most of the other smartphone sellers are providing similar products.

The inferences gathered from the survey, interview and literature pointed on the need for undertaking advanced and significant strategies for leveraging the innovation performance of the Micromax. Besides, the major barriers were noted as a lack of innovative tactics, financial issues and lack of effective leadership in streamlining business to accomplish innovative goals.

6.3 Recommendations

From the research findings, it was found that Micromax has been facing increased issues in its innovation performances. From the survey results, it was found that majority of the respondents finds Micromax as least innovation-oriented company.

Majority of the respondents identified the price of Micromax smartphones unique

compared to the competitors. While only a few identified the camera qualities of the Micromax unique when compared to the competitors. According to the survey findings, majority of the respondents i.e. the customers identified weak technology updates as the major shortfall of Micromax smartphones. Therefore, the following section of the current chapter will provide suitable recommendations to Micromax for improving the innovation performances of the company.

Regular technology improvements:

The technology updates in the smartphone industry refers to the commitment and the efforts of the Smartphone manufacturers to launch products that meets changing customer requirements. Assessing the customer expectations in the Smartphone industry, it can be identified that wearable and flexibility are the two major buzz words commonly discussed in the industry. Customers expect the Smartphone manufacturers to work on launching innovations that meets their comfortable level in terms of wearable and flexibility. From the survey findings, it was found that the camera qualities of Micromax smartphones are average and customers expects the Smartphone manufacturer to work on this aspect and to launch technological up gradations that facilitates improvements in the camera performances of the product. On the basis of survey results, it is highly recommended that Micromax max must consider the consumer needs when developing the cameras. The increased desire for the users to experience better visual contents on the other hand fueled technology revolution in the smartphone cameras. Compared to the competitors, Micromax has failed to launch technology innovations in the camera quality and performances in the smartphones. Bringing regular technology updates in the camera features will be helpful for Micromax to grab increased customer attraction and thereby the sales. Adrija (2019) identified that it is the sensor size determines the camera quality and perfection in the smartphones. Smartphones with larger sensor size will be able to capture lighter and thereby the images captured will be of greater quality. Technology up gradations in the lenses and processors works better on improving the camera quality of the Smartphone. It is recommended that Micromax must consider making use of 5th generation image signal processor and neural processing unit to bring innovations in the camera features.

Launch innovations considering the market trends:

It is important to explore the needs and requirements of the customers in order to launch the innovation accordingly. The Smartphone industry can be identified to be highly competitive within a number of highly performing players. The establishment of Reliance Jio itself can be known to be a great failure for the Micromax. The demand for the changes in the technology and more modernized models changing over shorter span of time can be also regarded to be critically important for the Smartphone brands for altering their innovation performance. Thus, it can be noted that it is requisitely important to explore the changing requirements and demands of the customers and their buying preferences to survive in the industry for more prolonged periods.

Micromax had produced its devices supporting the 3G technologies having wide varied of devices with both 2G and 3G technology. However, the company has faced with serious issues related to upgrading their 2G and 3G handsets with that of 4G technology on the right time when the market demanded for the same. On the launch of the Reliance Jio and their devices supporting 4G technology availing free services of voice calls and internet browsing.

The Smartphone manufacturers must be aware of upcoming and newer technologies and must consider upgrading existing products in to it. Primarily, Micromax operated in the 3G sphere and they have variety of mobile phones operating on the basis of 2G and 3G technology. Micromax encountered huge failure when the manufacturer has failed to upgrade their existing 2G and 3G supporting handsets to 4G supporting device on the right time. From the initial launch of Jio by reliance, 4G calls and internet was widely accessible to the entire population for free of cost. People's entire approach to internet usage was changed when Reliance introduced Jio for free. At the same time, the handsets of Micromax were meant to support 2G and 3G network. Therefore, many of the users of Micromax handsets shifted to the smartphones that supports 4G network. From this, it can be understood that Micromax delayed upgrading its 2G and 3G handsets to 4G supporting device.

As a result of this, Micromax had failed to capture good market share and incurred huge losses in the industry. The survey results accompany with the findings derived

from the literature. From the survey results, it is clear that weak technology updates are the major shortfall of Micromax. Therefore, it is recommended that Micromax must upgrade its existing products with respect to the newest technologies.

The firm must study and research the upcoming trends and the customer preferences in the industry and must soon consider launching innovations at right time. Identifying and analyzing the future of Smartphone industry and launching the products accordingly will be assistive for the Micromax to survive and attain long term competitive advantage in the industry.

Adopt suitable leadership style

The weak leadership style can also be regarded as one of the major reason that obstructs the innovation performance of the organisation. The presence of an efficient and supporting leadership within any organisation can help to build a better team that is capable of offering products to the customers in the most sophisticated and recent technological integration and models. It is also studied from the literature that the innovation performance of any company can be highly influenced by the leadership style. The team working under good leadership style will be able to encourage and promote knowledge sharing, collaboration and coordination which on the other hand is fundamental for fostering the innovation performances of the organization. From the interview and survey results, it was found that Micromax is a bit lagging company when assessing in terms of innovations. The failure of Micromax to focus up on innovation and development of technology is the other main factor that caused Micromax to incur downfall in the industry. The important focus of Smartphone manufacturers must be on the development of new and innovative products and make the products readily available in the market before the competitor does.

Therefore, it is highly recommended that Micromax must adopt efficient leadership style and must pool increased investments towards its research and development as this will facilitate in the development of latest technologies with respect to the market trends time to time.

6.4 Limitation of the study

The current study undertook both interview and survey strategy for understating the

significance of innovation performance in a business context by considering the case of Micromax in the Indian smartphone sector. Both survey and interview questions were designed initially; however, due to the time constraints of participants due to their busy schedule, the questions were reduced.

The survey conducted in the current study gathered response from the participants through an online platform by providing the URL through social media platforms and email. Majority of participants have responded to the survey questions; however, some participants omitted certain questions which was another limitation of the study. Besides, the time limit was another major issue experienced while conducting the interview data collection method. Moreover, there are only limited interpretations attained on conducting interview and survey analysis. For conducting qualitative research there is need of huge time that is several months or weeks for completing the process. In addition, on conducting qualitative research the process is open-ended and so regarding the content of the data collected participants have more control towards the study.

6.5. Recommendation for future researches

The current study undertook research on the Micromax in the Indian market for understanding the significance of innovation in the smartphone sector. However, a comparative study with other international marketers would help understand more detailed concepts of innovation performance in business. The current study considered the case of Micromax due to time constraints. However, in future researches, innovative practices undertaken by other international or domestic smartphone brands in the Indian market could be compared with the Micromax.

6.6 Contribution to the theory practice and knowledge

The researcher has used both the interview and survey strategy for collecting the data pertaining to the research study. The researcher has identified that the major causes for the weak innovation performances of Micromax is that the weak leadership style, corporate environment, lack of people support and weak understanding about the user needs and expectations. The researcher has identified from the survey results that the camera quality of Micromax is inadequate. This shows that Micromax has failed to implement technology improvements in the camera features of its Smartphone. Based

on the survey results and interview responses, the researcher has provided suitable recommendations to the company. Based on the findings, the researcher also recommended Micromax to consider launching innovations after studying the market trends and customers changing buying behaviour more in detail.

The researcher has identified the major shortfalls of Micromax and recommended the company to improve its leadership style. The researcher has recommended Micromax to adopt the leadership style that promotes innovations in the company. A good leadership style will be able to create and build a better team capable of delivering their best towards the innovation performances of the company. The researcher has also recommended to Micromax that the firm must consider implementing regular technology updates as this will be helpful in catering the changing needs and expectations time to time. The camera quality of Micromax was found as weak by many customers and this can be however fixed by the firm by considering the technology up gradations in the camera features.

The current study has elevated the theoretical underpins of the researcher on innovation performance. Besides, the study provided a detailed understanding of the significance of innovation performance in a business context. By comparing and contrasting the results from the literature review, the responses from the ten managers of Micromax smartphones and the survey results identified, it could be stated that customers, technological advancements, competition and current trends are the major factor that drives Micromax to launch innovations. Besides, the secondary data gained through the literature review and the primary data through the interview and the survey improved the theoretical expertise on innovation performance. On the other hand, the innovation performance in smartphone industries by probing the case of Micromax was highly helpful for enhancing the practical knowledge on the topic.

References:

Al-Furaih, S.A.A. and Al-Awidi, H.M. (2018). Teachers' Change Readiness for the Adoption of Smartphone Technology: Personal Concerns and Technological Competency. *Technology, Knowledge and Learning*.

Yahoo Finance (2021) *Global smartphone market (2020 to 2027) - by operating system, display technology, screen size, ram capacity, price range, distribution channel and region*. Available at: <https://finance.yahoo.com/news/global-smartphone-market-2020-2027-093800419.html>

(Accessed: 09 November 2021).

Business Today.In (2021) *India's smartphone market to touch record 173 mn units in 2021*. Available at: <https://www.businesstoday.in/industry/telecom/story/indias-smartphone-market-to-touch-record-173-mn-units-in-2021-304835-2021-08-21> (Accessed: 09 November 2021).

Giachetti, C. and Dagnino, G. B. (2021) *Competitive Dynamics in Strategic Management*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Fartash, K., Davoudi, S.M.M., Baklashova, T.A., Svechnikova, N.V., Nikolaeva, Y.V., Grimalskaya, S.A. and Beloborodova, A.V. (2018) The impact of technology acquisition & exploitation on organisational innovation and organisational performance in knowledge-intensive organisations. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 14(4), pp.1497-1507.

Anzola-Román, P., Bayona-Sáez, C. and García-Marco, T. (2018) Organisational innovation, internal R&D and externally sourced innovation practices: Effects on technological innovation outcomes. *Journal of Business Research*, 91, pp.233-247.

Micromax Informatics (2020) *Micromax – Nothing like anything*. Available at: <https://micromaxinfo.com/> (Accessed: 09 November 2021).

Yeo, C., Kee, D.M.H., Mo, X.Y., Ang, H.E., Chua, S.M., Agnihotri, S. and Pandey, S., (2020) Technology advancement and growth: A case study of Huawei. *Journal of the Community Development in Asia (JCDA)*, 3(1), pp. 82-91.

Sury, M. M. (2021) *Factors that led to India's spectacular performance in global innovation indexes*. Available at: <https://www.timesnownews.com/business-economy/economy/article/factors-that-led-to-indias-spectacular-performance-in-global-innovation-indexes/824627> (Accessed: 09 November 2021).

- Menon, V. (2017) *Innovation stories from India Inc. - Their story in their words*. London: Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Mohan, R. (2018) *India transformed: Twenty-five years of economic reforms*. Washington: Brookings Institution Press.
- Zuelke, A. and Kirwan, P. (2016) Global competitiveness and local business development. *Economic Development Journal*, 15(3), pp. 1-5.
- Livemint (2015) *Micromax world's 10th largest mobile phone brand in Q1*. Available at: <https://www.livemint.com/Consumer/NJWeTcXovj8YC7d7VN2TSN/Micromax-worlds-10th-largest-mobile-phone-brand-in-Q1-Gart.html> (Accessed: 22 November 2021).
- Molenaar, C. (2016) *Why Customers Would Rather Have a Smartphone than a Car*. Routledge: Taylor & Francis.
- Digit (2021) *Top 10 Mobile Companies in India*. Available at: <https://www.godigit.com/mobile-insurance/find/top-mobile-brands-in-india> (Accessed: 22 November 2021).
- Almeida, A. (2020) *What Happened to Micromax? The Rise & Fall Story!*. Available at: <https://tradebrains.in/micromax-story/> (Accessed: 22 November 2021).
- Boaz, A., Hanney, S., Borst, R., O'Shea, A. and Kok, M. (2018) How to engage stakeholders in research: design principles to support improvement. *Health research policy and systems*, 16(1), pp.1-9.
- Handa, M. and Ahuja, P. (2020). Disconnect to detox: a study of smartphone addiction among young adults in India. *Young Consumers*, ahead-of-print(ahead-of-print).
- Sidel, J.L., Bleibaum, R.N. and Tao, K.C. (2018) Quantitative descriptive analysis. *Descriptive analysis in sensory evaluation*, 287.
- Stankevich, A. (2017) Explaining the consumer decision-making process: Critical literature review. *Journal of International Business Research and Marketing*, 2(6).
- Derakhshan, R., Turner, R. and Mancini, M. (2019) Project governance and stakeholders: a literature review. *International Journal of Project Management*, 37(1), pp.98-116.
- Dinglas, V.D., Chessare, C.M., Davis, W.E., Parker, A., Friedman, L.A., Colantuoni, E., Bingham, C.O., Turnbull, A.E. and Needham, D.M. (2018) Perspectives of survivors, families and researchers on key outcomes for research in acute respiratory failure. *Thorax*, 73(1), pp.7-12.

Ismail, N., Kinchin, G. and Edwards, J.A. (2018) Pilot study, does it really matter? Learning lessons from conducting a pilot study for a qualitative PhD thesis. *International Journal of Social Science Research*, 6(1), pp.1-17.

Buffel, T. (2019) Older coresearchers exploring age-friendly communities: An “insider” perspective on the benefits and challenges of peer-research. *The Gerontologist*, 59(3), pp.538-548.

Yue, L., Chen, W., Li, X., Zuo, W. and Yin, M. (2019) A survey of sentiment analysis in social media. *Knowledge and Information Systems*, 60(2), pp.617-663.

Mkandawire, S.B. (2019) Selected common methods and tools for data collection in research. *Selected Readings in Education*, 2, pp.143-153.

Yu, Y., Umer, W., Yang, X. and Antwi-Afari, M.F. (2021) Posture-related data collection methods for construction workers: A review. *Automation in Construction*, 124, p.103538.

Ismail, N., Kinchin, G. and Edwards, J.A. (2018) Pilot study, does it really matter? Learning lessons from conducting a pilot study for a qualitative PhD thesis. *International Journal of Social Science Research*, 6(1), pp.1-17.

Rodríguez-López, Á. and Souto, J.E. (2020) Empowering entrepreneurial capacity: training, innovation and business ethics. *Eurasian Business Review*, 10(1), pp.23-43.

Hilton, C.E. (2017) The importance of pretesting questionnaires: a field research example of cognitive pretesting the Exercise referral Quality of Life Scale (ER-QLS). *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 20(1), pp.21-34.

Khan, M.N. and Rahman, O. (2019) Developing a Smartphone Dependency Scale for University Students in India: A Confirmatory Factor Analytic Approach. *International Journal of Knowledge Management and Practices*, 7(2), p.29.

Choudrie, J., Pheeraphuttrangkoon, S. and Davari, S. (2018). The Digital Divide and Older Adult Population Adoption, Use and Diffusion of Mobile Phones: a Quantitative Study. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 12(1SSN/0576).

Wells, P. and Nieuwenhuis, P. (2018). Over the hill? Exploring the other side of the Rogers' innovation diffusion model from a consumer and business model perspective. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 194, pp.444–451.

Almunawar, M.N., Anshari, M. and Susanto, H. (2018) Adopting Open-Source Software in Smartphone Manufacturers' Open Innovation Strategy. In *Encyclopedia of Information Science*

and Technology, Fourth Edition (pp. 7369-7381). IGI Global.

Ross, S. (2019). Samsung Vs. Apple: Comparing Business Models (AAPL, SSNLF). Investopedia. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/articles/markets/110315/samsung-vs-applecomparing-business-models.asp>

Marler, W. (2018) Mobile phones and inequality: Findings, trends, and future directions. *New Media & Society*, 20(9), pp.3498-3520.

Naik, M., Bhatia, A. and Tiwari, K. (2020) January. I know who you are: a learning framework to profile smartphone users. In *2020 International Conference on COMmunication Systems & NETworkS (COMSNETS)* (pp. 555-558). IEEE.

Chaudhuri, D.D. and Yadav, A. (2020) Productivity growth in Indian telecommunications equipment industry. *International Journal of Productivity and Quality Management*, 31(4), pp.508-526.

Bharucha, J. (2018). Social network use and youth well-being: a study in India. *Safer Communities*, 17(2), pp.119–131.

Zhang, X. (2018). Frugal innovation and the digital divide: Developing an extended model of the diffusion of innovations. *International Journal of Innovation Studies*, 2(2), pp.53–64.

Mehta, Y. and Rajan, A.J. (2017) Manufacturing sectors in India: Outlook and challenges. *Procedia engineering*, 174, pp.90-104.

Chopra, S. and Chawla, P. (2018). Innovation, Growth and Intellectual Property: A Study of the Indian Telecom Sector and the Way Forward. *Journal of National Law University Delhi*, 5(1), pp.40–60.

Sarmah, B., Kamboj, S. and Rahman, Z. (2017). Co-creation in hotel service innovation using smart phone apps: an empirical study. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 29(10), pp.2647–2667.

Susanto, H., Chen, C.K. and Almunawar, M.N (2018) Revealing big data emerging technology as enabler of LMS technologies transferability. In *Internet of things and big data analytics toward next-generation intelligence* (pp. 123-145). Springer, Cham.

Venugopal, S, Schulte, S., Janiesch, C., Weber, I. and Hoenisch, P (2015) Elastic Business Process Management: State of the art and open challenges for BPM in the cloud. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 46, pp.36-50.

- Vishwakarma, P., Mukherjee, S. and Datta, B. (2019). Antecedents of Adoption of Virtual Reality in Experiencing Destination: A Study on the Indian Consumers. *Tourism Recreation Research*, 45(1), pp.42–56.
- Gault, F. (2018). Defining and measuring innovation in all sectors of the economy. *Research Policy*, 47(3), pp.617–622.
- Chen, J., Yin, X. and Mei, L. (2018) Holistic innovation: an emerging innovation paradigm. *International Journal of Innovation Studies*, 2(1), pp.1-13.
- Kim, Y., Briley, D.A. and Ocepek, M.G. (2015). Differential innovation of smartphone and application use by sociodemographics and personality. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 44, pp.141–147.
- Cecere, G., Corrocher, N. and Battaglia, R.D. (2015) Innovation and competition in the smartphone industry: Is there a dominant design?. *Telecommunications Policy*, 39(3-4), pp.162-175.
- Kaylynn C. (2019). Strategic Thinking and Effective Change: Samsung - 4728 Words Retrieved from <https://ivy panda.com/essays/strategic-thinking-and-effectivechange-samsung/>
- Yun, J.J., Won, D. and Park, K., 2016. Dynamics from open innovation to evolutionary change. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 2(2), p.7.
- Rao, V.P. and Choudhury, R.R. (2017). A Strategic Imperative for Better Business: Designing the People-Centered Organization. *Asian Journal of Management*, 8(4), p.1247.
- Cecere, G., Corrocher, N. and Battaglia, R.D. (2017) Innovation and competition in the smartphone industry: Is there a dominant design?. *Telecommunications Policy*, 39(3-4), pp.162-175.
- Rosca, M., Lakshminarayanan, B., Warde-Farley, D. and Mohamed, S., 2017. Variational approaches for auto-encoding generative adversarial networks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1706.04987*.
- Geissdoerfer, M., Vladimirova, D. and Evans, S. (2018) Sustainable business model innovation: A review. *Journal of cleaner production*, 198, pp.401-416.
- Chan, A. (2016) *China's workers under assault: Exploitation and abuse in a globalizing economy: exploitation and abuse in a globalizing economy*. Routledge.
- Chan, K.W.C. (2018) Servant Leadership Supports Wellness Development in

- Adolescents. *Servant Leadership: Theory & Practice*, 5(2), p.3.
- Fuentelsaz, L., Maicas, J.P. and Montero, J., 2018. Entrepreneurs and innovation: The contingent role of institutional factors. *International small business journal*, 36(6), pp.686-711.
- Dhir, S. and Dhir, S. (2020). Factor Affecting Innovation Performance of Manufacturing Firms. *International Journal of Asian Business and Information Management*, 11(3), pp.85–100.
- Yun, J.J., Jeon, J., Park, K. and Zhao, X., 2018. Benefits and costs of closed innovation strategy: Analysis of Samsung's Galaxy Note 7 Explosion and withdrawal scandal. *Journal of open innovation: Technology, market, and complexity*, 4(3), p.20.
- Calvosa, P. (2020) Entry, Exit and Innovation over the Industry Life Cycle in Converging Sectors: An Analysis of the Smartphone Industry. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 15(12), p.p151.
- Huang, Y.T. and Shih, K.H. (2017). Customer-based brand equity of smartphone in the emerging market. *International Journal of Mobile Communications*, 15(5), p.467.
- Sharma, M.K. and Sharma, S. (2020) Hypercompetition in the Indian Smartphone Industry: Strategies to Sustain and Scale Up. *IUP Journal of Business Strategy*, 17(2).
- Singh, A.K. (2013) Innovative products and global sourcing: A case study of Micromax Informatics Ltd. *Delhi Business Review*, 14(2), pp.119-120.
- Madhusudan, C. and Panneerselvam, R. (2017) Disruptive Innovation-A Review with Particular Reference to India. *Asian Journal of Management*, 8(4), pp.1370-1378.
- Varriale, V., Cammarano, A., Michelino, F. and Caputo, M. (2021) The role of supplier innovation performance and strategies on the smartphone supply market. *European Management Journal*.
- Jha, M. (2015) A strategic framework for design and implementation of sustainable reverse supply chain with reference to consumer durables. *Asian Journal of Management*, 6(4), pp.342-346.
- Kumar, P.A., Surendrabhoopathi, G. and Kulakarni, S.V. (2013) Current Innovation in Layered Tablet Technology. *Asian Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical Science*, 3(4), pp.189-194.
- Stankovska, A., Dimitrieska, S. and Stamevska, E. (2019) Finance Innovations. *Economics and Management*, 16(2), pp.51-57.
- Rodríguez-López, Á. and Souto, J.E. (2020) Empowering entrepreneurial capacity: training, innovation and business ethics. *Eurasian Business Review*, 10(1), pp.23-43.
- Calvosa, P., 2019. Entry, Exit and Innovation over the Industry Life Cycle in Converging Sectors: An Analysis of the Smartphone Industry. *International Journal of Business and*

Management, 15(12), p.p151.

Hervas-Oliver, J.-L., Sempere-Ripoll, F., Boronat-Moll, C. and Rojas-Alvarado, R. (2017). On the joint effect of technological and management innovations on performance: increasing or diminishing returns? *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 30(5), pp.569–581.

de Solà-Morales, O., Cunningham, D., Flume, M., Overton, P.M., Shalet, N. and Capri, S., 2018. Defining innovation with respect to new medicines: A systematic review from a payer perspective. *International journal of technology assessment in health care*, 34(3), pp.224-240.

Varriale, V., Cammarano, A., Michelino, F. and Caputo, M. (2021). The role of supplier innovation performance and strategies on the smartphone supply market. *European Management Journal*.

Jain, P., Gedam, S.R. and Patil, P.S. (2019). Study of smartphone addiction: prevalence, pattern of use, and personality dimensions among medical students from rural region of central India. *Open Journal of Psychiatry & Allied Sciences*, 10(2), p.132.

Jamalova, M. and Milán, C. (2019). The Comparative Study of the Relationship Between Smartphone Choice and Socio-Economic Indicators. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 11(3), p.11.

Anagha, K. (2018) Role of Innovation Strategy in Organizational Success-The case of Micromax Informatics Ltd. *International Journal of Advances in Social Sciences*, 6(2), pp.139-142.

Mahadevaswamy, P. and D'souza, L. (2016). Prevalence of internet addiction among adolescents in and around Mysore city: influence of select demographic variables. *International Journal of Psychology and Psychiatry*, 4(2), p.1.

Geissdoerfer, M., Vladimirova, D. and Evans, S. (2018) Sustainable business model innovation: A review. *Journal of cleaner production*, 198, pp.401-416.

Dharmadhikari, S., Harshe, S. and Bhide, P. (2019). Prevalence and correlates of excessive smartphone use among medical students: A cross-sectional study. *Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine*, 41(6), p.549.

Raman, A. and Bharadwaj, S.S. (2017). Dynamic service capabilities enabling agile services. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 30(1), pp.166–187.

Arora, S. (2015). Micromax Informatics Ltd: Marketing strategy for emerging markets. *Emerald Emerging Markets Case Studies*, 5(5), pp.1–22.

Raman, P. and Aashish, K. (2020). To continue or not to continue: a structural analysis of

antecedents of mobile payment systems in India. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 39(2), pp.242–271.

Abdullah, M., Zailani, S., Iranmanesh, M. and Jayaraman, K. (2016) Barriers to green innovation initiatives among manufacturers: the Malaysian case. *Review of Managerial Science*, 10(4), pp.683-709.

Adrija (2019) *Why did Micromax fail?*. Available at: <https://www.finnovationz.com/blog/micromax-failure-story#:~:text=There%20are%20several%20factors%20because,of%20the%20Relian>

[ce%20Jio%20G.&text=Micromax%20primarily%20operated%20in%20the,the%202G%20and%203G%20technology](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353111117/Micromax-primarily-operated-in-the-the-2G-and-3G-technology). (Accessed: 26 December 2020).

Agolla, J.E., Makara, T. and Monametsi, G. (2018) Impact of banking innovations on customer attraction, satisfaction and retention: the case of commercial banks in Botswana. *International Journal of Electronic Banking*, 1(2), pp.150-170.

Agwu, U.J., Logvinovskaya, A. and Phetchpinkaw, G. (2017) *Innovation and commercialization potential of university-developed arctic ice-tethered platforms. A case study of research-based technology* (Master's thesis, UiT Norges arktiske universitet).

Ajibade, P. (2018) Technology acceptance model limitations and criticisms: Exploring the practical applications and use in technology-related studies, mixed-method, and qualitative researches. *Library Philosophy & Practice*.

Ambeth Kumar, V.D., Malathi, S., Kumar, A. and Veluvolu, K.C. (2020) Active Volume Control in Smartphones Based on User Activity and Ambient Noise. *Sensors*, 20(15),p.4117.

Anagha, K. (2018) Role of Innovation Strategy in Organizational Success-The case of Micromax Informatics Ltd. *International Journal of Advances in Social Sciences*, 6(2),pp.139-142.

Apanasovich, N., Heras, H.A. and Parrilli, M.D. (2016) The impact of business innovation modes on SME innovation performance in post-Soviet transition economies: The case of Belarus. *Technovation*, 57, pp.30-40.

Arfi, W.B., Hikkerova, L. and Sahut, J.M. (2018) External knowledge sources, green innovation and performance. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 129,pp.210-220.

Aricat, R.G. and Ling, R. (2020) Valuable information on recyclable waste: Mobile phones and the rationalization of the scrap-handling sector in Myanmar. *The Information Society*, 36(5), pp.242-251.

Arora, S. (2015) Micromax Informatics Ltd: Marketing strategy for emerging markets. *Emerald Emerging Markets Case Studies*. Vol. 5 No. 5.

Arpaci, I., Yardimci Cetin, Y. and Turetken, O. (2015) Impact of perceived security on organizational adoption of smartphones. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 18(10), pp.602-608.

Arshad, R., Zahoor, S., Shah, M.A., Wahid, A. and Yu, H. (2017) Green IoT: An investigation on energy saving practices for 2020 and beyond. *IEEE Access*, 5, pp.15667-15681.

Asher, V. (2020) *Smartphone market in India - Statistics & Facts*. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/topics/4600/smartphone-market-in-india/> (Accessed: 24 September 2020).

Atmowardoyo, H. (2018) Research methods in TEFL studies: Descriptive research, case study, error analysis, and R & D. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 9(1), pp.197-204.

Ávila, L.V., Leal Filho, W., Brandli, L., Macgregor, C.J., Molthan-Hill, P., Özuyar, P.G. and Moreira, R.M. (2017) Barriers to innovation and sustainability at universities around the world. *Journal of cleaner production*, 164, pp.1268-1278.

Bagga, T., Goyal, A. and Bansal, S. (2016) An investigative study of the mobile operating system and handset preference. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 35(9), pp.130-138.

Berghaus, S. and Back, A. (2016) September. Stages in Digital Business Transformation: Results of an Empirical Maturity Study. In *MCIS* (p. 22).

Boehmke, B., Hazen, B., Boone, C.A. and Robinson, J.L. (2020) A data science and open source software approach to analytics for strategic sourcing. *International Journal of Information Management*, 54, p.102167.

Bogers, M., Chesbrough, H. and Moedas, C. (2018) Open innovation: research, practices, and policies. *California Management Review*, 60(2), pp.5-16.

Borde, R. (2017) *Evolution Of The Indian Smartphone Landscape: Identifying Key Trends In The Fastest Growing Smartphone Market*. Available at: <https://dazeinfo.com/2017/07/18/smartphone-market-growth-india-2014-2017/>. (Accessed: 24 September 2020).

Bowen, P., Rose, R. and Pilkington, A. (2017) Mixed methods-theory and practice. Sequential, explanatory approach. *International Journal of Quantitative and Qualitative Research Methods*, 5(2), pp.10-27.

Brace, I. (2018) *Questionnaire design: How to plan, structure and write survey material for effective market research*. Kogan Page Publishers.

Brice, A., Burls, A. and Hill, A. (2020) Finding and appraising evidence. *Oxford Handbook of Public Health Practice 4e*, p.142.

Brindha, K. and Elango, L. (2015) Cross comparison of five popular groundwater pollution vulnerability index approaches. *Journal of Hydrology*, 524, pp.597-613.

Callegari, B. (2018) The finance/innovation nexus in Schumpeterian analysis: theory and application to the case of US trustified capitalism. *Journal of Evolutionary Economics*, 28(5), pp.1175-1198.

Cantner, U. and Vannuccini, S. (2018). Elements of a Schumpeterian catalytic research and innovation policy. *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 27(5), pp.833–850.

Cazeaux, C. (2017) *Art, research, philosophy*. Oxfordshire: Taylor & Francis.

Cecere, G., Corrocher, N. and Battaglia, R.D. (2015) Innovation and competition in the smartphone industry: Is there a dominant design?. *Telecommunications Policy*, 39(3-4), pp.162-175.

Chan, M. (2018) Mobile-mediated multimodal communications, relationship quality and subjective well-being: An analysis of smartphone use from a life course perspective. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 87, pp.254-262.

Chandola, V.K. and Fu, H. (2017) Market penetration strategy of smartphone companies from China for India market: a multiple-case study. *International Journal of Business*

Marketing and Management, 2(4), pp.10-16.

Chaudhuri and Yadav (2020) Productivity growth in Indian telecommunications equipment industry. *International Journal of Productivity and Quality Management*, 31(4), pp.508-526.

Chen, J., Han, L. and Qu, G. (2020) Citizen Innovation: Exploring the Responsibility Governance and Cooperative Mode of a "Post-Schumpeter" Paradigm. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 6(4), p.172. Grama, B. and Todericiu, R. (2016) Change, resistance to change and organizational cynicism. *Studies in Business and Economics*, 11(3), pp.47-54.

Chen, Y., Wang, Y., Nevo, S., Benitez-Amado, J. and Kou, G. (2015) IT capabilities and product innovation performance: The roles of corporate entrepreneurship and competitive intensity. *Information & Management*, 52(6), pp.643-657.

Chopra and Chawla (2018) Innovation, growth and intellectual property: a study of the Indian Telecom sector and the way forward. *Journal of National Law University Delhi*, 5(1), pp.40-60.

Cho Yongrae, Gunwoo Yoon, Wonjoon Kim and John Mirikitan (2018). Identifying Innovation strategy by examining Business Ecosystem: Exploratory research on Korea Smart-phone market via network analysis. Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Service Operations, Logistics, and Informatics (SOLI), 10-12 July, Beijing. pp. 208-213.

Christensen, C.M., McDonald, R., Altman, E.J. and Palmer, J.E. (2018) Disruptive innovation: An intellectual history and directions for future research. *Journal of Management Studies*, 55(7), pp.1043-1078.

Christensen, C.M., Raynor, M.E. and McDonald, R. (2015) What is disruptive innovation. *Harvard business review*, 93(12), pp.44-53.

Clarke, V., Braun, V. and Hayfield, N. (2015) Thematic analysis. *Qualitative psychology: A practical guide to research methods*, pp.222-248.

Cornell University (2019) *Global Innovation Index 2019*. Available at: <https://www.wipo.int/publications/en/details.jsp?id=4434> (accessed on September 23,2020)

Counter Point (2019) *India Smartphone Market Share: By Quarter*. Available at: <https://www.counterpointresearch.com/india-smartphone-share/> (Accessed: 28 November 2020).

Croitoru, A. (2017) Schumpeter, Joseph Alois, 1939, "Business Cycles: A Theoretical, Historical, and Statistical Analysis of the Capitalist Process ", New York and London, McGraw–Hill Book Company Inc. *Journal of comparative research in anthropology and sociology*, 8(01), pp.67-80.

De Langhe, R. and Schliesser, E. (2017) Evaluating philosophy as exploratory research. *Metaphilosophy*, 48(3), pp.227-244.

de Solà-Morales, O., Cunningham, D., Flume, M., Overton, P.M., Shalet, N. and Capri, S. (2018) Defining innovation with respect to new medicines: A systematic review from a payer perspective. *International journal of technology assessment in health care*, 34(3), pp.224-240.

Dhir and Dhir (2020) Factor Affecting Innovation Performance of Manufacturing Firms: Case Evidences. *International Journal of Asian Business and Information Management (IJABIM)*, 11(3), pp.85-100.

Doblin (2020) *A FRAMEWORK FOR INNOVATION* Available at: <https://doblin.com/ten-types> (Accessed: 24 December 2020)

Dougherty, M.R., Slevc, L.R. and Grand, J.A. (2019) Making research evaluation more transparent: Aligning research philosophy, institutional values, and reporting. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 14(3), pp.361-375.

Dudley. D. (2019) *The Evolution Of Mobile Phones: 1973 To 2019*. Available at: <https://flauntdigital.com/blog/evolution-mobile-phones/>. (Accessed: 24 September 2020).

Economic Times (2017) *Micromax's profits triples*. Available at: <https://m.economictimes.com/tech/hardware/micromaxs-profit-triples-to-rs-365-8-core-in-fy17/articleshow/61760659.cms> (Accessed: 28 November 2020).

Edquist, C., Zabala-Iturriagagoitia, J.M., Barbero, J. and Zofío, J.L. (2018) On the meaning of innovation performance: Is the synthetic indicator of the Innovation Union Scoreboard flawed?. *Research Evaluation*, 27(3), pp.196-211.

Edson, M.C., Henning, P.B. and Sankaran, S. eds. (2016) *A guide to systems research: Philosophy, processes and practice* (Vol. 10). Abington: Springer.

Edwards, D.M. and Meagher, L.R. (2020) A framework to evaluate the impacts of research on policy and practice: A forestry pilot study. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 114, p.101975.

El Kadiri, S., Grabot, B., Thoben, K.D., Hribernik, K., Emmanouilidis, C., Von Cieminski, G. and Kiritsis, D. (2016) Current trends on ICT technologies for enterprise information systems. *Computers in Industry*, 79, pp.14-33.

Eldridge, S.M., Lancaster, G.A., Campbell, M.J., Thabane, L., Hopewell, S., Coleman, C.L. and Bond, C.M. (2016) Defining feasibility and pilot studies in preparation for randomised controlled trials: development of a conceptual framework. *PloS one*, 11(3), p.e0150205.

Enago academy (2020) *Why is a Pilot Study Important in Research?* Available at: <https://www.enago.com/academy/pilot-study-defines-a-good-research-design/> (Accessed: 24 December, 2020).

Erasmus, E., Rothmann, S. and Van Eeden, C. (2015) A structural model of technology acceptance. *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 41(1), pp.01-12.

Escrivão Filho, E., Albuquerque, A.F., Nagano, M.S., Junior, L.A.P. and de Oliveira, J. (2017) Identifying SME mortality factors in the life cycle stages: an empirical approach of relevant factors for small business owner-managers in Brazil. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 7(1), p.5.

Estrin, S., Korosteleva, J. and Mickiewicz, T. (2020). Schumpeterian Entry: Innovation, Exporting, and Growth Aspirations of Entrepreneurs. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, p.104225872090977.

Fabijan, A., Olsson, H.H. and Bosch, J. (2015) June. Customer feedback and data collection techniques in software R&D: a literature review. In: *International Conference of Software Business*, pp. 139-153. Cham: Springer.

Ferreira, J.J., Fernandes, C.I., Alves, H. and Raposo, M.L. (2015) Drivers of innovation strategies: Testing the Tidd and Bessant (2009) model. *Journal of Business Research*, 68(7), pp.1395-1403.

Firdaus, H. (2016) 4G LTE Network Growth in India and Security Issue in Network. *International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security (IJCSNS)*, 16(11), p.75.

Flick, U. (2015) *Introducing research methodology: A beginner's guide to doing a research project*. London: Sage.

Foss, N.J. and Saebi, T. (2018) Business models and business model innovation: Between wicked and paradigmatic problems. *Long Range Planning*, 51(1), pp.9-21.

Friesen, M.A., Brady, J.M., Milligan, R. and Christensen, P. (2017) Findings from a pilot study: Bringing evidence-based practice to the bedside. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 14(1), pp.22-34.

Fu, N., Flood, P.C., Bosak, J., Morris, T. and O'Regan, P. (2015) How do high performance work systems influence organizational innovation in professional service firms?. *Employee Relations*.

Gault, F. (2018) Defining and measuring innovation in all sectors of the economy. *Research policy*, 47(3), pp.617-622.

Gaur, A. and Kumar, M. (2018) A systematic approach to conducting review studies: An assessment of content analysis in 25 years of IB research. *Journal of World Business*, 53(2), pp.280-289.

Geissdoerfer, M., Vladimirova, D. and Evans, S. (2018) Sustainable business model innovation: A review. *Journal of cleaner production*, 198, pp.401-416.

Gill, P. and Baillie, J. (2018) Interviews and focus groups in qualitative research: an update for the digital age. *British dental journal*, 225(7), pp.668-672.

Gray, D.E. (2019) *Doing research in the business world*. London: Sage Publications Limited.

Gundry, D. and Deterding, S. (2019) Validity threats in quantitative data collection with games: A narrative survey. *Simulation & Gaming*, 50(3), pp.302-328.

Gupta, H. and Barua, M.K. (2016) Identifying enablers of technological innovation for Indian MSMEs using best–worst multi criteria decision making method. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 107, pp.69-79.

G., T. (2020). Consumers' Preference towards the Usage of Organic and Non Organic Food Products. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(5), pp.2362–2366.

Hameed, W.U., Nisar, Q.A. and Wu, H.C. (2020) Relationships between external knowledge, internal innovation, firms' open innovation performance, service innovation and business performance in the Pakistani hotel industry. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 92, p.102745.

Haq (2017) Impact of reliance JIO on the Indian telecom industry. *International Journal of Engineering and Management Research (IJEMR)*, 7(3), pp.259-263.

Hazzi, O. and Maldaon, I. (2015) A pilot study: Vital methodological issues. *Business: Theory and Practice*, 16(1), pp.53-62.

He, P., Feng, H., Hu, G., Hewage, K., Achari, G., Wang, C. and Sadiq, R. (2020) Life cycle cost analysis for recycling high-tech minerals from waste mobile phones in China. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 251, p.119498.

Hoffman, H., Rice, C. and Skordalakes, E. (2017) Structural analysis reveals the deleterious effects of telomerase mutations in bone marrow failure syndromes. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 292(11), pp.4593-4601.

Hubert, M., Blut, M., Brock, C., Backhaus, C. and Eberhardt, T. (2017) Acceptance of smartphone-based mobile shopping: Mobile benefits, customer characteristics, perceived risks, and the impact of application context. *Psychology & Marketing*, 34(2), pp.175-194.

Hughes, J.A. and Sharrock, W.W. (2016) *The philosophy of social research*. Routledge.

Ibarra, D., Ganzarain, J. and Igartua, J.I. (2018) Business model innovation through Industry 4.0: A review. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 22, pp.4-10.

iPhone 12 Pro (2020) *It's a leap year..* Available at: <https://www.apple.com/in/iphone-12-pro/?afid=p238%7CsABiwcts2->

[dc_mtId_20925gyh65756_pcrId_476224261859_pgrId_119810616188_&cid=wwa- in-
kwgo-iphone-slid--Brand-iPhone12Pro-Tradein-](https://www.in-kwgo-iphone-slid--Brand-iPhone12Pro-Tradein-) (Accessed: 10 December 2020).

Istrate, C., Blaga, M. and Herghiligi, I.V. (2017) September. Methodological Framework Regarding Knowledge Innovation Matrix Development. In *European Conference on Knowledge Management* (pp. 1286-1291). Academic Conferences International Limited.

Jakhar, M. and Bharadwaj, S.S. (2018) Agile Capabilities for Innovative and Imitating Firms: A Framework for Mobile Handset Industry. *Journal of Management Research*, 18(2), pp.114-126.

Jenson, I., Leith, P., Doyle, R., West, J. and Miles, M.P. (2016) Innovation system problems: Causal configurations of innovation failure. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(11), pp.5408-5412.

Jung, J.H. (2017) Analysis on pre-service early childhood teachers' stage of concerns about software education according to the concerns-based adoption model. *Journal of the Korea Academia-Industrial Cooperation Society*, 18(7), pp.431-440.

Junyong In (2017) Introduction of a pilot study *Korean journal of Anesthesiology*, 70(6), pp. 601-605.

Kahn, K.B. (2018) Understanding innovation. *Business Horizons*, 61(3), pp.453-460.

Kaplan, S. and Vakili, K. (2015) The double-edged sword of recombination in breakthrough innovation. *Strategic Management Journal*, 36(10), pp.1435-1457.

Khandelwal, N. (2020) *Understanding Doblin's 10 types of innovations with examples* Available at: <https://medium.com/@hwabtnoname/understanding-doblin-s-10-types-of-innovations-with-examples-2da595cea601> (Accessed: 24 December 2020)

Kiani, S.H., Altaf, A., Abdullah, M., Muhammad, F., Shoaib, N., Anjum, M.R., Damaševičius, R. and Blažauskas, T. (2020) Eight element side edged framed MIMO antenna array for future 5G smartphones. *Micromachines*, 11(11), p.956.

Kianto, A., Sáenz, J. and Aramburu, N. (2017) Knowledge-based human resource management practices, intellectual capital and innovation. *Journal of Business Research*, 81, pp.11-20.

Kumar, R. (2019) *Research methodology: A step-by-step guide for beginners*. London: Sage Publications Limited.

Kundu, V.A. (2020) *Micromax Comeback: Can Micromax 'In' Phones Work? Should Xiaomi, Realme, Oppo, Vivo Worry?*. Available at: <https://trak.in/tags/business/2020/10/17/micromax-comeback-can-micromax-in-phones-work-should-xiaomi-realme-oppo-vivo-worry/> (Accessed: 28 November 2020).

Kyffin, S. and Gardien, P. (2009) Navigating the innovation matrix: An approach to design-led innovation. *International Journal of Design*, 3(1).

Laport-López, F., Serrano, E., Bajo, J. and Campbell, A.T. (2020) A review of mobile sensing systems, applications, and opportunities. *Knowledge and Information Systems*, 62(1), pp.145-174.

Läpple, D., Renwick, A. and Thorne, F. (2015) Measuring and understanding the drivers of agricultural innovation: Evidence from Ireland. *Food Policy*, 51, pp.1-8.

Livemint (2014) *How Micromax made it big in India*. Available at: <https://www.livemint.com/Industry/HAdRsdSfeXc5D3vuX6ojvO/How-Micromax-made-it-big-in-India.html> (Accessed: 28 November 2020).

Livemint (2020) *Micromax prepares for a second coming*. Available at: <https://www.livemint.com/companies/news/micromax-prepares-for-a-second-coming-11602901574435.html> (Accessed: 28 November 2020).

Lobe, B., Morgan, D. and Hoffman, K.A. (2020) Qualitative data collection in an era of social distancing. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 19, p.1609406920937875.

Lovarelli, D. and Bacenetti, J. (2017) Bridging the gap between reliable data collection and the environmental impact for mechanised field operations. *Biosystems engineering*, 160, pp.109-123.

Mackieson, P., Shlonsky, A. and Connolly, M. (2019) Increasing rigor and reducing bias in qualitative research: A document analysis of parliamentary debates using applied thematic analysis. *Qualitative Social Work*, 18(6), pp.965-980.

Mageswari, S.U., Sivasubramanian, C. and Dath, T.S. (2015) Knowledge management enablers, processes and innovation in small manufacturing firms: A structural equation modeling approach. *IUP Journal of Knowledge Management*, 13(1), p.33.

Malerba, F. and McKelvey, M. (2020) Knowledge-intensive innovative entrepreneurship integrating Schumpeter, evolutionary economics, and innovation systems. *Small Business Economics*, 54(2), pp.503-522.

Mankowski, P.J., Kanevsky, J., Bakirtzian, P. and Cugno, S. (2016) Cellular phone collateral damage: A review of burns associated with lithium battery powered mobile devices. *Burns*, 42(4), pp.e61-e64.

Marangunić, N. and Granić, A. (2015) Technology acceptance model: a literature review from 1986 to 2013. *Universal access in the information society*, 14(1), pp.81- 95.

Mardani, A., Nikoosokhan, S., Moradi, M. and Doustar, M. (2018) The relationship between knowledge management and innovation performance. *The Journal of High Technology Management Research*, 29(1), pp.12-26.

Mashayekhi, B. and Haji Azimi, F. (2018) Managerial ability and company performance in life cycle stages. *Empirical Research in Accounting*, 8(1), pp.29-54.

McDowell, D.L. and Kalidindi, S.R. (2016) The materials innovation ecosystem: a key enabler for the materials genome initiative. *Mrs Bulletin*, 41(4), pp.326-337.

McLain, C. and Kim, J. (2018) Ethical issues in qualitative data collection. In *Ensuring Research Integrity and the Ethical Management of Data* (pp. 112-126). IGI Global.

Mehta and Rajan (2017) Manufacturing sectors in India: outlook and challenges.

Procedia engineering, 174, pp.90-104.

Milner, R. and Furnham, A. (2017) Measuring customer feedback, response and satisfaction. *Psychology*, 8(3), pp.350-362.

Min, M. (2017) Teachers who initiate changes with an ebook-integrated curriculum: Revisiting the developmental assumptions of stages of concerns in the concerns- based adoption model. *Alberta Journal of Educational Research*, 63(1), pp.21-42.

Mobility India (2016) “*Micromax always brings latest and future-ready technologies to Indian consumers*”. Available at: <https://www.mobilityindia.com/micromax-always-brings-latest-and-future-ready-technologies-to-indian-consumers/> (Accessed: 25 December 2020).

Moon, K., Blackman, D.A., Adams, V.M., Colvin, R.M., Davila, F., Evans, M.C., Januchowski-Hartley, S.R., Bennett, N.J., Dickinson, H., Sandbrook, C. and Sherren, K. (2019) Expanding the role of social science in conservation through an engagement with philosophy, methodology, and methods. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 10(3), pp.294-302.

Munawar, S., Toor, S.K., Aslam, M. and Hamid, M. (2018) Move to smart learning environment: exploratory research of challenges in computer laboratory and design intelligent virtual laboratory for eLearning Technology. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 14(5), pp.1645-1662.

Mura, L., Machová, R. and Tóth, Z. (2015) Evaluation of the innovation performance of business networks. In *CERS 2014: 5th Central European Conference in Regional Science, International Conference Proceedings* (pp. 634-642).

Namboodiri, S., Banerjee, S. and Dasgupta, H. (2019) A coherent metasynthesis of blue ocean strategy (bos) using grounded theory approach. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 18(4), pp.1-18.

Naranjo-Valencia, J.C., Jiménez-Jiménez, D. and Sanz-Valle, R. (2016) Studying the links between organizational culture, innovation, and performance in Spanish companies. *Revista Latinoamericana de Psicología*, 48(1), pp.30-41

Narayanan, A., Ramadan, E., Carpenter, J., Liu, Q., Liu, Y., Qian, F. and Zhang, Z.L. (2020) A First Look at Commercial 5G Performance on Smartphones. In *Proceedings of The Web Conference 2020* (pp. 894-905).

NDTV Gadgets (2020a) *Samsung phones*. Available at: <https://gadgets.ndtv.com/mobiles/samsung-phones> (Accessed: 10 December 2020).

NDTV Gadgets (2020b) *Best camera mobile phones*. Available at: <https://gadgets.ndtv.com/mobiles/best-camera-phones> (Accessed: 10 December 2020).

Nekmahmud, M., Rahman, M.F., Huq, S.M. and Rahman, S. (2017) Generation Y Consumer's Attitude towards the Uses of Smartphone in Northern Area of Bangladesh. *Australian Academy of Business and Economics Review*, 3(4), pp.207- 223.

Nimmagadda, S.L., Reiners, T. and Wood, L.C. (2018) On big data-guided upstream business research and its knowledge management. *Journal of Business Research*, 89, pp.143-158.

Panda (2017) Growth and competitiveness of telecom sector in India: an overview. *TRANS Asian Journal of Marketing & Management Research (TAJMMR)*, 6(12), pp.70-76.

Parmar (2020) Rise of Rural Consumers in Developing Countries: Harvesting 3 Billion Aspirations. *South Asian Journal of Management*, 27(2), pp.217-220.

Pathak, T. (2019) *Mobile handset market in India*. Available at: <https://indiaincgroup.com/mobile-handset-market-india/>. (Accessed: 24 September 2020).

Petrovčič, A., Taipale, S., Rogelj, A. and Dolničar, V. (2018) Design of mobile phones for older adults: An empirical analysis of design guidelines and checklists for feature phones and smartphones. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 34(3), pp.251-264.

Piening, E.P. and Salge, T.O. (2015) Understanding the antecedents, contingencies, and performance implications of process innovation: A dynamic capabilities perspective. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 32(1), pp.80-97.

Pope, Z., Lee, J.E., Zeng, N., Lee, H.Y. and Gao, Z. (2019) Feasibility of smartphone application and social media intervention on breast cancer survivors' health outcomes. *Translational behavioral medicine*, 9(1), pp.11-22.

Presbitero, A., Roxas, B. and Chadee, D. (2017) Sustaining innovation of information technology service providers. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*.

Pringle Barnes, G. and Cheng, M. (2019) Working independently on the dissertation proposal: experiences of international Master's students. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 43(8), pp.1120-1132.

Pustulka, P., Bell, J. and Trajka, A. (2019) Questionable Insiders: Changing Positionalities of Interviewers throughout Stages of Migration Research. *Field Methods*, 31(3), pp.241-259.

Qutoshi, S.B. (2018) Phenomenology: A philosophy and method of inquiry. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 5(1), pp.215-222.

Rahi, S. (2017) Research design and methods: A systematic review of research paradigms, sampling issues and instruments development. *International Journal of Economics & Management Sciences*, 6(2), pp.1-5.

Rajasekaran, R., Cindhana, S. and Anandha Priya, C. (2018) Consumers Perception and Preference Towards Smartphone. *ICTACT Journal on Management Studies*, 4(3), pp.788-792.

Raman and Aashish (2020) Think Global and Buy Global: The Influence of Global Identity on Indian Consumers' Behaviour toward Chinese Smartphone Brands. *Journal of Global Marketing*, pp.1-20.

Ramírez-Montoya, M.S. and García-Peñalvo, F.J. (2018) Co-creation and open innovation: Systematic literature review.

Rasche, P., Mertens, A., Brandl, C., Liu, S., Buecking, B., Bliemel, C., Horst, K., Weber, C.D., Lichte, P. and Knobe, M. (2018) Satisfying Product Features of a Fall Prevention Smartphone App and Potential Users' Willingness to Pay: Web-Based Survey Among Older Adults. *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 6(3), p.e75.

Ravichandran and Devi (2017) EFFECTIVE BRAND BUILDING. *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 8(1).

Ricciardi, F., Zardini, A. and Rossignoli, C. (2016) Organizational dynamism and adaptive business model innovation: The triple paradox configuration. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(11), pp.5487-5493.

Ritala, P., Olander, H., Michailova, S. and Husted, K. (2015) Knowledge sharing, knowledge leaking and relative innovation performance: An empirical study. *Technovation*, 35, pp.22-31.

Rosca, E., Arnold, M. and Bendul, J.C. (2017) Business models for sustainable innovation— an empirical analysis of frugal products and services. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 162, pp.S133-S145.

Sadan, V. (2017) Data collection methods in quantitative research. *Indian Journal of Continuing Nursing Education*, 18(2), p.58.

Saebi, T. and Foss, N.J. (2015) Business models for open innovation: Matching heterogeneous open innovation strategies with business model dimensions. *European Management Journal*, 33(3), pp.201-213.

Saeidi, S.P., Sofian, S., Saeidi, P., Saeidi, S.P. and Saaeidi, S.A. (2015) How does corporate social responsibility contribute to firm financial performance? The mediating

role of competitive advantage, reputation, and customer satisfaction. *Journal of business research*, 68(2), pp.341-350.

Sağbaşı, E.A., Korukoglu, S. and Ballı, S. (2020) Stress detection via keyboard typing behaviors by using smartphone sensors and machine learning techniques. *Journal of Medical Systems*, 44(4), pp.1-12.

Saini, S. (2018) Difference in Customer Expectations and Perceptions towards Electric Utility Company. *National Journal of multidisciplinary research and management*, 3(1), pp.264-269.

Sakkthivel, A.M., Moovendhan, V. and Heggde, G.S. (2020) Investigating the relationship between age and smartphone usage patterns: evidences from Indian smartphone users. *International Journal of Business Excellence*, 21(3), pp.394-409.

Saleem, T. and Mehmood, N. (2018) Assessing the Quality of Supervision Experiences in the Different Research Stages at Postgraduate Level. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 5(2), pp.8-27.

Sandnes, F.E. and Eika, E. (2018) January. Statistics-IDE: Supporting the design of empirical experiments for non-experts during early stages of research projects. In *International Conference on Intelligent Human Systems Integration*, pp. 502-507.

Santoro, G., Bresciani, S. and Papa, A. (2020) Collaborative modes with cultural and creative industries and innovation performance: the moderating role of heterogeneous sources of knowledge and absorptive capacity. *Technovation*, 92, p.102040.

Scarpellini, S., Marín-Vinuesa, L.M., Portillo-Tarragona, P. and Moneva, J.M. (2018) Defining and measuring different dimensions of financial resources for business eco-innovation and the influence of the firms' capabilities. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 204, pp.258-269.

Schabenberger, O. and Gotway, C.A. (2017) *Statistical methods for spatial data analysis*. New York City: Chapman and Hall/CRC.

Schilling, M.A. and Shankar, R. (2019) *Strategic management of technological innovation*. New York: McGraw-Hill Education.

Schoonenboom, J. and Johnson, R.B. (2017) How to construct a mixed methods research design. *KZfSS Kölner Zeitschrift für Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie*, 69(2),pp.107-131.

Scott, S. and McGuire, J. (2017) Using Diffusion of Innovation Theory to Promote Universally Designed College Instruction. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 29(1), pp.119-128.

Scuotto, V., Del Giudice, M. and Carayannis, E.G. (2017) The effect of social networking sites and absorptive capacity on SMES'innovation performance. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 42(2), pp.409-424.

Shabrin, N., Khandaker, S., Kashem, S.B.A., Hie, C.K. and Susila, T. (2017) Factors affecting smartphone purchase decisions of Generation-Y. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government, The*, 23(1), p.47.

Sharma (2017) Building customer-based brand equity of domestic brands: Role of brand equity dimensions. *Metamorphosis*, 16(1), pp.45-59.

Sharma and Sharma (2020) Hypercompetition in the Indian Smartphone Industry: Strategies to Sustain and Scale Up. *IUP Journal of Business Strategy*, 17(2).

Siedlecki, S.L. (2020) Understanding Descriptive Research Designs and Methods. *Clinical Nurse Specialist*, 34(1), pp.8-12.

Silva, A.T., Moro, S., Rita, P. and Cortez, P. (2018) Unveiling the features of successful eBay smartphone sellers. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 43, pp.311- 324.

Sing, J. (2019) *DMicromax profits took a nosedive in FY18; revenue declined by 26%*. Available at: <https://entrackr.com/2019/01/micromax-revenue-fy18/> (Accessed: 28 November 2020).

Singh (2019) Enticements to Invent: A Quick fix for Standards-Essential Patents. *GLS Law Journal*, 1(1), pp.43-56.

Singhania, M. and Jaitly, A. (2017) March. Mobile Governance in India: Innovative Sustainable Business Modelling. In *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Electronic Governance* (pp. 544-545).

Sivarajah, U., Kamal, M.M., Irani, Z. and Weerakkody, V. (2017) Critical analysis of Big Data challenges and analytical methods. *Journal of Business Research*, 70, pp.263-286.

Spittle, A.J., Olsen, J., Kwong, A., Doyle, L.W., Marschik, P.B., Einspieler, C. and Cheong, J.L.Y. (2016) The Baby Moves prospective cohort study protocol: using a smartphone application with the General Movements Assessment to predict neurodevelopmental outcomes at age 2 years for extremely preterm or extremely low birthweight infants. *BMJ open*, 6(10), p.e013446.

Subedi, D. (2016) Explanatory sequential mixed method design as the third research community of knowledge claim. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 4(7), pp.570-577.

Sudevan, P. (2019) *How smartphones have changed our lives in the last 10 years*. Available at: <https://www.thehindu.com/sci-tech/technology/how-smartphones-have-changed-our-lives-in-the-last-10-years/article30434182.ece>. (Accessed: 24 September 2020).

Suifan, T. (2020) How innovativeness mediates the effects of organizational culture and leadership on performance. *International Journal of Innovation Management*, p.2150016.

Sujata, J., Yatin, J., Abhijit, C., Noopur, S. and Ruchi, D. (2016) Factors affecting smartphone purchase among indian youth: A descriptive analysis. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 9(15), pp.1-10.

Sundararaj, J. (2015) Brand Loyalty towards Smartphones—A Descriptive Study. *International Journal of Advanced Scientific Research & Development (IJASRD)*, 2(2), pp.477-482.

Suroso, E. and Azis, Y. (2015) Defining mainstreams of innovation: a literature review. In *International Conference on Economics and Banking (iceb-15)*. London: Atlantis Press.

Swendeman, D., Ramanathan, N., Baetscher, L., Medich, M., Scheffler, A., Comulada, W.S. and Estrin, D. (2015) Smartphone self-monitoring to support self-management among people living with HIV: perceived benefits and theory of change from a mixed-methods, randomized pilot study. *Journal of acquired immune deficiency syndromes (1999)*, 69(0 1), p.S80.

Tavassoli, S. and Karlsson, C. (2016) Innovation strategies and firm performance: Simple or complex strategies?. *Economics of Innovation and New Technology*, 25(7), pp.631-650.

Tech World Times (2020) *5 Reason That Made Micromax Failure*. Available at: <https://techworldtimes.com/5-reason-that-made-micromax-failure/> (Accessed: 28 November 2020).

Teece, D.J. and Linden, G. (2017) Business models, value capture, and the digital enterprise. *Journal of Organization Design*, 6(1), pp.1-14.

The Economic Times (2019) *Domestic mobile phone makers' revenues hit by Chinese companies*. Available at: <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/tech/hardware/domestic-mobile-phone-makers-revenues-hit-by-chinese-companies/articleshow/68770237.cms?from=mdr> (Accessed: 28 November 2020).

The Hindu (2020) *Micromax eyes comeback, to invest 500 cr.*. Available at: <https://www.thehindu.com/business/Industry/micromax-eyes-comeback-to-invest-500-cr/article32876347.ece> (Accessed: 28 November 2020).

The Hindu Business (2019) *As Chinese phones ring louder, Micromax sees 76% decline in profits*. Available at: <https://www.thehindubusinessline.com/info-tech/as-chinese-phones-ring-louder-micromax-sees-76-decline-in-profits/article25952282.ece> (Accessed: 28 November 2020).

Thimmaiah, N. (2016) The notion of 'Make In India': issues and challenges. *Afro Asian Journal of Anthropology and Social Policy*, 7(2), pp.23-27.

THOMAS, O.O. and LAWAL, O.R. (2020) Exploratory Research Design in Management Sciences: An X-Ray of Literature. *Annals of the University Dunarea de Jos of Galati: Fascicle: I, Economics & Applied Informatics*, 26(2).

Tobi, H. and Kampen, J.K. (2018) Research design: the methodology for interdisciplinary research framework. *Quality & quantity*, 52(3), pp.1209-1225.

Torugsa, N. and Arundel, A. (2016) Complexity of innovation in the public sector: A workgroup-level analysis of related factors and outcomes. *Public Management Review*, 18(3), pp.392-416.

Trapani, B. and Annunziato, A. (2019) Crossing the Bridge of Change: Measuring Instructional Change Using the Concerns Based Adoption Model. *Journal for Leadership and Instruction*, 18(1), pp.12-16.

Tripathi, S. (2018) The erring trends shaping Indian FRAND case law: towards a new approach. *Journal of Intellectual Property Law & Practice*, 13(3), pp.186-193.

Tsinopoulos, C., Sousa, C.M. and Yan, J. (2018) Process innovation: open innovation and the moderating role of the motivation to achieve legitimacy. *Journal of product innovation management*, 35(1), pp.27-48.

Valle, A.M., Santos, E.A. and Loures, E.R. (2017) Applying process mining techniques in software process appraisals. *Information and software technology*, 87, pp.19-31.

Venugopala, P.S., Nayak, A.A., Sarojadevi, H. and Chiplunkar, N.N. (2015) December. Various challenges in video watermarking for Android mobile devices.

In *2015 International Conference on Information Processing (ICIP)*, pp. 248-253. Pennsylvania: IEEE.

Vikram, K. and Ramanathan, K.V. (2015) A study on smartphone industry and their effects on indian market an over view. *Asia Pacific Journal of Research* Vol: I. Issue XXV.

Vuori, T.O. and Huy, Q.N. (2016) Distributed attention and shared emotions in the innovation process: How Nokia lost the smartphone battle. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 61(1), pp.9-51.

Walk Through India (2019) *Top 10 Trusted Indian Mobile Brands and Companies*. Available at:<http://www.walkthroughindia.com/industry/top-10-trusted-indian-mobile-brands-and-companies/> (Accessed: 28 November 2020).

Walk Through India (2020) *Top 10 Most Popular Smartphone*. Available at:<http://www.walkthroughindia.com/hot-trends/top-10-most-popular-smartphone-companies-in-india/> (Accessed: 28 November 2020).

Wan, F., Williamson, P.J. and Yin, E. (2015) Antecedents and implications of disruptive innovation: Evidence from China. *Technovation*, 39, pp.94-104.

Wang, C., Yi, J., Kafouros, M. and Yan, Y. (2015) Under what institutional conditions do business groups enhance innovation performance?. *Journal of Business Research*, 68(3), pp.694-702.

Wilson, C. and Tyfield, D. (2018) Critical perspectives on disruptive innovation and energy transformation. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 37, pp.211-215.

Witell, L., Snyder, H., Gustafsson, A., Fombelle, P. and Kristensson, P. (2016) Defining service innovation: A review and synthesis. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(8), pp.2863-2872.

Yates, J. and Leggett, T. (2016) Qualitative research: An introduction. *Radiologic technology*, 88(2), pp.225-231.

Zhai, Y.M., Sun, W.Q., Tsai, S.B., Wang, Z., Zhao, Y. and Chen, Q. (2018) An empirical study on entrepreneurial orientation, absorptive capacity, and SMEs' innovation performance: A sustainable perspective. *Sustainability*, 10(2), p.314.

Zhang, D., Sun, X., Liu, Y., Zhou, S. and Zhang, H. (2018) The effects of integrative leadership on the enterprise synergy innovation performance in a supply chain cooperative network. *Sustainability*, 10(7), p.2342.

Zhang, G., Wang, X., Duan, H. and Zheng, L.J. (2020) How do new entrants' pre- entry technological backgrounds impact their cross-industry innovation performances? A retrospective study of the mobile phone vendors. *Technovation*, p.102176.

Zhang, X., Yu, P., Yan, J. and Spil, I.T.A. (2015) Using diffusion of innovation theory to understand the factors impacting patient acceptance and use of consumer e-health innovations: a case study in a primary care clinic. *BMC health services research*, 15(1), p.71.

Zhao, S., Sun, Y. and Xu, X. (2016) Research on open innovation performance: a review. *Information technology and management*, 17(3), pp.279-287.

Zhao, Y., Xu, X. and Wang, M. (2019) Predicting overall customer satisfaction: Big data evidence from hotel online textual reviews. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 76, pp.111-121.